
THE RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN DIFFERENT BEHAVIOURAL FACTORS, MOTIVATIONS AND CRYPTO INVESTOR'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Over the course of its brief existence, cryptocurrencies have been playing a crucial part in changing the way people once knew about money. They are known as digital currencies which are fully decentralised and are run by no one. This means that no governmental bodies are required for their issuance and no banks are needed to manage accounts and verify transactions. Since BTC is the first crypto to be released, literature have found the market efficiency to increase over time. However, the cryptocurrency market is still considered to be highly inefficient. By looking for an alternative theory to traditional finance which assume financial markets are efficient, behavioural finance is chosen as a conventional theory. Behavioural finance argues that investors are humans with different level of emotions and are prone to behavioural biases.

The main objective of this research is to assess the direct impacts of different behavioural finance factors on crypto investors' performance. The behavioural biases can be categorised within heuristics, prospect theory and herding. Under heuristics perspective, overconfidence, anchoring and adjustment, and availability biases are examined. Under prospect theory, loss aversion, regret aversion and mental accounting are further focused to study their influence with crypto investment performance. Moreover, this paper also seeks to find a direct relationship between different types of motivation and crypto investment performance. To the author's knowledge, prior research on behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market remains to be very limited which leaves a gap for further fulfilment.

The study begins with a comprehensive literature review on behavioural finance and the cryptocurrency market which then is followed by the construction of research hypotheses and conceptual framework. Subsequently, the research hypotheses are tested using a sample of 264 retail crypto investors using voluntary response sampling, structured questionnaires, and multiple regression model. The sampled data is then

analysed by the STATA software. Cronbach's alpha is also adopted to test the reliability of the collected responses.

Researching findings consists of four different behavioural factors namely overconfidence, availability, mental accounting, and herding to have a significant and positive influence on crypto investors' performance. On the other hand, loss aversion, regret aversion and anchoring bias are found to have an insignificant effect on crypto investment performance. Motivation variable which is established in the form of a dummy variable returns a significant result and is positively correlated with crypto investors' performance. This research further attempts to provide on corporate and retail implications as well as look to contribute to policy makers for more consumer protection.

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION

When the internet first emerged in the early 1990s, many individuals struggled to understand and exert control over it. Even though the internet was still a relatively young convention, there had already been some intelligent individuals who were familiar with it and have come to the realisation that it has the potential to be a very useful space. They referred to themselves as Cypherpunks (Avdeychik and Capozzi, 2018). Later on, John Gilmore, Timothy May, and Eric Hughes, who claimed to be “cypherpunks” and activist cryptographers, established an organisation with the same name (Avdeychik and Capozzi, 2018). They were supporters of online privacy and have a libertarianism mindset which endorses full control over their money (Bartlett, 2016). By using cryptography, May proposed the idea of secure crypto-currencies which can aid anonymity and freedom in browsing as well as exchanging items under a third party’s radar (Bartlett, 2006). However, the first emergence of cryptocurrency and a decentralised money system did not happen up till 2009 when an individual known as Satoshi Nakamoto first introduced Bitcoin (BTC) to the public (Frisby, 2014). Until now, an enormous number of cryptocurrencies have been born and countless number of blockchain applications are freely accessible.

Since the emergence of various new cryptocurrencies, a huge extent of traditional finance operations are considered to be facing a continuous threat as a result. Cryptocurrencies offer the decentralised feature where no intermediate party is needed; this can cause traditional financial institutions such as a bank to cease as users can transfer to each other directly. In fact, the purpose of a crypto wallet is identical as that of a bank account. With the reality which involves about 1.4 billion people across the world remaining unbanked (WorldBank, 2022), cryptocurrencies could potentially set out a financial revolution and change the way people know about money.

Blockchain is known as the underlying technology used to support cryptocurrencies and also created by Nakamoto (Natarajan, Krause and Gradstein, 2017). It was firstly built to keep track of BTC ownership and transaction data on a decentralised ledger or digital blocks distributed among billions of computers worldwide (Natarajan et al. 2017). This set of computers act as transaction verifiers and can validate them in matters of seconds or minutes (Griffith and Grigg, 2014). Moreover, by recording all transaction information on the blockchain network, it is considered to be impossible to alter them (Guo and Yu, 2022). This technology has essentially eliminated the trust element between the payment maker and receiver. Altogether with decentralisation, a transaction made with a cryptocurrency on a blockchain network can guarantee a high level of trusting confidence.

Despite being tradable since 2009, BTC only began to gain more attention a few years later. In 2013, its market capitalisation reached \$1 billion and subsequently in 2021, it reached its all-time-high market capitalisation at over \$1,000 billion (Statista, 2022a). After the significant growth of BTC, more cryptocurrencies, also known as alt-coins, were born and shortly became available to be traded publicly. The second largest cryptocurrency by price and market capitalisation at the time of writing is Ether (ETH) which is built on the blockchain Ethereum. The greatest difference associated with BTC and ETH is that BTC was designed to be a form of money and store of wealth whereas the Ethereum network is built to optimise smart contracts and decentralised applications (dApps). Apart from BTC and ETH, there is an estimation of about 22,000 other cryptocurrencies, bringing the whole cryptocurrency market capitalisation to approximately \$850 billion (Forbes, 2022).

Besides from the decentralised unique feature that is associated with cryptocurrencies, investors are also understood to be motivated by other reasons; these motivations have been found to produce certain impacts to the market. Lee, Li and Zheng (2020) found that there are mainly two types of crypto investors which are speculators and technology enthusiasts. The researchers found speculators follow momentum strategy during high volatility and then switch to contrarian during low volatility. Technology

enthusiasts on the other hand remain consistently buying (selling) under (above) their expected prices. Smutny, Sulc and Lansky (2021) identified anonymity, difficulty in seizing crypto assets and anti-inflation characteristics to be the main motivations of crypto investors apart from gaining profits.

Bashir, Strickland and Bohr (2016) demonstrated that different motivations could come from varied aspects of wealth, technology, politics and social structure. Khairuddin, Sas, Clinch and Davies (2016) highlights the importance of the decentralisation system, democracy and financial reformation and their impact in creating a financial revolution. Greater profits, ease of exchanging, ideology support, incline to gain investment skills as well as trading experience, and a risk seeking mentality are also found to be different types of motivations in participating in the cryptocurrency market (Mattke, Maier, Reis and Weitzel, 2020).

These crypto motivation studies are understood to have aggregately developed two types of motivations: non-fundamental type and fundamental type. The fundamental type can be considered to be anyone who has strong interest in the underlying technology and characteristics, the freedom of exchange, control of money and could have libertarian mindsets. In some ways, investors with the fundamental motivations can be activists against the traditional banking system. The non-fundamental type can be considered to be simply speculators. Accordingly, this study looks to group the motivations into two primary types: increasing wealth (1) and belief in decentralisation, blockchain, free market and democratising wealth (2).

Previous studies have identified the BTC remained consistently an inefficient market from the early stages; however, it has gained greater efficiency across the years (Urquhart, 2016; Bariviera, 2017; Aggarwal, 2019; Wei, 2018). However, markets associated with other cryptocurrencies have been evidently found to not have the same condition (Kristoufek and Vosvrda, 2019; Charfeddine and Maouchi, 2019; Hu, Valera and Oxley (2019); Zhang, Pengfei, Xiao and Dehua, 2018). The authors agreed that the

cryptocurrency market as a whole remains to be highly inefficient due to the significant amount of new cryptocurrencies that could emerge in such a short period of time. Since the market as a whole has been documented to be inefficient, it is not appropriate to apply a traditional finance model to study the market. As a result, behavioural finance as a conventional theory is considered to act as a tool to understand the cryptocurrency market alternatively.

In traditional finance theory, it is believed by economic theorists that every investor is a rational thinker and processes all available information while placing buy and sell orders (Siegel, 2007; Subramaniam and Velnampy, 2017). The theory suggests that by behaving rationally, all financial securities should be fairly valued and leave no room for undervaluation or overvaluation (Fama, 1970). Accordingly, rational investors cannot see any potential opportunities to achieve abnormal returns. A rational choice theory or expected utility theory therefore have been derived to model the way a rational decision maker works, using Bernoulli's principle and the Von-Neuman and Morgenstern theorem (Fishburn, 1989).

Beside from the belief that all investors act rationally, there are also some assumptions made in traditional finance theory, namely a random walk and the efficient market hypothesis (EMH). A random walk assumes that future stock prices are independent from past prices so that the predicting probability for potential movements should be fifty percent; while EMH states that public information is reflected in the asset prices immediately once released and it is impossible to achieve abnormal returns without accepting the above average risks (Malkiel, 1973; Fama, 1970). Nonetheless, EMH has been challenged for a long period of time by practical phenomena such as market bubbles and fund managers who have consistently been beating the stock market. This led to the lack of confidence in the traditional finance theory and an alternative to that has been introduced - the behavioural finance theory.

Sevil, Sen and Yalama (2007) argue that investors are human and have emotions which can cause irrationality when participating in the financial markets. This argument is supported by Barberis and Thaler (2005), Russo and Schoemaker (1991) and Bazerman (1998). They each have a unique set of skills, amount of knowledge, and intellect to perceive new information, as well as limitations on their self-control (Akerlof and Shiller, 2009). This resulted in factors such as personality, personal judgement and social experience that can generate certain behavioural biases while making an investment decision (Khoshnood and Khoshnood, 2011). Firat and Fettahoglou (2011) added that financial investors can be irrational at times and act on their emotions, not on their logical thinking. Traczyk, Fulawka, Lenda, & Zaleskiewicz (2021) further demonstrated that emotions play a crucial role in violating rational principles in economic decision making.

Mitroi and Oproiu (2014) explained investors who are in stressful circumstances tend to be less focused, less optimistic and have brainfogs regularly. As a result, this creates confusion, reduction in ability to gather accurate pieces of information and higher tendency to over-trade or have illusion of control (Mitroi and Oproiu, 2014). There is also evidence of impacts from personality traits where apprehensive investors tend to avoid high risk investments and high in extroversion ones are more attracted to invest in riskier assets (Maner et al., 2007; Gambetti and Giusberti, 2019). With a vast amount of literature on how investment decisions can be influenced by various human factors, behavioural finance theory is proposed with the aim to explain investment decisions from a more realistic perspective and unusual market phenomena. Moreover, behavioural finance attempts to identify behavioural factors that might have a significant impact on different elements within trading and investing such as asset pricing, trading volume and investment performance.

Under behavioural finance theory, a number of aspects have emerged in order to categorise and describe certain biases namely heuristics, prospect theory and herding. Heuristics are mental shortcuts that are used in complex decision-making processes based on past outcomes rather than taking the entire picture into account (Mouni,

2012). It can act as a tool to navigate investment decisions within a highly uncertain situation (Ritter, 2003). By applying some mental shortcuts, assessment in potential outcome probabilities and expected values can become less complicated and time efficient (Kahneman and Tversky, 1974). Gigerenzer (2008) argues that optimisation is considered to be highly impossible to achieve and unlikely to be accurately measured due to estimation errors, hence, heuristics introduced as an alternative to be sufficiently adequate. Goldstein (2018) further added that due to uncertainty and lack of information availability, investors look to satisfy their needs rather than finding the best solutions or decisions. From a heuristics point of view, some behavioural factors which have been found to have an influence on investment performance are overconfidence, anchoring and adjustment, availability and representativeness (Broekema and Kramer, 2021; Gaudecker, 2015; Gentile et al., 2016; Khan, 2015; Ikram, 2016; Waweru et al., 2008; Shah et al., 2018; Aziz and Khan, 2016).

On the other hand, prospect theory was developed by Kahneman and Tversky (1979) and recommends a model where people tend to more risk seeking towards losses and less towards gains. Kahneman and Tversky (1979) illustrate investors perceive gains differently from losses. Losses can present greater and more negative emotional effects, meaning the pain of experiencing a loss is much higher than the joy of experiencing gains (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). This could potentially divert investors from taking on extra risk associating with a prospective sure gain (Kahneman and Tversky, 1992). Elliot and Archibald (1989) support the idea of prospect theory and argue it can enhance the prediction of economic actors' behaviour. D'Aveni (1989) found evidence supporting prospect theory where creditors delayed bankruptcy by avoiding loss realisation and decided to take on more risks. Leclerc, Schmitt and Dube (1995) further approve the concept of prospect theory by discovering people treat time the same as money, similarly to the convex function proposed by prospect theory. The behavioural biases under prospect theory that receive highest attention are loss aversion, regret aversion and mental accounting. Some evidence of their impacts on investment performance also have been found namely Bouteska and Regaieg (2018), Lee and Veld-Merkoulova (2016), Yiwen (2021), Mahina, Muturi and Memba (2017), Isidore and

Christie (2019), Wangzhou et al. (2021), Mellers (2000), Rashwan and Shaqfa (2021), and Obademi and Ogunlusi (2019).

Herding bias is the propensity for people to adopt other people's viewpoints rather than their own (Baddeley, 2010). Avery and Zemsky (1998) demonstrated that investors tend to ignore or reject their initial examination and follow previous price trends. Moreover, investors frequently pay more attention to experts and advisors in the financial markets because they feel they have a better comprehension of the situation and the knowledge needed to choose the appropriate investments (Chen et al., 2020; DeBont and Forbes, 1999). Chiang et al. (2013) and Pompian (2012) emphasise on the negative effect of herding on investment performance due to high level of irrationality. However, herding can also be considered to benefit investors. Nonetheless, Bikhchandani and Sharma (2000) found that investors can exploit herding by drawing their own judgements from comparable sets of fundamental data, rather than simply mimicking the action of the bigger group. Froot et al. (1992) added that market participants can learn what others know by herding on the same information. Furthermore, Scharfstein and Stein (1990) found that reputation considerations can lead to rational herding in the labour markets. Some scholars documented herding's relationship with investment performance are Le and Doan (2011), Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), Nareswari, et al. (2021) and Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna (2020), and Karmacharya et al. (2022).

Behavioural finance has gained tremendous attention from different scholars; however, it has been mainly studied within the stock market, debt market and some cases in the real estate market. To the author's knowledge, there is a highly limited number of researched studies on behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market. Due to the cryptocurrency market's significant growth and potentially lead to a potential financial revolution, it is necessary to deliver more research for the cryptocurrency market, especially from a behavioural finance perspective. The author believes the significance and importance to examine the performance of crypto investors through the lens of the behavioural finance theory can be bridges via the reasons as follows:

- Traditional financial assets such as stocks and bonds can often be analysed based on their intrinsic value or the organisations' cash flow as well as financial reports. This plays a crucial role in determining different fundamental aspects of these assets (Penman, 1992). However, cryptocurrencies' value often rely on the utility and practical applications of these assets. These can be driven by constant technology innovations and demands which might lead to high volatility and speculation nature of the market and investors to make investment decisions depends more on psychological elements and less on analysing fundamental factors.
- Apart from the different determination components from traditional assets and crypto assets, it is evidently that crypto assets can experience much greater volatility in pricing than traditional financial assets (Bianchi, 2020). This can be explained through speculative trading behaviour, risk and loss perception, and market bubbles and crashes. As they are the underlying features of behavioural finance theory and may not apply under the assumptions of traditional finance theory, it is crucial to study crypto assets under behavioural finance perspective. It will also contribute to provide more insights on such different pricing movements between crypto assets and traditional financial assets.
- Unlike traditional financial assets, crypto assets are still in the evolving and developing phase as a kind of alternative financial assets. The policy and regulating aspects for these assets remains to be require substantial work from relevant financial authorities to help cryptocurrency markets progress in the right direction. Therefore, this suggests a heightened level of anxiety and uncertainty regarding regulatory developments amongst crypto investors comparing to traditional financial asset investors. Accordingly, psychological, and emotional biases may arise when making an investment decision for individual crypto investors.

Furthermore, in order to provide explanation towards investment decisions, investors' performance is deemed to be studied in relation to its relationship with different behavioural finance factors. The research also aims to contribute to other individual investors a better understanding of trading behaviours within the cryptocurrency market to acquire more efficient strategies. Moreover, since the cryptocurrency market

remains to be new compared to other financial markets, institutional investors and financial advisors can observe research findings for anticipative future investments. Regulators and policy makers can also benefit from this paper in order to implement new policies in order to protect individual investors as the cryptocurrency market remains to have significant high risks and be a largely unregulated market.

1.2. RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to critically evaluate the behavioural factors and motivations that affect the investors' performance within the cryptocurrency market. Accordingly, this research aims to deliver the following objectives:

- To identify which behavioural biases provide significant/insignificant effects on crypto investors' performance via the behavioural finance theory
- To determine if there is a negative/positive influence between different behavioural biases and cryptocurrency investors' performance
- To identify if there is a relationship between different investing motivations and crypto investors' performance

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In accordance with the aims and objectives of this study, the author attempts to answer the following research questions:

- What are the behavioural biases that have significant impacts on crypto investors' performance?
- Do the identified behavioural finance biases (from the heuristics, prospect theory and herding perspective) have a negative influence on investors' performance in the cryptocurrency market?

- Does any investing motivation suggest a positive relationship with crypto investors' performance?

1.4. STRUCTURE OF THE STUDY:

This paper consists of five chapters:

- Chapter One - This chapter provides an overview, research rationale, aims and objectives as well as research questions
- Chapter Two - This chapter review previous literature on the cryptocurrency market, crypto investors' motivations and behavioural finance in general and within the cryptocurrency market
- Chapter Three - This chapter explained the chosen research methodology for this paper. It involves research philosophies, research approaches, research designs, collection of data and data analysis method
- Chapter Four - This chapter includes data analyses, regression result assessments and discussion regarding research findings
- Chapter Five - This chapter provides conclusion, summary of findings, research contribution, recommendations and limitations of the research

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. OVERVIEW

This section is divided into three parts. The first part outlined the different features associated with cryptocurrency alongside a range of previous research on the motivational factors, consideration of cryptocurrency during uncertain periods and market turbulence as well as different research findings on the market efficiency of cryptocurrencies. The following sub-chapter will highlight how behavioural finance was introduced as the result from the over time inconsistency of the traditional finance theory. Previous research will also be included to assess the overall findings under seven behavioural factors. The last part of the literature review includes some available papers directly studying the behavioural finance aspects in the cryptocurrency market and establishes research hypotheses for this study.

2.2. INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE

Either from an institutional or individual perspective, the goal of a financial investor is to constantly look for the growth in value of capital, to increase income and have the ability to earn excess returns on investment overtime (Feibel, 2003). According to Feibel (2003, p.1), the possible extra amount earned, or in other words “compensation”, from the investment is known as return. The process of attempting to earn this return can involve arbitrage sales with a possible maturing period with interest rate (Feibel, 2003). After a period of time, an investor can revise the price performance of the asset(s) invested and evaluate profit and loss after the time they wish to proceed through (Birken and Curry, 2022). The step to take away net profit and obtain statistically the percentage of it by the initial amount of capital is to calculate the rate of return or return on investment (ROI) (Birken and Curry, 2022). ROI is viewed to be a simple, yet key performance indicator of how well and efficient an investor has been performing with their investment. For instance, after a week of investing £100 into a

tech stock, investor A gained an extra £10 on the initial investment. By selling what he owns right now, he could get that £10 in his pocket straight away and have a ROI of 10%.

Institutional and retail investors can utilise the use of ROI to make judgements, rationale and justifications for their future investments where comparison and expectations are required (Gennaioli, Ma and Shleifer, 2015). A benchmark ROI can be set out so investors can develop certain strategies in order to achieve that goal (Botchkarev, Andru and Chiong, 2011). In addition, ROI can also assist in re-assessing the current investment projects to facilitate better decision making (Botchkarev, Andru and Chiong, 2011).

In economics and finance, returns and risk are the two elements which are often mentioned parallelly and strongly correlated to each other (Chiang and Zhang, 2018). Risk can be understood as the extent of possible deviation from expected results lying within an investment project (Outreville, 1998). The more risk associated with a potential investment, the higher expected returns it can offer to investors (Malkiel, 1982). With that being said, they can also be exposed to more financial losses. An investor should explore and determine their own risk profile to find the best suited project for themselves since everyone carries a different risk appetite (Klement, 2015). Risk profile is defined as the parameter of an investor's inclination to bear risk (Sivarajan, 2018). In other words, it is the amount of risk someone is prepared to accept and pursue their goal. It is worth noting that to construct a risk profile, an investor should sub-categorically determine their risk capacity and risk aversion (Klement, 2015). Risk capacity is the maximum degree of risk that an investor can handle from an investment (Brayman, 2012). On the other hand, risk aversion is a term referring to the tendency to select an investment option with lower risk or prefer one with more certainty to uncertainty (CFI, 2022). In practice, identifying the risk profile of a client is one of the first steps for financial institutions to select the most compatible products and to strictly manage investment strategies (Hubble and Dannhauser, 2020). From a retail investing perspective where no brokers or financial advisors are involved, an

individual investor should also acquire a check for their own profiling and self-manage their strategies (Khanna and Chauhan, 2017). Khanna and Chauhan (2017) also added that although different individual investors may have different respective risk profiles, they shall remain rational in order to select suitable security classes.

When it comes to risk aversion, it is one of the foremost important areas within behavioural economics (Zhang, Brennan and Lo, 2014). While Khanna and Chauhan (2017) argued that by including risk aversion in risk profiling, the assumption of rationality should still prevail. This can be considered to be a counterpoint with the behavioural finance theory which says financial investor behaviours are often and inevitably irrational (Singh, 2012). Behavioural economics and behavioural finance is an emerging area attempting to explain the financial markets by studying human psychological interference (Sarkar, 2011). If numerical factors such as return on investment can explain how efficiently and well an investor performs with their investments, the psychological component should also be accounted for in their investing outcomes. In addition, Daniel, Hirshleifer and Subrahmanyam (1998) stated that investor's behaviours can act as a function for investment outcomes. Since this paper is studying the impact of behavioural finance on individual investors, the author has chosen to place assumptions in line with the behavioural finance theory.

RETURN ON INVESTMENT AS A METRIC

A vast amount of academic and practitioner studies has utilised return on investment as a measure for investment performance and investment outcome for not only individual investors, but also for institutional investors and corporations. Return on investment provides value in establishing rationale for future decisions, re-assessing the current one and most importantly measuring investment performance (Botchkarev and Andru, 2011). Previous studies have examined factors relating to macroeconomics, demographics, financial literacy, investor sentiments, attention, news, risk perception and so on and how they can affect return on investment. This section proposes a

number of research on return on investment to emphasise the extended usage of this metric. To measure investment performance based on return on investment, most scholars selected secondary data regarding asset price movements as a tool and chose to analyse the data within a specific time period.

Botchkarev and Andru (2011) attempts to analyse the key attributions of return on investment to the taxonomy of information systems. The researchers indicated that return on investment is a widely used measurement for investment performance and evaluation. In addition, they further highlighted that the analysis of return on investment is a strong and effective tool for assessing information systems, hence, it promotes better decision making and managing business projects. The findings conclude that return on investment is a powerful metric for business performance and has great ability to assist business decision making in a meaningful way.

Musa, Tsegba, Ibe and Onaji (2021) conducted research on the influence of tax incentives on return on investment of twelve publicly listed companies in Nigeria. The tax incentives were examined through the scope of tax exemption for these companies throughout the period between 2015 and 2019. To measure investment performance of these firms, the author adopted the measurement by ROI and all data was classified as secondary through financial reports and reported digitally stock prices. Ordinary Least Square regression analysis was used as the methodological approach to produce statistical results. The study found that there were clear relationships between tax exempt income and loss on ROI. That is tax exempt income has a positive correlation with return on investment while loss relief produced an opposite impact.

Wilcox and Moore (2016) assessed the influence of social media on business progression as a potential area with little exploration academically. The researchers applied the social media performance model to test if social media can play a crucial role in improving business investment performance through return on investment. Lal, Ismagilova, Dwivedi and Kwayu (2018) also investigated measures on social media

marketing to determine return on investment of businesses. The authors strongly emphasised that by looking at investment performance through return on investment can boost better quality strategies in advertising companies' products and services. In addition, it also helped to manage budget and improve the overall business management.

Orbay and Yurtoglu (2006) studied the variation between cash flow rights and voting claims within corporate governance structures in Turkey. The aim of the research is to find the impact of that on corporate investment performance. The author measured the investment performance based on return on investment with regards to corporate costs of capital. By using return on investment as a measurement and quantitative methodology, the study reports similar results on impact with previous studies which mainly adopt literature review as the researching method.

Zhang and Zhang (2021) conducted their research on the investment performance of Chinese venture capitalists and how that is connected to their foreign experience. By using return on investment as the metric to measure investment performance, the authors were able to discover that venture capitalists with foreign investments were less successful than the ones investing more in domestic projects. Prudent investment strategies and lack of supervision were pointed out to be the reasons behind this poorer investment performance.

In terms of individual investing, some scholars studied investment performance of retail investors based on stock returns as well as various factors that can influence investment decisions. Rate of return as a measurement for investment performance can be dated back to the 1970s. Schlarbaum, Lewellena and Lease (1978) reported investment records of individual investors on common stock portfolios and compared to professional mutual fund investors. The research found that retail investors might select stocks in a naive manner, hence, became less successful than the professional ones. Later, Ivkovich and Weisbenner (2003) explored the performance of individual

investors in local investments between 1991 and 1996. They used return on investment as the indicator for investment performance and could conclude that local investors gained excess returns and have the ability to utilise their local knowledge. Another example on evaluating individual investors' performance is the research from Park and Kim (2014). They investigated how well retail investors performed using equity holding data in the South Korean stock market, also by using return on investment. Retail investors are found to be highly associated with small-cap investments, low asset price, low return on investment and high income. Magron (2012) furthermore assessed performance of individual investors and their objectives. The author examined a large sample of 56,723 French retail investors for the period between 1999 and 2006. Profit and loss based on return on investment was adopted to measure investment performance and concluded that the sample performed poorly during that period and executed buy decisions were less profitable than the selling ones.

Regarding assessing relationship between investment outcome with other elements, Khan, Haq and Ahmed (2022) explored the relationship between demographic aspects and investment decision making of retail investors. The authors used return on investment as the measure for their performance between 2009 and 2021. The sample was asked for their demographic details such as education level, income, stock investment experience and location. The findings suggest high correlations between the collected demographic factors and individual investment return on the stock market. Willows and West (2015) studied the influence of gender and age on investment performance of 19,021 South African individual investors. The paper took into consideration returns earned by different sub-sample groups and variance of returns between them for comparison. The results show that women over 60 years of age perform better than men overall. The authors however found there is no statistically difference in investment performance between men and women of younger age.

Akhtar, Thyagaraj and Das (2017) published their paper to provide better understanding between social influences and perceived individual investment performance in India. The research design was questionnaire-based and data was

collected from 396 survey respondents. According to Akhtar et al. (2017), the survey asked the participating investors to self-evaluate their investment performance instead of collecting numerical data such as over time return on investment. The findings suggest that experiencing positive emotions has a direct link and can improve perceived investment performance. The author also conducted a robust check and confirmed the reliability of their model.

Fashagba, Olasehinde, Atsanan and Adebayo (2022) studies the relationship between the inflation rate and ROI of Nigerian stock investors between 1998 and 2017. In this research, return on investment was used as an indicator to measure investment performance of Nigerian investors. The authors adopted the quantitative methodology by using t-test and ANOVA to test their hypothesis. The delivered results suggest that high levels of inflation could potentially plumb real return on investment to below zero. In addition, the findings also indicate high inflation rates are negatively correlated to investors' motivation. Further recommendation from this study proposes although inflation has a significant impact on investment performance, its effect on investments alone was found to be minimal.

SATISFACTION LEVEL AS A METRIC

Measuring investment performance by taking into consideration the satisfaction level has been widely focused as a metric within investor behaviour research. This is because behavioural finance and behavioural economics are constructed around the Utility theory (Dhami and Nowaihi, 2010). In economics, the term 'utility' is used as a frequent alternative to the maximum satisfaction and pleasure of a product or service consumer (Salvatore, 2008). As an economic consumer, everyone would seek to maximise their own utility with their decision making and preferences (Simon, 1966). Unlike traditional finance where maximising personal benefits and rewards is the major aim, behavioural finance proposed that consumer satisfaction should also be included in the decision making process and its outcomes (Lemon and Verhoef, 2016). Consequently, a

body of economics and finance literature has covered consumer utility, or satisfaction, as a metric to measure investor's decision outcomes and performances. Whereas return rates can provide an objective evaluation towards investments, investors' satisfaction can accommodate the subjective side for the matter (Dar and Hakeem, 2015). This section aims to demonstrate the importance of the proposed statement, hence, combining both return on investment and investor satisfaction can provide improved explanation to investor decision making.

One of the early papers to assess retail investors' satisfaction is Oberlechner and Osler (2008). The researchers refer to investment satisfaction as "cognitive performance" where minimum acceptability on retail investments are considered individually (Oberlechner and Osler, 2008, p. 4). By conducting a self-valuation survey and multiple probit regression model, the findings suggest that overconfidence, as a bias within behavioural finance, can enhance trading success. In addition, the research also suggests that professional performance can be regarded in different dimensions, and not only just profitability. Researchers are further advised that return on investment can be adopted in the cognitive performance evaluation (Oberlechner and Osler, 2008).

Following the suggestion of this type of measurement, other behavioural finance papers have further adopted it for their models. Dar and Hakeem (2015) studied the impact of different behavioural factors on investment outcomes. The conceptual framework of this research proposed that investment outcomes can be collectively considered in the forms of investment performance and satisfaction. In addition, Khurshid, Ahmed and Irrum (2021) also studied the effect of herding and overconfidence on individual investment outcomes. The respondents were required to self-evaluate their stock investments instead of collecting secondary data from brokerage companies or a particular data source. Similar adoption can be seen in Khan, Afrin and Rahman (2015), Boda, Guniganti and Ray (2016), Keswani, Dhingra and Wadhwa (2019), Cao, Nguyen and Tran (2021) and Bairagi and Chakraborty (2021). The listed researches are all within the behavioural finance field.

Metrics	Author(s)	Key Findings
Return on investment	Botchkraev and Andru (2011)	Return on investment is a powerful metric for business performance and has great ability to assist business decision making in a meaningful way
	Musa, Tsegba, Ibe and Onaji (2021)	By using return on investment as a metric to measure firms' performance, the authors were able to find tax exempt income has positively impacted investment performance
	Wilcox and Moore (2016)	Social media can improve business performance, through return on investment
	Lal, Ismagliova, Dwivedi and Kwayu (2018)	Managing return on investment can boost better quality strategies in advertising and better allocating budgets
	Orbay and Yurtoglu (2006)	By using a quantitative method on return on investment, positive impact of cash flow rights and voting claims on corporate governance is documented. Similar findings with same area research using literature review method
	Zhang and Zhang (2021)	Venture capitalists with foreign investments are less successful than the ones investing more in domestic projects, with regards to return on investment
	Schlarbaum, Lewellena and Lease (1978)	By studying return on investment records, retail investors were reported to select stocks in a naive manner and became less successful than the professional ones
	Ivkovich and Weisbenner (2003)	Local investors gained excess returns and have the ability to utilise their knowledge, compared to non-local investors
	Park and Kim (2014)	Retail investors are found to be highly associated with small-cap investments, low asset price, low return on investment and high income
	Magron (2012)	By measuring profit and loss on return on investment, the sample performed poorly during that period and executed

		buy decisions were less profitable than the selling ones
	Khan and Ahmed (2022)	High correlation between return on investment and demographic details such as education level, income, stock investment experience and location
	Willows and West (2015)	Women over 60 years of age perform better than men overall, however, no statistically difference in investment performance between men and women of younger age
	Akhtar, Thyagaraj and Das (2017)	Experiencing positive emotions has a direct link and can improve perceived investment performance, measuring with return on investment
	Fashagba, Olasehinde, Atsanan and Adebayo (2022)	High levels of inflation could potentially plumb real return on investment to below zero. Inflation rates are found to have positive impact on investors' performance but remains minimal
Satisfaction	Oberlechner and Osler (2008)	Overconfidence can enhance trading success. Professional performance can be regarded in different dimensions, not only just profitability but also satisfaction
	Dar and Hakeem (2015)	The conceptual framework of this research proposed that investment outcomes can be collectively considered in the forms of investment performance and satisfaction
	Khurshid, Ahmed and Irrum (2021)	Adopted investors' satisfaction as a metric to measure investment decision outcomes. Similar adoption can be seen in Khan, Afrin and Rahman (2015), Boda, Guniganti and Ray (2016), Keswani, Dhingra and Wadhwa (2019), Cao, Nguyen and Tran (2021) and Bairagi and Chakraborty (2021)

In terms of perspective on investment satisfaction, this thesis proposes four elements to determine the overall satisfaction: buying and selling decisions, asset picking and trading volume.

BUYING AND SELLING DECISIONS

Munthiu (2009) stated making a buying or purchasing decision is not simply a one-step process, and should follow different stages namely problem acknowledgement, information search, consideration of alternative options, buying decision and finally post evaluation. Lin (2002) further emphasised the importance of information search while making a buying decision as it can potentially minimise associated risk with the investment. Investors are advised to be well informed by thoroughly researching different aspects of a security and to make better decisions (Gill, Khurshid, Mahmood and Ali, 2018). Nonetheless, behavioural finance states not all investors act rationally in reality and evidence can be presented (Joshi, Joshi and Desai, 2012).

By behaving in an irrational way, they enact mental shortcuts when making a decision (Dale, 2015). According to Odean (1999), one of the factors influencing purchasing decisions is attention effect. The author explained that instead of attempting to find the best listed stocks, investors may execute a buy position based on their interest in a particular company. Sudden interests may arise from a recent read from the media and news where unusual price movements of a business are discussed (Odean, 1999). Regardless of how well or bad the asset is performing, retail investors still have the incentive to make a buy decision (Odean, 1999).

Another phenomenon which has been recognised to influence purchasing decisions is fear of missing out, or FOMO (Good and Hyman, 2020). This behaviour can be understood as the feeling of missing out from potential opportunities and must act immediately (Dennison, 2018). Gupta and Shrivastava (2020) described retail investors experiencing FOMO tend to ignore facts and truth about an asset and act impulsively by making buying decisions. Where investors could spend some time to validate their judgements, the fear of losing possible gains prevails and makes them too anxious to allow extra time (Gupta and Shrivastava, 2020). In a way, FOMO makes buying decisions

riskier and may affect market prices on a large scale (Franchina, Abeelee, Rooji, Coco and Marez, 2018). Gupta and Shrivastava (2020) further suggested FOMO can also be explained through herding. Retail investors seem to have the tendency to buy more when they notice more buying orders from other investors (Gupta and Shrivastava, 2020). In the cryptocurrency space, FOMO can be observed as a significant phenomenon and affect investors' buying decisions (Bernard, 2022). Initial coin offering (ICO) issuers even use FOMO as a tool to promote buying and ownership of new crypto assets (Momtaz, 2020A).

Barberis and Thaler (2003) specified buying and selling decisions are treated differently. The reason behind that can be explained based on the asset ownership status (Barberis and Thaler, 2003). When making a buy decision and without owning the asset previously, investors are presented with numerous choices (Barberis and Thaler, 2003). This requires them to spend time to study all potential options and then each individually. Whereas, selling decisions requires actions only to their limited holding assets (Barberis and Thaler, 2003). In a way, the attention effect mentioned previously has the tendency to influence purchasing decisions more than selling decisions.

Disposition effect is found to influence investors' willingness to sell. This was early defined by Shefrin and Statman (1985) as the reluctance to sell at a loss of an investor, with respect to the initial purchasing price. Among previous studies, Odean (1998) demonstrated the evidence of disposition effect by analysing 10,000 retail investors from a brokerage house. The findings suggested the researched participants had the tendency to sell stocks with negative returns with respect to the buying value, rather than the ones with positive returns. Since the sample is considered to be significantly large, this result can be generalised and implies that stock retail investors hold on more to losers than winners. Disposition effect can be illustrated through the prospect theory (Barberis and Xiong, 2009). According to Barberis and Xiong (2009), as prospect theory suggests investors are more risk-averse when there is a possibility of reducing losses,

they are hesitant to sell their assets just yet with the hope of a reversed price movement.

ASSET PICKING DECISION

Previous literature has further provided evidence on the influence of behavioural and psychological aspects on asset allocation decisions, though all papers conducted only within the stock market context. Auger, Devinney, Dowling and Eckert (2016) stated there is a level of inertia among retail investors when choosing socially responsible investment funds. In behavioural finance, inertia regards the tendency to follow a prior choice without considering its outcome (Alos-Ferrer, Hugelschafer and Li, 2016). Investors who are prone to inertia tend to repeat the same investment as before. This can be explained due to the decrease in cognitive effort (Auger et al., 2016). It acts as a shortcut and aims to accelerate the process of making decisions (Auger et al., 2016). In terms of fund managers, they also repeat the same asset selection choices if their investment strategy remains unchanged (Auger et al., 2016).

Over-extrapolation is another behavioural factor affecting asset picking decisions. According to Greenwood and Shleifer (2014), an over-extrapolative investor expects repeated patterns in stock returns. Particularly, one would suppose high returns are more likely to occur again after a high return and vice versa for low returns (Greenwood and Shleifer, 2014). Investors with good previous experience with their asset allocation would want a similar outcome to happen again. In the research of Anderson, Freeborn and Hulbert (2018), their experimental survey findings suggest great adjustment on investments occurs when investors experience a loss after a return. This may result in underinvestment and reduced earnings with future decisions (Anderson et al., 2018).

TRADING VOLUME

Beside buying, selling and asset allocation decisions, trading volume has also been found to be influenced by psychological factors. In the paper of Odean (1999), the findings suggested that high levels of trading can be expressed in the form of overconfidence behaviour. When investors are feeling over-optimistic about the future of the market, they trade more and aggressively (Odean, 1999). Furthermore, in a later collaboration, Barber and Odean (2000) demonstrated prior trading successes can lead to investors' belief of their strong security allocation skill. This ultimately results in over-trading and weak performance (Barber and Odean, 2000). Shiller (2005) adds overconfidence creates risk-seeking behaviour for investors, hence, increase in trading activity. Investors who trade intensively are reported to perform significantly worse than ones who trade less (Prosad, Kapoor, Sengupta and Roychoudhary, 2017).

Disposition effect, which previously was found to have an impact on selling decisions, is too linked with more trading volume. Szyszka and Zielonka (2007) reported its relationship with the trading volume in the Initial Public Offering (IPO) market. The authors emphasise the unique feature of the IPO market where all investors have the same buying price on the first day of offering, hence, disposition effect can be examined at the market level. The research was conducted in the Polish IPO market and detected a correlation between disposition effect and the trading volume. When the share price is trading at a lower level compared to the initial offering price, the trading volume is considerably lower than when the price is trading at a higher level. Initial negative rates of returns make investors more reluctant to sell and hope for a price reversal. Whereas, they sell the stocks as soon as they can realise gains and more trading volume is documented. This finding is in line with Kaustia (2004) in the US market, Feng and Seasholes (2005) and Shumway and Wu (2006) in the Chinese market, and Shapira and Venezia (2001) in the Israeli market.

Aspects	Author(s)	Key Findings
Buying and selling	Odean (1999)	Instead of attempting to find the best listed stocks, investors may execute a buy position based on their interest in a particular company. That is called the

decisions		attention effect
	Gupta and Shrivastava (2020)	Retail investors experiencing FOMO tend to ignore facts and truth about an asset and act impulsively by making buying decisions
	Momtaz (2020A)	Initial coin offering (ICO) issuers even use FOMO as a tool to promote buying and ownership of new crypto assets
	Barberis and Thaler (2003)	The attention effect mentioned previously has the tendency to influence purchasing decisions more than selling decisions, therefore, buying and selling should be treated differently
	Odean (1998)	The sample showed evidence of disposition effect where they had the tendency to sell stocks with negative returns with respect to the buying value, rather than the ones with positive returns
	Barberis and Xiong (2009)	As prospect theory suggests investors are more risk-averse when there is a possibility of reducing losses, they are hesitant to sell their assets just yet with the hope of a reversed price movement
Asset picking decisions	Auger, Devinney, Dowling and Eckert (2016)	There is a level of inertia among retail investors when choosing socially responsible investment funds
	Greenwood and Shleifer (2014)	Developed the concept of over-extrapolation where one would suppose high returns are more likely to occur again after a high return and vice versa for low returns
	Anderson, Freeborn and Hulbert (2018)	Evidence on over-extrapolation on asset allocation decisions after experiencing a loss. This may result in underinvestment and reduced earnings on future decisions
Trading volume	Odean (1999)	High levels of trading can be expressed in the form of overconfidence behaviour. When investors are feeling

decisions		over-optimistic about the future of the market, they trade more and aggressively
	Barber and Odean (2000)	Overconfidence can lead to over-trading and weak performance
	Prosad, Kapoor, Sengupta and Roychoudhary (2017)	Investors who trade intensively are reported to perform significantly worse than ones who trade less
	Szyska and Zielonka (2007)	Disposition effect is also documented with trading volume in the IPO market. When experiencing negative initial return, trading volume was found low but increased drastically once experiencing positive return on IPO. Findings in line with Kaustia (2004), Feng and Seasholes (2005), Shumway and Wu (2006) and Shapira and Venezia (2001)

2.3. CRYPTOCURRENCY CHARACTERISTICS AND THE MARKET

2.3.1. CRYPTOCURRENCY CHARACTERISTICS

The idea of money as a medium of exchange has been existing at least for the past 5000 years (Davies, 2016). Medium of exchange means that individuals can use money to trade objects, commodities, intangible assets and services. It can also be used as a tool for measurements or a depository for wealth (Credit Suisse, 2021; Federal Reserve, 2022). According to the Federal Reserve of the United States (2022), money does not necessarily require a physical design but may exist in the forms of digital banking and non-banking balances. Within the concept of money, currency is often referred to or used as an interchangeable term and can represent in the physical sense of notes and coins issued by a body of government and its central bank (McLeay, Radia and Thomas, 2014). This usually is indicated as fiat currency namely British Pound Sterling, US

dollars, Japanese Yen, Turkish Lira and so on. However, the emergence of new technologies and digitalisation has forced banks to change the core interpretation of currency. Central Banks such as the Bank of England and the Federal Reserve later included the term “digital currencies” in their reports as an electronic form of currency and can only be accessed by an electronic device (Frankenfield, 2022). According to Frankenfield (2022), there are two types of digital currencies coexisting in the financial markets, namely cryptocurrency and central bank digital currency (CBDC). While CBDC was established with inspiration from the idea of cryptocurrency (Krylov, Lisitsyn and Polyakov, 2018), cryptocurrency remains to have the foremost fundamental value, unique characteristics and represents a monetary reformation which has had and will continue to provide great influence in people’s everyday life (IMF, 2022).

Cryptocurrencies are fully decentralised digital currencies run by no one entity, with no government to issue it and no banks needed to manage accounts and verify transactions. Bitcoin (BTC) is known to be the earliest invention of cryptocurrency, introduced to the public in 2009 by Satoshi Nakamoto whose true identity remains a guarded secret (Nakamoto, 2009). He also created the blockchain technology in order to track the ownership of Bitcoin and store transaction information in the form of a decentralised ledger or digital blocks across millions of computers around the world (Natarajan, Krause and Gradstein, 2017). Since no central banks are needed to verify a transaction, these computers can essentially replace them for the purpose of validation in matters of seconds or minutes (Griffith and Grigg, 2014). All information once enters a blockchain network is highly difficult to be changed or reversed and it is nearly impossible to hack the server (Guo and Yu, 2022). This principle of validation has virtually eliminated the “trust” factor between payer to payee or vice versa and the central banks like how a transaction is traditionally meant to be completed. At the end of the verifying process, the network of member computers shall be rewarded with a certain amount of the cryptocurrency which was transacted and this is known as mining (Glass, 2016). Furthermore, with no central banks involved in the system, many different cryptocurrencies can control their coin supply and minimise the inflationary effect unlike fiat currency where central banks hold the power of infinite money printing (Choi and Shin, 2022). For instance, BTC only allows a maximum of 21 millions

coins in circulation (McGovern, 2022). Other examples are Cardano (ADA) and Ripple (XRP) with the limited token supply of 45 millions and 100 millions respectively (McGovern, 2022). For the case of coins without a definite token supply limit, network users will be asked to vote and grant decisions based on the majority if there is a desire to increase the supply cap of a cryptocurrency (Park, Specter, Narula and Rivest, 2021).

In order to own, spend or exchange cryptocurrency, users are required to use a digital crypto wallet. This kind of wallet strictly comprises two elements used in cryptography: public key and private key (Glass, 2016). Like its name, public key consists of a string of code which is available and public to everyone within the network and can be used as an address to send cryptocurrency to other people. Although crypto wallets can contain identifiable information of the crypto holders, the public key system allows them to have a certain level of anonymity when making transactions (Glass, 2016). On the other hand, the private key paired with the existing public key provides great security functions to the crypto holders. In order to access, receive and spend the crypto fund, it is compulsory to present the network with the associated private key which is unique for each digital wallet. The idea is to serve as a step of identity verification and prevent unauthorised access in case of frauds and scams (Glass, 2016). However, it is necessary for users to store the private key firmly and discreetly as losing it exposes themselves to the inability to access their own wallet.

2.3.2. BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain is a great unique and essential component of cryptocurrency and has been utilised throughout its concept. The blockchain technology has generated a vast amount of benefits to cryptocurrencies by providing a payment system enforcing trust, security and transparency between transaction makers without the need of knowing one another. In addition, by cancelling out any middlemen and centralised authority body, cryptocurrencies make it faster and cheaper in terms of fees while making a transfer. As the cryptocurrency market has been growing significantly in recent years, there are a lot of opportunities to improve earnings by taking advantage of massive price swings on

a timely basis or just by holding crypto coins. However, that comes with associated massive risks in the sense that one can potentially lose their entire livelihood because of such volatility. While the cryptocurrency market has exponentially grown over the last ten years, it still remains to be a slowly regulated market amongst financial regulators from all around the world (Thomson Reuters, 2022). Illegal activities such as stealing, money laundering and illegitimate purchases on the darknet have been utilising the use of cryptocurrency because of its anonymity and convenience features (Houben and Snyers, 2018). Another disadvantage of cryptocurrency is enormous consumption of energy during the crypto mining process which could be very costly and intensively damage the environment.

To summarise all key characteristics of cryptocurrency, readers can refer to the following diagram.

2.3.3. THE CRYPTOCURRENCY MARKET

In economics, a market is defined as a structural environment where buyers and sellers interact with each other, with the purpose to exchange goods or services at agreed prices (Stigler and Sherwin, 1985). In terms of financial markets, the exchanged goods are financial securities such as foreign currencies, stocks, bonds, and other derivatives products (Parameswaran, 2002). These products are often traded on a public brokerage exchange or over-the-counter which means no involvement of a broker (Macy and O'hara, 1999). Although cryptocurrencies do not match the description of a type of financial instruments under International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), they

are widely traded on numerous cryptocurrency exchanges and treated as investment assets and portfolio diversifiers (PwC, 2019; Goldman Sachs, 2021). Unlike traditional financial markets, the cryptocurrency market is fully open for trading over 24 hours a day, 7 days a week (Fang, Ventre, Basios, Kanthan, Martinez-Rego, Wu and Li, 2022). This is due to the unique decentralisation feature where no central authority is required to manage the currencies, unlike traditional fiat currencies' demand for central banks. Furthermore, crypto coins can be exchanged from different locations around the world and not limited to one place (Fang et al., 2022).

Although BTC was available to trade since 2009, it only started growing significantly and increased its market capitalisation to \$1 billion in 2013; it was later brought to an all time high which is over \$1,000 billion twice in 2021 (Statista, 2022). Following the success of BTC, there are now thousands of other cryptocurrencies such as Ether, Litecoin, Polkadot, Solana, Avalanche and more available to be traded on exchanges. These coins are often referred to as altcoins, meaning alternative crypto coins to Bitcoin (Houben and Snyers, 2018). Each coin is associated with different crypto blockchain projects providing different functions to solve a problem to one another. For example, Ether is a cryptocurrency associated with the Ethereum network that allows programmers to build decentralised applications (dApps) using its own programming language and infrastructure. Differently, Polkadot represents the ability to connect between different networks of blockchain. Solana, by putting the time factor into the consensus mechanism between the network computers, is built to substantially speed up duration of validation, duration of creating new blocks of information and expand the capacity of transaction handling and so on on other cryptocurrencies.

Beside the crypto coins with active price speculation, there are stablecoins which is another type of cryptocurrency tracking movements of a reserved asset such as fiat currency or commodity (FSB, 2022). Examples are Tether (USDT), USD Coin (USDC) or DAI that peg the price of US dollars. The purpose of stablecoin is to protect investments, reduce volatility and exchange of funds with the value of a stable security regardless of users' location (Arner, Auer and Frost, 2020). As of November 2021, the total

cryptocurrency market capitalisation peaked at nearly \$3 billion; that is approximately a 1000% rise compared to November 2017 (CoinMarketCap, 2022).

As of March 2022, there are a total of approximately 18,000 cryptocurrencies being actively traded according to Pupkevicius (2022). This number has grown to nearly 22,000 in December 2022 with regards to Forbes (2022). The top 20 cryptocurrencies ranked by the value of market capitalisation are presented in the table below. The data is also retrieved from CoinMarketCap (2022). CoinMarketCap is known to be one of the highly inclusive information sites among the crypto space (Senkardes and Akadur, 2021).

Rank	Cryptocurrency	Symbol	Market Cap	Price	Circulating Supply
1	Bitcoin	BTC	\$783,260,570,383.7	\$41,247.82	18,989,137 BTC
2	Ethereum	ETH	\$343,377,833,604.3	\$2,860.46	120,042,908 ETH
3	Tether	USDT	\$80,781,817,395.21	\$1.00	80,747,335,458 USDT
4	BNB	BNB	\$64,522,408,664.10	\$390.77	165,116,761 BNB
5	USD Coin	USDC	\$53,000,906,379.47	\$0.9999	53,004,490,761 USDC
6	XRP	XRP	\$38,791,824,340.83	\$0.8061	48,121,609,012 XRP
7	Terra	LUNA	\$33,016,693,268.72	\$90.53	364,695,245 LUNA
8	Cardano	ADA	\$29,569,834,894.15	\$0.8771	33,713,492,092 ADA
9	Solana	SOL	\$28,388,486,843.57	\$88.61	320,358,097 SOL
10	Avalanche	AVAX	\$22,636,838,970.73	\$84.72	267,182,355 AVAX
11	Polkadot	DOT	\$18,407,139,481.67	\$18.64	987,579,315 DOT

12	Binance USD	BUSD	\$17,794,988,349.19	\$0.9994	17,806,035,748 BUSD
13	Dogecoin	DOGE	\$15,808,231,747.90	\$0.1192	132,670,764,300 DOGE
14	TerraUSD	UST	\$15,439,586,892.30	\$1.00	15,381,792,869 UST
15	Shiba Inu	SHIB	\$12,697,232,753.07	\$0.00002313	549,063,278,876,302 SHIB
16	Polygon	MATIC	\$11,266,425,868.33	\$1.46	7,696,069,521 MATIC
17	Wrapped Bitcoin	WBTC	\$11,253,279,811.45	\$41,208.58	273,081 WBTC
18	Cronos	CRO	\$10,245,494,361.34	\$0.4056	25,263,013,692 CRO
19	Dai	DAI	\$9,963,862,903.19	\$0.9993	9,971,241,657 DAI
20	Litecoin	LTC	\$8,025,097,838.83	\$114.83	69,887,294 LTC

Source: CoinMarketCap (2022)

2.3.4. MOTIVATION OF CRYPTOCURRENCY INVESTORS

Cryptocurrency and the blockchain technology were created based on the fundamentality of a decentralising system where the power to govern is distributed to each and every person involved in the network, not by a centralised body or authority (Atzori, 2017). In a way, decentralisation can enhance and strengthen democracy (Faguet, Fox and Poschl, 2015). It promotes equality and liberty belonging to every network member. They have the rights to be engaged and have their say in all decision making and planning processes within the network.

The benefits decentralisation can bring have been recognised to a greater extent as the time goes on and blockchain technology is increasingly becoming widely employed and further integrated in different fields. It provides a secured and transparent environment and the ability to make decisions without having to trust other people in the process

(Farnaghi and Mansourian, 2020). In addition, network users have equal access to all transaction data in the form of distributed ledgers which cannot be altered or reversed after being put through the blockchain. This also produces more efficiency in communication and conflict resolving (Keil and Anderson, 2018). Furthermore, cryptocurrency is considered to have an opposed effect on inflation where it does not allow the coin supply limit to increase freely as discussed previously. Accordingly, the principle of decentralisation can be considered to be one of the main motivations why people want to invest in cryptocurrencies. They have the tendency to believe in a future world of complete democracy and free market where everyone has an equal chance to define a market with no interruptions or market manipulation from the governments (Wintermeyer, 2021). This belief seems to have come from citizens in different democratic countries all around the world getting exhausted and having lack of faith in their country's politicians and the central authorities (Community of Democracies, 2022). They seeked for a system that can dismiss the governmental body and allow themselves to manage all aspects of their lives. Certainly, decentralisation matches the requirements and seems to be the perfect concept one can follow and be in charge of any situation surrounding him or her. By investing or getting involved in cryptocurrencies, they believe to create a revolution to eliminate any third party as well as a free market that is available to everyone.

Apart from the belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth, some people choose to invest in cryptocurrency simply because they want to increase their income passively or actively. The emergence of decentralised finance (DeFi) has allowed people to earn passive income on investments just at where they are sitting with their computers. Earning interests through cryptocurrency can be done by staking, saving and lending or yield farming. Staking refers to the action of token holdings that shows support or confidence of the holder on the future of a token project (Verspeek, Eisses and Dawe, 2019). The staking procedure can vary among different projects, however, the principle is the same where token investors earn rewards on top of their staking amount with respect to a project's proposed APY. While well-established crypto coins can yield around 10% annually offered by different staking platforms, some newer crypto protocols can offer from 97% (Kingspeed) to 382,945% (Safuu) in terms of

annual percentage yield (APY) if investors choose to stake tokens directly on their platform (Yahoo, 2021a; Yahoo, 2021b). Greener crypto tokens might offer extremely attractive APY, however, there are some underlying risks that investors should always keep in mind. The cryptocurrency market can be highly volatile (Liu and Serletis, 2019); hence, a large drop in prices might result in outweighing any rewards that have been generated over a long period of time. Some crypto projects even demand investors to lock in for a minimum staking period (Sandor, 2022). This can cause investors themselves a great exposure to substantial losses if the market is not in a great state.

Another way to make money with less effort in crypto is saving and lending. As it works in the similar way with traditional banks, investors can inject money into their crypto savings account as a product offered by crypto banks or decentralised finance (DeFi) protocols. Investors then can earn interest on top of their savings account or their lending amount depending if they are locked in for a certain amount of time or on flexible terms. For flexible terms, interest is normally paid daily, on a compounding basis and investors can withdraw funds anytime as they wish (Wade, 2022). Many DeFi platforms have been created and offer different APYs since the crypto market and demand for lending and borrowing have been growing. That has resulted in the creation of yield farming which is referred as an activity to maximise their return on capital by leveraging between different DeFi protocols (Cousaert, Xu and Matsui, 2022). This strategy may involve moving funds between those protocols or exchanges of crypto coins which award higher yield across the time of holding. Apart from earning passive income on cryptocurrency, active trading on crypto exchanges can be another way for investors to expand their livelihood. At the end of 2021, Coinbase, one of the biggest cryptocurrency exchanges worldwide, reported the presence of 89 million verified active users on their platform (Statista, 2022). That is about a 60% increase in the number compared to March of the same year and a 230% increase compared to March of 2019 (Statista, 2022). The crypto exchange also announced their total retail trading volume hiked from \$32 billion to \$177 billion between quarter 4 of 2020 and 2021 respectively; that is over 450% growth over the 12 month period (Coinbase, 2022). Other crypto exchanges like Binance, Gemini, FTX or Kraken have also reported to experience dramatic changes in terms of trading volume and activities (Paz, 2022).

It cannot be denied that retail trading in crypto around the world has exponentially expanded in recent years. COVID-19 is considered to be a booster in terms of accelerating these figures as people consider some assets in the cryptocurrency markets as a form of “epidemiologically safe” investment (Boguslavsky, Sharova and Sharova, 2021). Unlike passive ways to earn interest on crypto holdings, active trading on crypto platforms where leverage can be applied to each buy and sell position can offer extremely attractive returns on investment but also involves much higher risks and exposure to severe volatility. Retail traders should be ultimately careful with their strategies, tools and analysis to minimise the damage as much as possible.

DIFFERENT TYPES OF MOTIVATION

Lee, Li and Zheng (2020) studied the effect of two categorised investor groups in the BTC market that involve speculators and tech savvy individuals. The sample consisted of 373 weekly observations on the dynamics of the BTC market. The results later conclude that there is the presence of impacts from both investors who are aiming to speculate the market and truly technology enthusiasts. The authors further recorded evidence of speculators following momentum strategy while the market was experiencing high volatility and shifting to contrarian strategy when the market was undergoing low volatility. In contrast, tech enthusiasts remained persistent to buy when price fell under their anticipating value and sell when price rose above their anticipating value (Lee et al., 2020). Furthermore, tech enthusiasts showed strong belief in the prospects of BTC and the blockchain technology which will drive and enhance general productivity in the near future (Lee et a., 2020). This research however only addresses the strategies of different crypto investors and not what made them decide on those investment strategies. Despite that, the authors emphasised it is highly necessary to study and gain a deeper understanding of the individuals who believe in the technological revolution and also make up for a significant portion of the studying sample (Lee et al., 2020).

Smutny et al. (2021) carried out a survey of 468 Czech crypto investors between the age of 18 and 42 using quota sampling. The purpose of the study is to investigate their motivational factors and their barriers to take risks in the cryptocurrency markets. The researchers identified lack of information and experience, negative encounters to be the main obstructions for them to fully participate in the markets. However, the desire to gain good profits from volatile speculation in value is determined to be the main motives of the researched respondents. The other motivational factors, that account of at least 85.7% for the male respondents and 78.4% of the female respondents, are anonymity and inability to seize crypto assets in a short period of time as well as the impossibility of cryptocurrency deflated by hyperinflations. One of the drawbacks from this research is that the sample was dedicated only to the Swedish investors. A more overview of a bigger sample from more global cryptocurrency investors around the world would conceivably provide more enhancing results and findings. Furthermore, although having a contribution in establishing different investing motives and behaviours between two genders, this paper does not cover how they can overcome the barriers to take risks. By doing this, one of the ways is to help investors understand more about the market, other agents' movements and be able to direct themselves based on that (Britainthinks, 2021). In a way, this calls out a necessity to other researchers to conduct more in-depth studies of investors' behaviours in the cryptocurrency market, conceivably by different theoretical approaches.

Sun, Dedahanov, Shin and Kim (2020) studied the encouragement and reasons of why traditional asset investors decided to switch to the cryptocurrency market. The researchers gathered data from 244 questionnaire participants and used structural equation model (SEM) for analysing methodology. The findings indicated that the majority of switchers accounted for personal innovativeness. The researchers explained the demographic details of this group are in line with middle-class and well educated earners who are also self-equipped with years of trading experience, hence, they looked for new investing opportunities to expand their monetary fund. Another motivational reason is outlined to be the preference of more retail investors in the cryptocurrency

market to the traditional security markets. As the traditional financial markets involve a large number of institutional investors, individual investors could see an imbalance of trading power (Sun et al., 2020). This results in less perceived risks for retail investors which motivates them to be more involved in the cryptocurrency market (Sun et al., 2020). This motivating perception can be considered to strengthen the concept of libertarianism where it promotes the idea of a free market system and everyone has an equal chance of developing their wealth (Collins, 2015). This could be considered to be a deeper view, unlike more surfacing aspects such as earning more income or a developed interest without an underlying belief. The findings from this research has created an incline and encouraged other researchers to find out more about these investors with a wiser intention in investing in cryptocurrency.

To support libertarianism as one of the fundamental ideas of why people participate in the crypto market, Bashir, Strickland and Bohr (2016) studied different aspects of BTC to gain a deeper understanding of why people are motivated to invest in it. The study sent out invitations to 7,500 students at a Midwestern University in the U.S, however, the response rate indicated only 7% of the whole sample. Students were chosen to participate as the author argued they can get familiarity with new technology quicker than other generations. The results showed certain attitudes varied from wealth, technology, politics and social structure. From the greater risks come with greater gain and attraction, BTC is also strongly appealing to individuals with libertarian ideology (Bashir et al., 2016). Although the sample is concentrated into more of a junior scholar and younger generation group, the decentralisation feature of cryptocurrency in general and BTC can be said to have rooted out among themselves and helped specifically to support their view of owning total freedom and less dependence on their government.

Khairuddin, Sas, Clinch and Davies (2016) conducted an exploratory research by interviewing 9 individual BTC users about why they participated in the market. The research findings indicated three main aspects namely the belief in a positive financial revolution, increase in society's approval and their perception on the true value of BTC. Apart from promoting a prospective future of BTC, the paper also emphasised on the

great benefits of blockchain technology. They endorse the value of a decentralisation system, democracy and financial reformation (Khairuddin et al, 2016). Hence, participation in the cryptocurrency market marks a crucial impact and is necessary for the people and organisation to adopt and utilise the use of the technology. It can be said that the 9 interviewees of this study share the same outlook on how BTC and the blockchain technology can transform the traditional finance system and have the possibility to create higher democracy for the present and future generation (Khairuddin et al., 2016). Although it might seem that there is a potential bias among all of the researched participants, the sample has addressed the importance of these motivations within the crypto space. The authors stated a strong need for more research to be conducted especially for this group of investors to hopefully gain more insights on their opinions and their behaviours in the cryptocurrency market.

Alqaryouti, Siyam, Alkashri and Shaalan (2020) examined the knowledge and experience of cryptocurrency users in qualitative research with structured interviews. All three interviewees demonstrated a good understanding on both technicality and nature of cryptocurrency. All three participants claimed to be most motivated with the feature of no intermediate parties when making transactions. They further demonstrated the ability to have full control over their funds in crypto, its flexibility, security and anonymity (Alqaryouti et al., 2020). Full control without central banks and governments is also determined to be the main reason why they would keep and be confident in using cryptocurrency in the future (Alqaryouti et al., 2020). This presents more evidence on the doubts among investors in a centralised authority to influence their wealth, hence, another encouragement of a decentralisation system. Nonetheless, this paper used a descriptive and exploratory approach which attempts to determine the profiles of this investor sample (Alqaryouti et al., 2020). Thus, it further calls out for a necessity of studying these individuals' investing behaviours to help others understand and construct more suitable strategies to strengthen their investment performance.

Mattke et al. (2020) identified lack of understanding on motivations of cryptocurrency investors, hence, more research is needed for this particular topic. By using a mixed research methodology on two different samples, they found a range of motivational types in BTC investments. They are anticipation of greater profits, ease of exchanging, ideology support, incline to gain investment skills as well as trading experience, and finally a risk seeking mentality (Mattke et al., 2020). Anticipation of greater profits was indicated as one of the motivations, however, the results showed lower significance compared to other motivations. Furthermore, one of the key finding takeaways from this research is that a portion of the studied sample would still invest in BTC even though they would not expect any profits from it. The explained reason for this is the continuance of supporting BTC ideology (Mattke et al., 2020). This is such an important aspect about addressing the difference between investors who express strong belief in cryptocurrency and speculative investors. At the conclusion of this paper, the authors urge other scholars to define a more in-depth role of decentralisation and cryptocurrency in the global society.

In summary, the motivations that lie within most advantages of using cryptocurrency can be seen to be present in most previous studies. These include the ease in using virtual currencies, decentralisation and possibility of great financial system transformation. This paper however seeks for deeper understanding in terms of fundamental values of why people invest in the cryptocurrency market. The concept of decentralisation, total democracy and less reliance on an authority body is determined to strongly coordinate with libertarian ideology in Bashar et al. (2016) and Khairuddin et al. (2016) amongst cryptocurrency investors. Characteristics alongside with the desire for a balance in trading power and full control of the cryptocurrency funds in Sun et al. (2020) and Alqaryouti et al. (2020) can further be considered to be related to a certain level of libertarian ideology. Apart from that, incentive aligned with increasing wealth is determined to remain popular amongst investors in the cryptocurrency market (Matteke et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Smutny et al., 2021). By following these arguments, this study focuses on two fundamental ideologies amongst crypto investors which are desires simply for generating greater wealth and for a deeper and not necessarily money-oriented belief. That is an anticipation that is in line with the

libertarianism ideology, a free-dom world and a possibility of worldwide monetary reform.

2.3.5. CONSUMER CHOICE AND CRYPTOCURRENCY DURING ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTY

ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTY

Economic or macroeconomic uncertainty entails an unpredictable and uncertain future prospect of an economy (Haddow, Hare, Hooley and Shakir, 2013). In other words, it means there is a lack of knowledge and information about predicting economic growth amongst all agents which causes them anxiety, concerns and delays in making decisions (Jackson, Kliesen and Owyang, 2018). Çolak, Guney and Hacıhasanoglu (2020) further stated an increase in economic uncertainty tends to trigger negative anticipations and downturn economic events. The most recent uncertainty events that are worth mentioning and have influenced the global economy are the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, and the exit of Britain from the EU (Brexit) for the case of the UK's economy (Lyon and Dhingra, 2021; Balbaa, Eshov and Ismailova, 2022). Jackson, Kliesen and Owyang (2018) specified the impact of a sudden rise in uncertainty could vary in many ways, including expectation of higher inflation rate, concerns for higher unemployment, disruption of investments and recruiting within firms, reduction in consumer spending and rising credit costs. To measure economic uncertainty, researchers have constructed and developed an abundance of methods based on different macroeconomic variables. However, one of the widely used key indicators among a large number of studies is the economic policy uncertainty index (EPU) by Baker, Bloom and Davis (2016). The EPU was also introduced as a tool to assist investors to track and evaluate their investment decisions (Jackson and Orr, 2019; Ashraf, Khawaja and Bhatti, 2022; Dejuan-Bitria and Ghirelli, 2021).

CRYPTO AS A HIGH-RISK INVESTMENT

After the introduction of the first cryptocurrency namely Bitcoin in 2009, the cryptocurrency market has increasingly developed followed by the creation of other coins using similar technology (Smales, 2022). As of November 2021, the market has grown to have more than 7,500 different securities with the total market value peaking at approximately \$2.7 trillion (Statista, 2022b; Statista, 2022c). Since the inception of Bitcoin, the total cryptocurrency market capitalisation was relatively flat until late 2020 according to CoinMarketCap (2022). The first market significant rally brought the capitalisation value to about \$2.5 trillion which was an over 250% increase with respect to the total value at the end of 2020 (CoinMarketCap, 2022). The second rally led the total market cap peaking at \$2.9 trillion and also marked its all time high. The third one resulted in the surpassing value of \$2.7 trillion as also specified earlier via Statista (CoinMarketCap, 2022). For Bitcoin, it has recorded a 62% increase in prices throughout 2021 with its all time high in the same year reaching \$68,649.05 per coin (Williams and Pistilli, 2022).

However, following these significant rallies, cryptocurrency investors had faced substantial losses measuring in thousands to millions of dollars because of the tumbles in the spot market. According to Malwa (2021), the drop of the market after the second rally in late 2021 caused around \$300 million of crypto traders to evaporate. Long positions on crypto futures contracts were forced to be liquidated within the matter of 24 hours (Malwa, 2021). The loss on long positions of Bitcoin was accounted to be \$94 million while closure of positions on Ethereum caused investors around \$57 million (Malwa, 2021). The liquidation on other altcoins such as LUNA and SOL took much lower losses, nonetheless, still to be measured in millions (Malwa, 2021). Furthermore, Coin360 (2022) has produced visualisation on the daily percentage change in total crypto market capitalisation with certain dominant coins such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, BitcoinCash, Ripple, Litecoin between the beginning of 2019 and September 2022. Viewers can see great fluctuations in percentage change of mainly three coins: Bitcoin, Ethereum and BitcoinCash. As can be seen in the chart, the Bitcoin market cap could

swing between 10-20% day over day whereas BitcoinCash can be seen with two substantial percentage changes in early 2020 and 2021.

Overall, the evidence on rallies, slumps and considerable changes on crypto prices has demonstrated how volatile and unpredictable the market has been and should it be considered to be a high-risk investing environment. Consequently, market participants are deemed to face a great level of future uncertainty. As the purpose of this paper is to uncover investors' behaviours in the cryptocurrency market, it is necessary to study their attitudes and choices in a more general high risk investing environment before exploring them in a more specific context of the crypto market.

HIGH RISK INVESTMENTS DURING ECONOMIC UNCERTAINTY

High risk investment is the type of investment involving quick and large swings in value over time (Simpson, 2022). These swings can potentially offer significant returns to the investment holders, however, they also face a risk of substantial losses (Simpson, 2022). Examples for high risk investments can be stocks and shares, private equity, hedge funds, crowdfunding, real estate and cryptocurrencies (FCA, n.d.). Contradictory, low risk investments, such as treasury bonds and money market funds, maintain much more stable rates and are less volatile overall. This means this type of investment provides lower income from investment but also less chance of big losses (Simpson, 2022). A big problem with low risk investments is when the product's or fund's growth rate is lower than the inflation rate. In this circumstance, low risk investors would suffer a reduced value in their own investments (Simpson, 2022). In a research about the relationship between risk and time with regards to high level of inflation, Elston research (2022) found that low risk investments such as cash and bonds offer lower bearing risk to investors in the short term but higher risk in the long term. This is because inflation rates can change more quickly and destroy the lower risk assets' purchasing power (Cobbe, 2022). This argument can be evidently seen across the performance of the S&P 500 and cash during the high inflation period in the UK starting 1972. According to Cobbe (2022), staying invested with the S&P 500 might not deliver positive returns on investment in the short duration of 5 years, nonetheless, it could generate positive rates of approximately 73% and 474% over 10 and 20 years respectively. In the UK, the 1970s were known for a time period with double digit inflation rates caused by the energy crisis and series of economic shocks (Macalister, 2011). Cobbe (2022) stated the purchasing power on cash to have significantly reduced from -54% to -84% over 5 and 20 years respectively (Cobbe, 2022). By taking both returns on the S&P 500 and purchasing power on cash across short and long term durations, investors are advised to be better off with riskier assets over longer investment periods and can use them to hedge against inflation.

	Over 5 years	Over 10 years	Over 20 years
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Return on the S&P 500	-1.3% (-0.5% annualised)	+72.9% (+5.6% annualised)	+473.7% (+9.1% annualised)
Purchasing power on cash	-54% (accounted for 14.2% annualised on average inflation)	-73% (accounted for 12.4% annualised on average inflation)	-84% (accounted for 8.8% annualised on average inflation)

Source: Cobbe (2022)

High risk investments such as stocks and shares are recommended as hedging instruments for investors for the long-term duration, however, this only works if it is certain that the nominal value of the invested assets or funds would increase gradually over time (Olesen, 2000). In the case of cryptocurrency, it can be highly volatile and treated as a high-risk asset class, nonetheless, it is still yet in a debate to be a hedge against inflation. With that being said, not every crypto asset can be considered to act as a hedge.

One of the principles to create deflationary is that a currency should have a limited supply level or quantity (Humphrey, 2003). The approximately 70% plunge in Bitcoin price between November 2021 to June 2022 called the crypto deflationary theory into question (Browne, 2022). As for Bitcoin, it has a limited supply and a capped price system, hence, its core fundamentals may strengthen the belief of an inflation hedge (Rudolf, Ajour El Zein and Lansdowne, 2021; Baur and Dimpfl, 2021). To demonstrate the value of Bitcoin for the long term contribution against inflation, more time is yet needed to test the argument as cryptocurrency is still classified as a new asset class (Albano, 2022; DeMatteo, 2022). However, higher inflation and economic uncertainty can be intertwined. If economic uncertainty can be looked at as a whole, numerous pieces of literature have studied the relations between it and BTC using EPU as the measurement tool. Besides BTC, there are also several other cryptocurrencies that have

limited level of supply such as LTC, and XRP. The following section will examine certain literatures to support this argument.

CRYPTOCURRENCY DURING UNCERTAINTY

Certain scholars have considered a number of crypto assets to be more or less a “safe haven” and can be compared to the gold and precious metal markets during worldwide financial turbulence. When BTC was first introduced in 2009 which is shortly after the global financial crisis in 2008, it can be considered that BTC was born for the purpose of a monetary and financial system transformation (Huhtinen, 2014). Although it took a period of time to get more acknowledged and recognised by the society, BTC has certainly become a trend and more cryptocurrencies are established. During the COVID-19 period, much attention was gained for the cryptocurrency market as BTC achieved its all time high (ATH) at around \$60,000 per coin in 2020.

This section will examine papers from previous scholars on investors’ engagement with some assets within the cryptocurrency markets when facing uncertainty. A range of scholars specifically concentrated on the economic policy uncertainty (EPU) to identify if an asset is a good diversifier. EPU can be understood as unpredictable changes in economic policy issues by a government when facing a crisis (Al-Thaqeb, Algharabali and Alabdulghafour, 2020). Some mixed findings from recent literature have been found on whether BTC and other cryptocurrencies can be a good asset class to hedge against uncertainty, however, crypto as a good hedge maintains to dominate.

Koumbe, Mudzingiri and Mba (2020) adopted the D-vine pair-copula method to examine the impact of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) on three cryptocurrencies namely BTC, ETH and XRP during a crisis. Using daily frequency in crypto prices, the author found that ETH is a better hedge than BTC and XRP during financial turbulence. While BTC has the biggest market cap in the market, ETH was evidently shown with

significant correlation to the US EPU. Furthermore, the study also proposed that EPU promotes the overall dynamic of the cryptocurrency market. Bouri, Lucey and Roubaud (2020) studied the diversification impacts of BTC, ETH and LTC against the APAC and Japanese equity markets. To investigate this, the authors adopt a mixture of a conditional correlation approach and regression analysis on the daily data between 2015 and 2018. While the findings proposed all three types of cryptocurrencies show evidence of being great diversifiers against the studied stock markets and can be used as hedging assets when facing uncertainty, BTC and ETH are considered as slightly better hedge than LTC. The conclusions also indicated similarity in the case of hedging with gold and crude oil.

Bouri, Shahzad, Roubaud, Kristoufek and Lucey (2020) also investigated the extent of BTC, gold and commodity indices against different types of equity markets such as emerging, American and Chinese. The study adopted the wavelet coherence approach to test the dependency of proposed diversifying options on the stock markets. Results suggested there is smallest dependency present with BTC, hence, it can be endorsed as a good hedge as prices are shown to be not correlated in extreme downtrend of the equity markets. With that being said, BTC still cannot be compared to be identical to gold because it has not achieved a great price track record and stability like gold is during previous financial turbulences. Fang, Su and Yin (2020) used the GARCH-MIDAS model to study the influence by hedging five different cryptocurrencies on News-based Implied Volatility (NVIX) and the S&P 500 index. The authors selected the long-term volatility of BTC, ETH, XRP, LTC and XLM by examining both daily and monthly data to assess the impacts. They conclude that all five cryptocurrencies show positive and significant evidence as a hedge against NVIX and the S&P 500.

Paule-Vianez, Prado-Roman and Gomez-Martinez (2020) examined BTC and gold's daily prices between July 2010 and April 2019 with impacts on EPU. The purpose of the paper is to identify if BTC can be seen as a safe haven like gold or more of a speculative security during market turbulence. Their empirical findings show that returns on investment of BTC as well as perceived risk increased as financial markets experience

more uncertainty. Further conclusion also proposed BTC is almost identical to gold during unpredictable times and can act as a safe haven. Hence, the author suggested investors can consider BTC specifically as an option to exchange funds to protect their own wealth. Jiang, Wu, Tian and Nie (2021) presented similar results not only with BTC but most cryptocurrencies as diversifiers against Chinese, American and British EPU in the context of COVID-19. The study confirms cryptocurrencies, especially XLM, can be considered to be good hedging options when EPU is expected to be high, however, it does not necessarily remain when EPU is low or moderate. The paper further stated with evidence that XRP and XLM particularly showed great resilience against significant times of a crisis. In addition, BTC and XLM are considered as good diversifiers for both retail and institutional investors. However, the hedging range can be expanded more with LTC and XMR for retail investors.

Another study on the effect of EPU on BTC during the coronavirus pandemic can be viewed in Raheem (2021). Raheem (2021) applied ordinary least squares regression analysis on daily data to test the hypothesis whether BTC can be seen as a safe haven during the pandemic. The results show that BTC is a safe haven for the prior phase of COVID-19. Nonetheless, after the pandemic was officially declared, the null hypothesis was tested to be insignificant to reject. The study further suggests that BTC can only maintain and act as a good hedge when the financial markets still experience calm manners and not yet panics.

On the other hand, other scholars have shown different findings where BTC and other cryptocurrencies are not good hedging tools during uncertainty. An instance is Hasan, Hassan, Karim and Rashid (2022). The authors used a combination of approaches such as OLS, quantile and quantile-on-quantile regression model to assess the hedging effect of BTC, gold and US dollars in different types of contexts namely bearish, bullish and stable stages. The results suggest while gold remains to be a safe haven during highly unpredictable times, BTC and US dollars reveal negative impact and cannot act as hedging items for uncertainty. Furthermore, the researchers also implies investors should add cryptocurrency risks to the present unassertiveness.

Cheema, Szulczyk and Bouri (2020) tested EPU indices from 10 different countries including America, the UK, Russia, China and Japan if they can predict positive total cryptocurrency returns. Monthly data was gathered during the period of 2013 to 2019 and the research hypothesis was further tested with robustness using three quantitative methodologies: OLS, augmented and quantile regression analysis. Their empirical findings suggest the EPU indices do predict positive aggregate returns of cryptocurrency but only in the long-run. Therefore, market participants and investors should carefully consider whether to include cryptocurrency in their portfolio diversification as short term results might not be consistent. In other words, cryptocurrency cannot be determined for sure as safe haven during turbulent periods.

Similarly, Wu, Tong, Yang and Derbali (2019) assessed the hedging properties of gold and BTC with respect to EPU shock. The research obtained daily returns for both securities and performed GARCH model and quantile regression using dummy variables to test the hypothesis of significance in hedging effects. They concluded that both gold and BTC cannot be considered to be complete safe havens during uncertain periods. In fact, they show weak effects in both upturn and downturn conditions. However, they can still be used as diversification for investment portfolios for normal times. Further findings include BTC to be more sensitive in reaction to EPU shocks whereas gold seemed to be less volatile and more stable compared to BTC.

Fasanya, Oliyide, Adekoya and Agbatogun (2021) studied the BTC and precious metal markets to see if they can be considered to be hedging tools against US EPU. By analysing the daily data of 10 years from 2010 to 2020 with spillover tests and nonparametric causality-in-quantiles approaches, the authors found strong evidence of sensitivity of BTC to the US EPU shocks, especially during the COVID-19 period. Further evidence shows that BTC and precious metal markets are strongly correlated during more tranquil times but less connected when certain market stress prevails. Hence, investors, analysts and policy makers are suggested to not assume BTC to be a good hedge property when facing uncertainty.

2.3.6. CRYPTOCURRENCY AND MARKET EFFICIENCY

More detailed and thorough discussion on market efficiency can be found later in the literature review chapter. As research objectives will be focusing on the cryptocurrency investors and behavioural finance biases which provide certain disagreement on assumptions of market efficiency, it is important to understand previous literature have been reporting on the efficiency of the cryptocurrency market. This particular topic has gained much attention from researchers, however, a mixture of findings has been observed. However, it can be said that the evidence of market inefficiency is more intensive and wider compared to reports on a certain level of efficiency.

Le Tran and Leivrik (2020) addressed from their empirical findings from the five large cryptocurrencies namely BTC, EOS, ETH, LTC and XRP with the data obtained from the public database Coinmarketcap.com. They indicated that these cryptocurrency markets have not always been efficient. In particular, only the period after 2017 showed some signs of market efficiency whereas it could be considered to be no efficiency before this time. Overall, XRP is suggested to be the cryptocurrency with the highest level of efficiency and LTC acquired for the least.

In line with the results from Tran and Leivrik (2020), Kristoufek (2018) studied the two pairs of BTC markets with respect to the US dollar and Chinese Yuan and found that these markets show inefficiency for most of the period between 2010 and 2017. Interestingly, the only times that BTC is considered to be reasonably efficient are the calming periods after a surge in prices. Furthermore, the author suggested the pair BTC-USD showed more tendency of inefficiency than the pair BTC-CNY. Kristoufek and Vosvrda (2019) tested the market hypothesis on a set of high-frequently traded cryptocurrencies including BTC, DASH, LTC, XMR, XRP and XLM. The collected data ranged from 2015 to 2018. The authors analysed the overall period using the Efficiency Index and concluded that the markets are inefficient on average. However, for the

period between July 2017 and June 2018, evidence on market efficiency was found on most studied markets. Amongst the set of the cryptocurrencies mentioned above, DASH was awarded to have the highest market efficiency in this period whereas ETH and LTC were stated to be the least efficient cryptocurrencies.

In contrast, the amount of literature on total evidence of market inefficiency seems to be greater than the ones introducing some confirmation of efficiency. Urquhart (2016) used a range of 6 robustness tests on information effectiveness of BTC and only tested for the presence of weak efficiency. The sample period was also divided to be two parts of 2010-2013 and 2013-2016. The author concluded that BTC remained to be totally inefficient throughout both of the periods. However, the Ljung-box and AVR tests demonstrated some signs of market efficiency for the second period. The author later suggested that BTC might be becoming more efficient in the near future. Similarly, Vidal-Tomas and Ibanez (2018) studied the BTC market with the hypothesis to follow a semi-strong form of market efficiency. The results suggest that BTC did not respond to events relating to a change in monetary policy. However, the market picked up some movements when there was both good and bad news relating to the cryptocurrency as a whole.

Jiang, Nie and Ruan (2018) employed the rolling window approach and a new efficiency index to assess the market efficiency of the BTC market between the period 2010 and 2017. The use of the rolling window approach is believed to provide more consistent and reliable findings. Subsequently, the author reports on what they found from the acquired daily data to be strongly inefficient. The reasons for this were suggested to be a reasonable amount of irrational investors and lack of pricing structure. Nevertheless, the researchers of this study recommend that future studies with better pricing theories are needed to justify their findings. Wei (2018) assessed a total of 456 cryptocurrencies with their liquidity and efficiency levels. The proposed result suggested that while BTC did show very few signs of market efficiency while other cryptocurrency are illiquid, hence resulting in investors' inability to act quick enough.

Hu, Valera and Oxley (2019) used the sample of 31 largest cryptocurrencies by market cap at the time of conducting research to test for the efficiency of the whole market across different periods. The authors employed cross-sectional dependence in panels and unit root tests to test the hypothesis. The results return with no indication of market efficiency in any of the 31 cryptocurrencies, hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Caporale, Gil-Alana and Caporale, Gil-Alana and Plastun (2018) applied two different long-memory techniques namely R/S analysis and fractional integration to analyse the market efficiency of BTC, LTC, XRP and DASH over the period of 2013-2017. Suggested findings are suggested to be similar with previous papers where there is no evidence of market efficiency amongst all four cryptocurrencies. Zargar and Kumar (2019) undertook a more intensive approach on frequency of data where they acquire 15, 30, 60, 120 minutes and daily BTC prices. The research was conducted and tested the hypothesis using different ratio tests. The findings indicated that the higher the frequency in data, the more evidence of market inefficiency and random behaviours in prices. Al-yahyaee, Mensi and Yoon (2018) examined four types of markets namely BTC, gold, equity and currency markets. The results of this research further support the inefficiency of BTC and stated BTC to be the most inefficient market amongst all four.

2.4. DECISION THEORIES FROM THE TRADITIONAL FINANCE AND BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE PERSPECTIVE

2.4.1. WHAT IS DECISION MAKING?

Decision making exists in everyone's daily life where it involves the act of selecting the best possible course of action between two or more to solve a facing problem. That can be ranging from simple issue such as what to have for dinner or what is the best route to get to a destination, to more serious life-changing decision such as what higher education degree is best suited for an individual, what pension fund should one invest in or is it a right decision to get married with a particular person. Certainly with more trivial issues, it is quite easy and takes a small amount of time to conclude with the best option. However, when dealing with more complex matters, people have to take more time, gather more information and produce analysis on the problem in order to see which alternative is the most reasonable and helps to achieve the best outcome.

Name of scholars	Published book	Definition of decision-making
Koontz and O'Donnell	Principles of Management: An analysis of Managerial Functions (1972)	Decision making is the actual selection from among alternatives of a course of action
George R.Terry	Principles of Management by George R. Terry (1972)	Decision-making is the selection based on some criteria from two or more possible alternatives
Andrew D. Szilagyi	Management and	Decision-making is a process involving

	performance (1981)	information choice of alternative actions, implementations and evaluation that is directed to the achievement of certain stated goals
James A.F. Stoner, and R. Edward Freeman	Management (1995)	Decision making is the process of identifying and selecting a course of action to solve a specific problem
F.A. Shull, A.L. Delbecq and L.L. Cummings	Organisational decision making (1970)	Decision making is a conscious human process involving both individual and social phenomena based on upon actual and value premises which conclude with a choice of one behavioural activity from two or more alternatives with the intention of moving towards some desired state of affairs
J. Edward Russo	Neuroeconomics, judgement and decision making (2015)	Decision-making is the process whereby an individual, group or organisation reaches conclusions about what future actions to pursue given a set of objectives and limits on available resources. This process will be often iterative, involving issue framing, intelligence-gathering, coming to conclusions and learning from experience

Koontz and O'Donnell (1972) and Terry (1972) defined decision making as a selection between multiple alternative actions while Szilagyi (1981) and other scholars mentioned above used the word 'process'. A selection is simply an action of choosing between the already available options, however, the definition from Kootnz and O'Donnell (1972) can be considered to be too general and does not specify on what

matter that the true selection should be made. The definition from Terry (1972) further added that the selection should be based on “some criteria”. This is pivotal in the decision-making, nonetheless, this definition remains to be relatively modest in terms of wording. Fischer, Greiff and Funke (2015) described that dynamic decision-making is the fourth step or action within a complex problem solving process after information generation, information filtering and model building. However, this step should comprise a system for effectiveness and best outcome achievement. Therefore, the author would argue that it is more meticulous to refer to decision-making as a ‘process of selection’ instead of just ‘a selection’. Furthermore, this shall be in line with all definitions from most well respected dictionaries that have defined decision-making as a process.

The definition introduced by Szilagyi (1981) derives from the fact that people should carefully filter information for each alternative action and execute the best action to achieve the predetermined goals. This is further agreed in the definition by Stoner and Freeman (1995). However, Szilagyi (1981) was slightly more detailed on the choosing of information and executing steps as the substitute for ‘identifying’. During a discussion about decision-making in his published book “The managerial decision-making process”, Harrison (1975) highlighted that the decision-making should be fixated by at least one of the factors that are the decision to be made, the decision maker and the decision making process. This explains the proposal of a more constructive definition for decision-making from Shull, Delbecq and Cummings (1975). The definition from these authors follows all three variables whereas:

- The decision is to be sought giving the objective of “some desired state of affairs”
- The decision maker is the individual owning his or her conscious reasons to make the decision
- The decision-making process involves consideration of human values learned from social phenomena as well as subjective goals so that a decision can be made more or less rationally

2.4.2. DECISION MAKING UNDER TRADITIONAL FINANCE

When it comes to the decision making process, it usually requires decision makers to consider their outcomes or expectations and the associated underlying risks (Slovic, Kunreuther and White, 2016). Here the involved risks can also be identified as the probability of the opposite consequence or in case of three or more possible outcomes, the probability should be weighted accordingly (Millroth, 2020). Therefore, decision makers can measure for themselves what the most and least risky choices are with the intention to achieve what they want and furtherly to proceed with the most optimal option (Kant, 1991). This decision-making process shall define the decision makers themselves as rational thinkers (Jonge, 2012). In traditional finance, economic theorists believe that all investors process information and behave 'rationally' when putting in buy or sell orders, in order to maximise expected returns (Siegel, 2007; Subramaniam and Velnampy, 2017). The word 'rational' is truly the main key term as it indicates two significant points for investors and share prices (Fama, 1970). Firstly, when approaching new information, investors are assumed to possess relevant skill sets as well as knowledge to make the most out of it to have a fair view on a company's value and not make themselves confused with cognitive mistakes or information gathering errors (Fama, 1970; Kamoune and Ibenrissoul, 2022). Hence, they can construct the most optimal and logical investment moves. This also means that they consistently do not let their emotions be involved in their decision-making process. The theory insists the motivation behind the unemotional and unbiased behaviour is due to investors always making their decisions by exercising perfect self-control and based on their best long-term self-interest (Bisati, Haque, Ganai and Gulzar, 2021). Secondly, all assets and securities are fairly valued as the results of completely rational investment behaviours in the market (Fama, 1970). In other words, it is not possible to spot opportunities for any undervalued or overvalued stocks in order to acquire exceeding profits on the markets.

In some situations, it is not possible for decision makers to assign any probability to their choices because of uncertainty. When the state of uncertainty exists, it could be due to the unavailability of key information or decision makers not possessing the

relevant knowledge. Examples can be found in normal daily life such as obtaining a letter without knowing its delivery date for key information missing and picking wrong ingredients to cook for not knowing what is exactly needed for the dish. In finance, the decision to buy or sell is a type of decision making that could be uncertain to investors; simply because they do not acquire enough knowledge and/or are unable to obtain certain pieces of data to perform a comprehensive technical and fundamental analysis. So, the question is how do investors make their investment decision if the probability of the outcomes is unknown to them? Rational choice theory is introduced to overcome this matter.

2.4.2.1. RATIONAL CHOICE THEORY (EXPECTED UTILITY THEORY)

THE BERNOULLI'S PRINCIPLE

Expected utility theory was introduced as a tool for decision making when risks are involved and there is an outcome uncertainty. The theory also defines a rational person, referring as a homo economicus, is the most practical individual and always makes their decisions with the intention to maximise their utility (Peterson, 2019). It was first used as the sole foundation to explain human's decision making in 1738 by Daniel Bernoulli – a prominent mathematician and physicist from a highly science and mathematics orientated family in the Netherlands (Peterson, 2019). Bernoulli's work is also known as the solution to the St. Petersburg paradox which is to find the best pay-in value of money for a game player in a coin tossing game (Peterson, 2019). The game works as follows:

- Head must appear for the player to get to the next toss. If the tail appears, the game ends and the player wins whatever is in the pot.
- For the first round, if the tail appears, they get \$2 and the game is over. If the head appears, they get the second toss.

- For the second toss, if the tail appears, they get \$4 and the game stops. If head appears again, they move on to the third toss.
- For the third toss, if the tail appears, they get \$8, game over. In case the head appears, they get the next toss and so on.
- To summarise, the pay-out for each round of the game is $\$2^n$ until the tail appears. The probability for the tail to appear for each round is $\frac{1}{n}$ (where n is the number of rounds).

The game basically suggests if maximising expected value is the winning objective, the player would be willing to pay an indefinite amount of money to play the game as the expected value is infinity (expected value for the whole game is the sum of expected value for each toss). Nonetheless, no reasonable individuals realistically would want to do that. Instead of using expected value, Bernoulli proposed a convincing solution to the paradox using expected utility. The mathematician made a clear distinction between the 'utility of money' and the 'value of money', explaining that people tend to maximise their expected utility rather than the game's expected value. The concept of diminishing marginal utility is also used to argue that a game player's utility tends to shrink as additional monetary gain is added. Therefore, it helps the player to identify a finite amount of money they are willing to pay for the game.

In order to build the model, the player needs to assign their utility for each payoff. The player's expected utility for the whole game will be the sum of corresponding probability for the game to continue in each round and each payoff's utility measured as before. This will identify the amount of money a rational person would like to pay to play the game. This is known as Bernoulli's formulation.

The Bernoulli formulation however is only able to solve the paradox when the payoff is equal to \$2. If the payoff is raised above \$2, the formulation crumbles as utility for the raised payoff will become different. The paradox became unsolved again until 1944,

when John Von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern developed a more sophisticated model to solve the problem based on the conception of utility (Fishburn, 1989).

THE VON NEUMANN AND MORGENSTERN THEOREM

In 1944, John Von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern made a publication of their book called 'Theory of Games and Economic Behaviour' (Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944). It introduces an extension axiom of consumer's behaviour in regard to risk and uncertainty. This is also known as the Von Neumann-Morgenstern (VNM) utility function or theorem. The theorem however did not refer to the St. Petersburg paradox as the problem but a lottery gambling game. Its objective is to help assign specific utility values for each available lottery prize. This should be equivalent to the issue in the St. Petersburg paradox when the stake value is different.

It uses the expected utility as the based concept, suggesting players to proceed with the option that produces the highest associated expected utility for the players themselves. Each option involves a different number of outcomes, their associated utilities and level of probability. The expected utility for each outcome is subjected to personal preference. They need to rank what prize they most and least prefer and assign utility value accordingly to each prize. Under this state of uncertainty, the utility value here basically is used as a tool for probability distributions of winning the prize. The most optimal choice is the one that maximises the probability-weighted average of expected utility value. Ultimately, this has explained the question raised above and concludes that the way to assign unknown probabilities to an outcome is using a person's own utility value. In other words, it refers to the amount of desirability an individual has in order to win something.

2.4.2.2. A RANDOM WALK

In previous subchapters, the expected utility theory was developed to be the foundation of a decision-making process with uncertainty. The uncertainty can be largely seen in the stock markets and one of the most traditional theories to explain this is the Random Walk theory. This theory was raised by Burton Malkiel in his famous book “A Random Walk Down Wall Street” published in 1973 (Smith, 2020). The assumption of the theory is that the price of a stock tomorrow is independent of its past prices and the probability of it hiking up or down should be the same at fifty percent (Malkiel, 1973). In other words, it suggests that investors cannot predict the movement of future stock prices. If one is looking to achieve abnormal returns for their portfolio, they would need to take on above market risks. Furthermore, the theory also suggests that both technical and fundamental analysis cannot be dependable as the direction of price movements is absolutely unknown according to the random walk.

Investors who follow this theory are advised that they might be better off with a passive fund, rather than pursuing active fund managers. After more than 140 contests, the Wall Street Journal presented the results, which showed the experts won 87 of the contests and the dart throwers won 55 (Smith, 2020). However, the results showed that the experts were only able to beat the Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJIA) in 76 contests. Malkiel commented that the experts' picks benefited from the publicity jump in the price of a stock that tends to occur when stock experts make a recommendation (Smith, 2020). Passive management proponents contend that, because the experts could only beat the market half the time, investors would be better off investing in a passive fund that charges far lower management fees.

2.4.2.3. EFFICIENT MARKET HYPOTHESIS

Another stream of traditional finance is Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH). It was developed by Eugene F. Fama in 1965, assuming that the share prices that are presented to the investors today should reflect all the available information and they are fairly valued (Sewell, 2011). The basis of this hypothesis is similar to the Random Walk theory in terms of future price being independent to past performance of a stock.

The EMH's assumption produces two fundamental assertions about the EMH. One is that all public information is reflected in the asset prices immediately once released (Fama, 1970). This implies a totally perfect market competition where there is no room or ability for purchasing undervalued stocks or closing a trade at an overvalued price (Fama, 1970). Another assertion of the EMH is that in an efficient market, it is impossible to achieve abnormal returns without accepting the above average risks (Fama, 1970). In other words, investors cannot beat or outperform the market index. However, a certain number of phenomena have arisen in today's world that are considered to be 'unusual' under the EMH's assumption of perfectly rational markets. If stock prices always reflect all the information and fair value of their assets, market bubbles should not come into existence (Topol, 1991). In an economic context, a bubble refers to a scenario where there is a rapid climbing in value of an individual security, asset class or an entire market, followed by a sudden and significant crash (Topol, 1991). It happens when the presented market price exceeds its true value by a great margin. The crash following the price escalation then occurs to enforce a market correction (Topol, 1991). Another 'unusual' market phenomena is records of active fund managers' performance to have outperformed the benchmark and acquire abnormal profits consistently for a long period of time (Ninan, 2021).

ACTIVE FUND MANAGERS

It has been quite controversial that EMH is true in reality. According to the SPIVA U.S. Scorecard published in 2018, over 90% of all active investment funds across large-cap, mid-cap and small-cap have been unable to outperform S&P indices relatively over the 15-year period (Soe, Liu and Preston, 2018). Although most general investors fail to outperform the market benchmark, there are nonetheless a long list of investors who have managed to have the market beaten. These investors tend to have highly similar investment strategies: disbelieve in EMH and believe that the equity market follows a random walk, thus, they should have their own technique or investing formula to overcome the random walk. In many cases, most investors who outperform the stock market are determined to focus on either value stocks or growth stocks. Value stocks are the ones priced significantly low compared to their true or fair value, but they are believed to follow market corrections eventually to reach the right price (Malkiel, 2003). Hence, the purpose is to maximise expected gains. Growth stocks are securities believed to have great potential in generating higher cash flows and profitability than average (Malkiel, 2003). There are many examples to be referred to regarding active managers who managed to outperform market indices on a long-term basis. However, this thesis will present one representative case each for the value stock and growth stock approach.

The first and foremost instance is the world-renowned billionaire and great stock market investor, Warren Buffett. He is the owner and CEO of Berkshire Hathaway. This investor profile could not be unmentionable for his track record of successfully having Berkshire Hathaway beat the S&P 500 by 2.5 million percentage points over the last 50 years or more (Gupta, 2020). One of Warren Buffett's investing philosophies is not supporting the EMH by not considering the equity market activities at all but rather look at companies' business indices and form a strategic analysis (Insider, 2010). He believes that by looking at all financial and operation prospects of a company as a whole is the major component that will decide whether it is a good or bad investment in the long term, regardless of short-term stock price changes. Indeed, not everyone can identify high potential profit generated investments, but good decision making will also depend on an active fund manager's intellectual level, personality, and attitude, said in Warren Buffett's comments to his nine selective apprentices (Insider, 2010). These nine

apprentices also managed to gain abnormal returns against the benchmark index and are the followers of Graham-and-Doddsville approach, similarly to Buffett (Insider, 2010).

Another great example is the legendary investor, Peter Lynch, who was proved to have also had beaten the S&P500 with his Fidelity's Magellan Fund, by expanding his assets from being worth \$18 million in 1977 to \$14 billion to 1990 (Perlberg, 2013). In the recent interview with Baystate Business of Bloomberg Radio, Lynch asserted that it would be a mistake for anyone to switch from actively managing their fund to passive as following the market index (Mohamed, 2021). Unlike Warren Buffett's belief in value stocks, Lynch emphasises the importance of the growth stock approach. He popularised the Fidelity's own approach which is Growth at a Reasonable Price (GARP) as the primary step for picking stocks (Chen, 2022a). GARP concentrates on the price to earnings (P/E) ratio of a company and its growth rate. For example, if the P/E ratio for the last year of company A is less than its historical growth rate of the last 3 years, it indicates that company A's stock is being traded at a bargain price and should be picked to invest in. On the contrary, if company A's P/E ratio is higher than the growth rate, this stock is not so attractive since it will not maximise the investment as time goes along. Lynch articulates on his belief that a fair value of a company would have its P/E ratio equal to its growth rate (Kennon, 2021).

They all reject the efficiency of the markets as there is clear evidence that exceptionally skilled active fund managers can achieve far more superior results compared to the benchmark, not particularly just in the short run but in the long run. If the EMH is valid, it means that these fund managers who have beaten the market for such long periods of time were purely but consistently lucky. Critics also look at another phenomena to pinpoint that the EMH is invalid, which is market bubbles.

MARKET BUBBLES

The EMH states that all asset prices are at their true values and there shall not be any undervalued transactions to be proceeded to achieve abnormal returns. A market bubble normally occurs following a sudden market crash where the market is basically adjusting itself to the more rational and reasonable price at the time (Topol, 1991). It also happens when the market is inefficient to the point where the stock mark-up price does not make sense, when there should be a lot of due diligence missing and people keep pumping the price until the bubble pops (Pederson, 2022). They tend to think that it is a good investment because everyone else is doing it (which they believe it must be good and the price would just go up nonetheless). During the life cycle of a bubble, it can be quite misleading and difficult for market participants to actually detect either a bubble or a genuine price speculation (Pederson, 2022).

The dotcom bubble began from the late 1990s when the use of the internet was booming and became essential in every day's life, followed by a huge escalating series of advancement in computer technology. The dotcom bubble burst around the early of 2000 and at the end of the year, the NASDAQ exchange dropped to 1173 points from 5132.52 as at its peak on March 10th, 2000 (Carter, 2020). In other words, approximately 73% of the dotcom value, meaning over 4 billion dollars evaporated in the matter of 6 months (Ofek and Richardson, 2003). Unlike Amazon, Ebay and Shutterfly which participated but survived the dotcom bubble and became some of the biggest corporations in the world nowadays, companies such as Boo.com, Pets.com, The Leaning Company and many more declared bankruptcies as soon as the bubble burst. An explanation to this is corporates such as Amazon and Ebay were determined to prove that their products were feasible and focused more on branding and product development while the majority that failed were targeting on winning the bet of gaining huge market share (Ofek and Richardson, 2003). The truth only revealed when investors realised the unrealistic ideas of the dotcom companies' ideas and their inability of making profits and actual production, they lost the confidence in these companies and proceeded with liquidity, resulting in such a quick crumble of the dotcom wave (Ofek and Richardson, 2003). In conclusion, it cannot be said that the trading price of these dotcom companies reflected all information about themselves. If that was the case, market participants would not make completely irrational

investments on entirely unfeasible and unrealistic products with no chance to generate returns. Another perspective to look at is the media presentation. The price speculation seemed to be incredibly sensitive to the reported news. According to the EMH, it could be valid to say that the information transposed to the public did reflect on the dotcom companies' prices, however, the reality was the information reported were not accurate and credible.

Another event relating to market bubbles is the global financial crisis 2007-2009. The crisis was estimated to cost over 10 trillion USD and over 30 million people ended up in unemployment (IMF, 2010). This is due to the collapse of Lehman Brothers, which was in the top four biggest investment banks in the United States at the time, by underwriting an overwhelmingly mortgage-backed asset portfolio while engulfed with the subprime borrowing culprits (Rudd, 2009). This led to the house market bubble significantly inflating since 2003/2004 to pop. People reached their point where they no longer could afford to pay their mortgages and simply the market also did not have any more buyers. Across the crisis period between 2007 and 2009, the stock market indices, including NASDAQ, S&P500 and Dow Jones, dropped by more than 50 percent (Williams, 2022). Many financial critics have blamed the credibility of EMH for this crisis event since it should have reflected the fair value of all market stocks. Robert Shiller, the economist from Yale University, and the Business Week magazine similarly criticised EMH as such a failure theory in the world of economics (Malkiel, 2011). Furthermore, Justin Fox, the author of the bestselling book *The Myth of the Rational Market* in 2010, believed the EMH misled the majority of investors and was the reason causing the recurrent credit crisis (Malkiel, 2011). Jeremy Grantham, a British investor and big vocal critic on financial disasters, and Paul Krugman of the New York Times shared the same view with Justin Fox, claiming that the theory was directly responsible for the housing market bubble which led to the biggest global financial crash in history.

A recent short term price speculation of "meme stocks" in 2021 was another market bubble that challenges EMH. Reddit users from the thread [r/WallStreetBets](#) and their followers on other social media platforms allied together to drive up the price of certain

underperforming stocks, referred to as “meme stocks” (Costolla, Iacoppini and Santagiustina, 2021) . These stocks normally account for a large portion under short positions amongst hedge funds. The idea of inflating the price of these stocks emerged and served as an action by retail investors against large institutional investors who intend to take advantage of the financial distress and manipulate the market during the COVID-19 pandemic (Costolla et al., 2021). It can be said that the concept and the execution of “meme stocks” arose from the emotional side of retail investors. The main evidence of “meme stocks” are GameStop (GME) and AMC Entertainment Holdings Inc (AMC), with stock price rallies accounted for approximately 620% and 1,000% respectively during 2021 (Li, 2021). However, as it was more or less a rebellion act of retail investors for a short period of time and the rallied stock prices did not reflect the intrinsic value of these stocks, they started to deflate shortly after. This whole market phenomena has put rather a challenge to the EMH, proving that markets are not always efficient. Furthermore, it seems that certain market manipulation can always exist which causes inaccurate indication of face value and true prospect from an asset’s price. In this case, GME, AMC and many other “meme stocks” were nominated by retail investors from the internet to fight market manipulation by short-selling from institutional investors; they were also used as a tool for retail investors to manipulate the market themselves and drive the stocks up. In a way, the “meme stock” market bubble has demonstrated the incredibility and unreliability of EMH.

2.4.3. DECISION MAKING UNDER BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE

In contrast to traditional finance regarding the assumption of a perfectly rational human being, it is quite clear that humans have emotions and are not always rational in reality (Sevil, Sen and Yalama, 2007). In fact, they would be considered abnormal and 'off' like a robot if they consistently act rationally and emotionless. They also have limits on their self-control, and each owns a different ability, amount of knowledge and intelligence to perceive new information (Akerlof and Shiller, 2010). Moreover, human biases do exist in everyday activities whether they were born with the biases, or they arose from the surrounding environment. When it comes to investing, it is believed to have no exception. Khoshnood and Khoshnood (2011) strongly emphasises that factors such as personality, personal judgement and social experience can cause behavioural biases while making an investment decision.

Traczyk et al. (2021) further added that emotions can be an important agent in violating the rational axioms in making economic choices. Through the research of Mitroi and Oproiu (2014), it suggested when people are going through a distressing situation that makes them anxious and distracted, they tend to become more pessimistic, impatient and unable to think clearly. The level of stress evolved from the facing situation offsets the rational mindset and creates mistakes in information processing such as "overtrading, overconfidence or illusion of control" (Mitroi and Oproiu, 2014).

In addition, apprehensive people are more likely to avoid spending money and high-stake investments while ones with high scores of extroversion and self-control tend to be involved in riskier investments (Maner et al., 2007; Gambetti and Giusberti, 2019). Evidently, everyone is not the same and human related factors can cause cognitive errors, bad investment decisions and the inability to be a completely rational investor as well as to maximise their own expected utility. This has been constantly challenging the assumption under traditional finance theory where all market participants are rational and the markets are always efficient. The question then is: does traditional finance or EMH hold validity where it is a common sense for a human acting like a human in

reality? From the beginning of 1980s, the EMH was continually questioned as a result of unexplained and excessive volatility within the stock markets (Shiller, 2003). The concept of behavioural finance was later arose and has been used to address a catalogue of human biases and irrationality which could lead to financial market inefficiencies.

Behavioural finance is an area within economics and finance that proposes theoretical axioms using psychological analysis to explain investors' economic decisions and unusual movements of financial markets. It was described by Van Boven, Kamada and Gilovich (1999) as a combination of psychology, economics and finance seeking to interpret human illogical and irrational decisions when taking monetary interests into consideration. These decisions are asserted to further influence financial markets, causing phenomena inconsistency and market anomalies (Frankfurter and McGoun, 2002; Shefrin, 2001; Sewell, 2007; Forbes, 2009). The underlying assumption of behavioural finance is that a market participant's decision as well as market outcomes are interconnected and systematically influenced by his or her own individual characteristics and perception on information processing (Qawi, 2010).

According to Sarri (2016), "the human brain uses shortcuts and emotional filters to categorise information and save time". In many cases, investors fail to react to relevant information and do not possess enough knowledge to form a reliable trading analysis (Shleifer, 2000). They choose to listen to abbreviated guidance from financial experts or follow the crowd, speculations or rumours instead and abandon the possibility of more portfolio diversification, selling high and buying low (Shleifer, 2000; Grable and Joo, 2004; Muhammad and Adullah, 2009; Jamal et al., 2015). This process can seriously damage an investing decision where the decision maker acts in an irrational manner and does not thoroughly consider the full consequences of their actions. That can lead to the failure to achieve the most optimal outcome on personal wealth as well as making investors themselves to lose money on more tax liabilities and costly managed investment funds (Shleifer, 2000).

Further impacts on irrational decisions can be complete inefficiencies of the capital markets and worsen financial performance on the corporation level (Szyszka, 2013). As a result, behavioural finance emerged with the attempt to eliminate or conceivably minimise these impacts and provide insights in the way people make economic decisions as well as how to improve them.

2.4.3.1. BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE VERSUS TRADITIONAL FINANCE

Whereas traditional finance suggested all market participants are homo economicus or economic men, meaning they have the infinite ability to consistently maximise their own utility in decision-making, behaviourists argue that is an ideal world, not the existing realistic world (Brzezicka and Wiśniewski, 2014). The main differences between traditional and behavioural finance are summarised as follows:

- **Information:** Traditional finance assumes people own the complete ability to process information correctly, precisely and are free from bias. In contrast, behavioural finance considers the human aspect, disputing that investors are under influence of their own emotions and often use shortcuts in making investment decisions. They can turn to risk averse when they are over-pessimistic and risk seeking if they are over-optimistic at times. Shortcuts can be following trusted partners or listening to the majority while making a decision.
- **Perfect knowledge:** Under traditional finance, investors are equipped with the perfect knowledge and unlimited data. They can plan and make mathematical calculations based on all available options to arrive at the most optimal choice and maximise their own utility. This essentially means that all market participants are absolute experts in the field of financial investing. On the other hand, behavioural finance recognises the imperfection of brain capacity, different intellectual levels amongst folks and the involvement of non financial background people in the markets. It became a normality for everyone to simply make a mistake when they make their own judgement.

- The efficiency/inefficiency of market: Traditional finance retains complete market efficiency and states that the price of each asset reflects its true intrinsic value. In opposition, behavioural finance argues there is presence of market inefficiency in terms of price speculations and those can be caused by human related issues such as cognitive errors, framing or social influences.
- Price prediction: Traditional finance follows the EMH which is defined by the random walk theory. Tomorrow's asset price is independent from the price from yesterday. However, behavioural finance detects patterns in investors' behaviours where they attempt to forecast direction in prices or estimate future value of that asset.

2.4.3.2. ASPECTS UNDER HEURISTICS

Heuristics can be understood as a mental shortcut in a complex decision-making process based on previous experience rather than considering the bigger picture (Muoni, 2012). People tend to use the first and foremost available information that can deliver a simple, easy and efficient, but not necessarily optimal solution to their problem (Baron and Szymanska, 2010). This problem-solving technique can be sufficient for decision making within a given time window (Chen, 2022b; Waweru et al., 2008). People need to make decisions between alternative options everyday. Some can become very routine and without spending much time of their day, heuristics can help to make quick decisions but also efficient enough to move on to the next problem.

In finance and economics, the advantages in the use of heuristics are saving time, reducing costs as well as improving productivity in generating financial analysis, economical decisions and investing activities as the number of derivative products are huge and information can be published overwhelmingly (McLaughlin et al., 2014; Lau and Redlawsk, 2001; Frankovic and Budinska, 2000). The stock market is an example of a fast paced environment where investors need to make their choice to buy or sell quickly, otherwise they might miss some available opportunities to lock in the best

price. Nonetheless, heuristics can critically damage one's investment performance and decisions because of poorly made judgements (Kleinmuntz, 1985). Time and data constraints can make decision makers arrive at an inaccurate and imprecise solution to their problem (Bobadilla-Suarez and Love, 2017). Furthermore, when heuristic is applied inappropriately, it can be associated with massive errors, hence, massive losses (Hirshleifer, 2008).

It can be said that it is impossible to completely exclude heuristics in economic decision making because sometimes time as well as cost saving can outweigh the drawbacks of heuristics. The point is that investors should learn how to live with heuristics and do not misapply the technique. They should also be aware of the associated risks when the solutions using heuristics turn out to be wrong. In order to systematically manage the risks and avoid substantial losses, behaviourists have introduced different types of biases connected with heuristics. However, this paper will focus on the most important, yet most dangerous, four heuristic biases which are overconfidence, availability, and anchoring and adjustment.

OVERCONFIDENCE

When an investor is considered to have overconfidence bias, it can be understood that he or she has the tendency to believe or misjudge his or her own skills, talent and intellectual mind to be superior to others (Weinberg, 2009). Investors who suffer under this bias often find themselves to have a gifted ability or access to information that can help them predict future market movements. In most cases, this belief introduced an illogical faith amongst investors of being smarter and better than anybody else. An interesting survey conducted by Montier (2006) with the participation of over 300 active fund managers proposed the following findings: 74% of surveyed fund managers believed they are above average; the remaining 26% believed to be just about average. These results further suggest 0% of the participants thought they were below average which can be considered to be unrealistic.

Pompian (2006) proposes the existence of overconfidence bias and its effect on investors' trading performance and outcome as follows: (1) Excessive trading based on the belief that they are superior to others in terms of talent and intellectual level, (2) underestimate the inherent risks, (3) overestimate their ability to evaluate an asset/security and (4) possibility of under-diversified portfolios.

It was found that men are generally more confident than women, especially when it comes to finance (Prince, 1993). This leads to more aggressive and excessive trading for men and they experienced more losses compared to women (Barber and Odean, 2001). The reason behind this is that overconfident investors believe that they have a gifted talent and superior intellectual level. Hence, they tend to increase their trading frequency and volumes in order to get more exposure to higher returns and underestimate the associated risks (Kyle and Wang, 1997; Odean, 1998; Graham et al., 2005; Grinblatt and Keloharju, 2009; Statman et al., 2003; Glaser and Weber, 2003). As a result, the surge in trading activities as well as volatility can lead to reduced or, in some cases, negative earnings (Gervais and Odean, 2001). Kirchler and Maciejovsky (2002) detected that investors with high levels of confidence tend to trade more frequently and experience much lower profits and sometimes buy stocks that have negative earnings. Further evidence on poor investment decisions can be found in the research of Biais et al. (2002) as overconfident investors tend to be associated with investing in companies who offer no benefits at all.

Benos (1998) suggests that overconfident investors regularly overestimate the accuracy of information received and their ability to assess an asset's valuation as they think they are more capable and better in information evaluation than others. Similarly, Malmendier and Tate (2005) conducted research on overconfident CEOs and their corporate investments. The results suggest the investments' expected cash flows were over-magnified by participants exposed to high levels of overconfidence and the returns on those investments are found to be lower than other CEOs who showed less level of overconfidence. Park et al. (2013) adds that overconfident investors are often prone to

confirmation bias, which is the tendency to gather information only in favour with one's existing belief. Both biases can make the investors themselves become too optimistic in terms of expectations in their choice of investment and generate lower returns compared to those who suffer from low levels of confidence.

Regarding the effect of overconfidence bias towards portfolio diversification, previous researchers have also provided evidence representing the influence. Broekema and Kramer (2021) studied the relationship between Dutch investors' overconfidence and their losses from lack of diversification portfolios; they found that overconfident investors suffer much higher losses from under-diversified portfolios since they underestimate the stock returns' variances, misestimate their skills to select the best stocks and exaggerate their knowledge to the point where they withdraw from advice from professionals. This is in line with Von Gaudecker (2015), Gentile et al. (2016) and Kramer and Liao (2016) who also suggest overconfident investors are less reliant on financial experts' assistance.

Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) conducted a study on behavioural factors and retail investors in the stock market but within the Colombo Stock Exchange in Sri Lanka. Cross-sectional and questionnaire designs are employed using the stratified sampling method. The multiple regression results suggest overconfidence to have a negative impact on investors' performance.

However, several researchers have reported that overconfidence bias can lead to successful investment performance. Abdin, Qureshi, Iqbal and Sultana (2022) examined different aspects of overconfidence such as self-attribution, optimism and illusion of control and their effects on investment performance within the stock market. The researchers used risk propensity as the mediator and found overconfidence to have a positive relation with investment performance. The study further highlights that overconfidence can be seen clearer by measuring investment satisfactions, instead of by objective rate of returns. This is also supported by Riaz and Iqbal (2015) whose findings

show that overconfidence has a statistically positive impact on investment performance within the Karachi Stock Exchange. Further consistency of this research finding lies within Nareswari et al. (2021) and Rehan and Umer (2017).

AVAILABILITY

As a part of the heuristics branch, availability bias is understood as the tendency to use the immediate information or examples from recent experience to make a decision, although it may not fully represent the problem that is existing (Kahneman and Tversky, 1974). The information one can easily recall normally is something that comes across quite frequently or very likely to happen on a timely basis. Although all relevant information is available for a decision maker to use and be the most rational, the human brain may not be fully capable of remembering everything or thoroughly exploring all potential solutions to the situation.

In financial markets, investors can suffer from availability bias and irrationally expect similar market phenomenon to repeat again rather than examining its objective probability. The consequence of this can cause investors to be overly involved in either bear or bull markets. The high expectation of prices to keep falling in a bear market and climbing in a bull market without constructing a fundamental analysis can significantly damage investing profits and strongly harm investors' trading performance and outcome (Read and Grushka, 2011). Khan et al. (2017) examined the Malaysian and Pakistan stock markets by both quantitative and qualitative approach and further found that there is a strong correlation between the presence of availability heuristics and investors' buying decisions. However, Khan (2015) and Ikram (2016) suggested availability heuristics can boost the decision making process of investors.

ANCHORING AND ADJUSTMENT

Another type of bias under heuristics theory is anchoring and adjustment. In the work of Kahneman and Tversky (1974), they described it as a cognitive bias where people make the final decision with their computation based on an initial value or a reference point. The principle under this bias is that people essentially concentrate on a piece of information which they think is reliable; in other words, they anchor at the value initially introduced by the piece of information. Hence, incorrect adjustments from the referenced value are constructed and those lead to wrongly made decisions. Stewart et al. (2014) explained this effect evolves from the fact that the human brain can remember information that comes first better than later. As a result, people unconsciously accredit the first available information with foremost importance in their head than any information being delivered afterwards.

Previous researches have evidently shown there is a correlation between anchoring and adjustment bias and investment decisions. By studying the Nairobi Stock Exchange, Waweru et al. (2008) provided results on the negative impact of anchoring and adjustment bias on institutional investors' trading decisions. Shah et al. (2018) further showed similar illustration of data between individual investors being active in the Pakistan Stock exchange and the anchoring bias.

Nonetheless, several studies argue that anchoring and adjustment bias can positively influence investment performance. Aziz and Khan (2016) found there is a significantly positive correlation between individual investors' trading performance and the anchoring bias. Similar results are introduced in the work of Ranjbar et al. (2014), Ishfaq and Anjum (2015), Menike et al. (2015), Obara (2015) and Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014).

However, there are two papers documenting an insignificant effect of anchoring bias on investors' performance. Babajide and Adetiloye (2012) used a primary data technique to look into how behavioural biases affected the performance of the security market in Nigeria. In order to assess a survey of 300 randomly chosen investors in the security

market, the paper used a questionnaire as an instrument and the correlation with Pearson Product Moment Coefficient approach. According to the regression results, there is no discernible effect of anchoring bias on investment performance, and the null hypothesis should remain in place. Tin and Hii (2020) sought to investigate the link between investing performance on debt securities in Johor, Malaysia, and the heuristic behaviour aspects. The result showed a similar finding to Babajide and Adetiloye (2012).

2.4.3.3. ASPECTS UNDER PROSPECT THEORY

Prospect theory was first submitted to the public in 1979 by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky which explains a model of making decisions under risks and uncertainty (Barberis, 2013). This invention was later awarded the Nobel Prize in 2002 (Barberis, 2013). The paper proposed a critical analysis on how people are prone to certain prospects to any risky ones in a winning situation; vice versa, they tend to be risk seeking if they are facing a potential loss in their decision (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). An example is illustrated on winning and losing scenarios as follows:

A: 50% of winning \$1,000 and 50% of winning nothing.

B: 100% of winning \$500.

And

C: 50% of losing \$1,000 and 50% of losing nothing.

D: 100% of losing \$500.

When facing a winning situation, most asked people prefer to proceed with option B and are able to receive \$500 without any effort. However, when facing a losing situation, people tend to be risk seeking and choose option C instead of option D. In terms of expected value, all options represent an absolute value of \$500. In other words, a rational person would find no difference between each choice, hence, there is no appropriate rational explanation for the selection made in two different scenarios. As a result, Kahneman and Tversky (1979) proposed an answer to the problem - the prospect theory. According to the theory, investors perceive the value of gain and losses differently which results in the tendency to misestimate the probability associated with each framing scenario (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). In the gain frame, they become risk averse and underestimate their chance of winning \$1,000, thus, they choose to receive \$500 for sure instead. On the other hand, they become risk seeking and overestimate their chance of losing nothing that makes them retain the gambling mindset. Behavioural biases related to prospect theory to be discussed are loss aversion, regret aversion and mental accounting.

LOSS AVERSION

Loss aversion was identified as a dominant behavioural bias under prospect theory by Kahneman and Tversky (1979). This bias suggests that investors have the tendency to minimise losses at all cost, regardless of the associated probability and the value of potential loss. Accordingly, the suffering and negative emotion is perceived to be signified more when a person faces losses than when perceiving gains. For instance, the loss of satisfaction when an investor loses \$1,000 might be much greater than the gain of satisfaction when he or she wins \$1,000. For this reason, loss aversion can lead to bad as well as costly executions in trading and investing. Investors who suffer from loss aversion bias can be patient, able to tolerate the pain of having a negative profit and loss position with the hope of a price rebound while it is still open. However, if a sign of continuing trend can be detected from an earlier stage, they could have minimised the losses by executing their position prior or avoided the potential of complete liquidity.

The action of holding on losses and locking in the collaterals for far too long can also lead to missing out on other investing opportunities.

Bouteska and Regaieg (2018) studied the impact of loss aversion bias on nearly 7,000 companies from the United States and confirmed that there is a negative relationship between the bias and the companies' performance within the stock market. Evidence was shown when there is a sign of pessimism indicating loss aversion amongst investors, the overall performance of these companies were badly influenced which led to stock prices to go down. Lee and Veld-Merkoulova (2016) assessed the loss aversion bias within the Dutch stock investors by surveying approximately 2,000 observations. Similar results are drawn where loss aversion has a negative and significant correlation with the respondents' equity investments.

Yiwen (2021) similarly conducted research on the influence of loss aversion but within the China stock market by using percentage of variation in transaction volume to measure the loss aversion bias. The results implies there is a clear negative effect from loss aversion bias and led to the fall in performance amongst the included sample. In the Rwanda stock market, Mahina, Muturi and Memba (2017) established a researching survey including evaluating statements to detect loss aversion bias in the market. The findings further confirmed that there is a significant impact of loss aversion on the investment decisions.

However, Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), which was mentioned previously in the overconfidence section, found that there is no significant impact of loss aversion on investors' performance. This is in line with Sugathadasa (2018).

REGRET AVERSION

Regret aversion is another behavioural bias that falls under prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). It was explained as a concept where people can sometimes be reluctant to make a decision because of the fear of making a wrongful decision if they do (Chen et al., 2018). Under uncertainty, it can be very difficult to establish a great valuation upon potential outcomes. As they do not want to suffer from any regret from their own actions, they prefer to not make any decision so that they can protect themselves emotionally and materially. The pain of losses was previously explained to be much more powerful than the pleasure of gain, hence, people can be highly sensitive when facing losses. They understand the burden of emotions such as regret, unhappiness and disappointment if they make a wrong move can be strongly tough for them to deal with. Therefore, they attempt to avoid going through such pain by withdrawing themselves from repeating the same action. By means of protecting themselves materially, the author refers to anything else that can be tangible or intangible and has the potential of being affected by making a decision. That can be monetary belongings or physical possessions such as money savings, investments or estate assets. In most of the financial markets' cases, investors tend to avoid decisions which can lead to potential regret and investment losses in the future (Sattar et al., 2020). Regret aversion might seem to be similar to loss aversion, nonetheless, there is one major difference to distinguish the two behavioural biases. Investors can be subject to both biases but loss aversion bias alone can still encourage investors to make a decision even though it might not necessarily be right whereas regret aversion alone does not promote the urge to make a decision (Thaler, 1985).

Although it is understood that regret aversion might encourage investors to be more risk averse, they can also be risk taking if they are prone to this bias. Shiller (2003) found the presence of regret aversion where investors tend to take on a massive amount of risk in exchange of avoiding any losses. As a result, they tend to hold on to losing stocks (Shiller, 2003). In case of short sellers, being subjected to regret aversion can cost them a lot of money by holding onto stocks that continually experience an upward trend in price (Shiller, 2003).

Previous researchers have provided evidence on how regret aversion can affect investment decisions. Isidore and Christie (2019) assessed how different behavioural biases, including regret aversion, can affect annual income of stock investors in India and suggested that low annual income investors are more likely to be risk averse and have the tendency to sell stocks too early. Wangzhou et al. (2021) studied the influence of regret aversion within the real estate sector in developing countries. They found that regret aversion can cause a significant negative impact directly on investment decisions. Furthermore, when taking into account risk perception and financial literacy, the result provides a similar effect which leads to investors' irrationality. This is in line with earlier studies including Mellers (2000) and Zeelenberg and Pieters (2004).

Again, Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) which studied the influence of behavioural factors on Sri Lankan stock investors found no significant effect of regret aversion on investors' performance. This is also supported by Sugathadasa (2018).

MENTAL ACCOUNTING

The third behavioural bias based on prospect theory is mental accounting. It was described as a set of cognitive biases including assessing, categorising and monitoring financial activities by individuals (Thaler, 1999). They tend to separate their money into different "pots" and assign distinguished functions to each pot. Each individual can have different criteria for their own fund. When applied appropriately, mental accounting can help to achieve one's financial goals, allow diversification within investing and reduce the risk of losing money. However, inappropriate pot assignment can lead to one's irrational spending and wrongful holding. The commitment to consider different types of money possession can also lead to inflexibility and inability for optimisation where a person can find it difficult to adjust their fund due to change of circumstances. In investing, an investor might assign a specific amount of money to winning positions and a complete separate pot for losing positions (Isidore and Christie, 2019). The problem arises when the investor is considering closing a position, he or she tends to sell the

winners instead of selling the losers. This is intertwining with the regret aversion bias where the pain of losing money is too much to be dealt with. Instead, the investor must sell the winners and gain short term positive liquidation, instead of suffering with emotions from a loss.

Unlike loss aversion and regret aversion, previous studies have shown rather a positive impact of mental accounting to investment decisions. Rashwan and Shaqfa (2021) assessed the influence of mental accounting on financial decisions of 136 Palestinian investors. The findings indicate mental accounting bias helps the Palestinian investors to make better investment decisions. It plays an important role among investors in expanding their knowledge, skills and experience as well as reducing errors and better estimating investments' returns and associated risks. Similarly, Obademi and Ogunlusi (2019) found there is an existence of mental accounting bias within stock market investors and a positive relationship between mental accounting bias and the decisions of financial investors. Mascarenas and Yan (2017) further explained each investor's investment portfolio shall be determined by the risk appetite of that individual and mental accounting can support as a tool to correctly monitor financial activities and to meet the satisfaction and preference of his or her.

2.4.3.4. HERDING

The last but not least branch within behavioural economics is herding and it can be said to be one of the most researched areas for financial and investing decisions. Herding bias refers to the tendency in people to follow others' opinions rather than conducting their own (Baddeley, 2010). In other words, it is a shortcut in making a decision with the hope to gain some benefits by taking advantage of a trend. Herding behaviour can be seen in different aspects of life from purchasing a piece of fashion based on current trends, taking COVID vaccines with encouragement from the government or friends and family, to investing in companies whose productions support the need to reduce climate change.

The reason for herding to arise in a situation can be justified by there is some presence of uncertainty, lacking relevant skills and knowledge as well as facing incomplete information (Fernandez et al., 2011). In financial markets, investors tend to listen to more financial experts because they believe the experts should have a better understanding of the current situation and information to pick the right investing securities (Chen et al., 2020; DeBont and Forbes, 1999). Investors frequently disregard or reject their initial analysis and adhere to prior price trends, according to research by Avery and Zemsky (1998). As a result, herding behaviour can lead to serious irrationality in investment decision performance (Chiang et al., 2013; Pompian, 2012). Apart from an individual's decision, herding can further affect the efficiency of a market (Arisanti and Oktavendi, 2020).

In the context of market bubbles that cannot be explained by the EMH, herding can act as the answer for price speculation. One of the real life examples can be referred to the dotcom bubbles. As previously discussed, the hyper rise of the internet and how an enormous amount of companies were increasingly built to catch that trend can be explained by herding behaviour. The bubble later burst which led to the rapid fall of many investors and the dotcom companies.

On another note, there is evidence of herding that can have a positive impact on financial investors. According to Bikhchandani and Sharma (2000), there are two types of herding: "spurious" herding, in which investors make judgements based on comparable sets of fundamental data, and "intentional" herding, in which investors actively seek to imitate other investors' actions. The former could result in a successful outcome, whilst the latter could not. Intentional herding may also lead to fragile markets, excess volatility and systemic risk.

Scharfstein and Stein (1990) illustrated managers may copy each other's behaviour due to reputational concerns and imperfect information in the labour markets as well as a

desire to share the responsibility when things go wrong. The authors also suggest a learning model in the labour market which can predict a manager's aptitude based on the investment choices made by others. As a result, the worry for their reputation may lead to a rational (but socially inefficient) herd where one discards private knowledge and adheres to the judgements of other managers.

Herd behaviour could further benefit investors if they only engage with the market for a short period of time. Froot et al. (1992) found when speculators have limited time horizons, herd behaviour can aid to reveal what others know by herding on the same piece of information. Their approach allows for some speculators to have brief time frames for trading, which suggests that they might not allocate research funds in the most efficient manner. This can create an informational deficiency where investors have the tendency to focus on one source rather than using a variety of information sources. It can be advantageous to obtain this information at an early stage because then it will be shared in the market as more and more speculators obtain it. The authors refer to this as “positive informational spillovers”.

Sabir et al. (2019) examined the relationship between illusions of control, self-attribution, herding behaviour, and information availability on investor's decision making. This study followed a survey questionnaire approach to collect data from 300 respondents. The authors concluded that illusion of control and self-attribution favour investor's herding while greater information availability may lead to more logical, reasoned, and rational behaviour, discouraging herding. Another study by Abreu and Mendes (2012) examined the impact of information available on the trading behaviour of investors. The data for this study were collected through the questionnaire, and the results showed that investors with more information have a higher tendency to trade more frequently.

Similar to this, a study by Tauni et al. (2015) found a link between Chinese investors' trading frequency and the availability of information. To make cautious, wise, and

logical investing decisions, investors devote a lot of time to locating, gathering, and analysing information. According to literature by Prechter (2010), Fernández et al. (2011), Chiang et al. (2013), and Sabir et al. (2018), large investors have less of a tendency to herd than small investors because the former may use a variety of sources to gather and analyse the information that is available, abstaining from herding, while the latter may simply mimic the large investor's investment behaviour.

Le and Doan (2011) studied the impact of behavioural factors, including herding, on individual investors' performance in the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange (HOSE). The study adopts a mixed research method and the structural equation modelling on a sample of 172 retail investors. The findings suggest herding has a statistically positive and significant impact on investors' performance. The authors explained that due to the Vietnamese stock market's immaturity, there is lack of information availability which led to the existence of herding behaviour. It is also known as a small market, hence, stock prices can be easily driven by small and wealthy entities who have the dominance over the market. This can explain the positive correlation between herding behaviour and investors' performance in HOSE. Their research findings also found that herding rises when there is more trading volume and liquidity.

Karmacharya et al. (2022) conducted their study on behavioural biases, including herding, among the Nepalese stock market. The scholars also adopted structural equation modelling, on which the data consists of 350 observations. The results suggest there is a positive relation between herding and investors' performance in Nepal. They further added that Nepalese stock investors rely heavily on other investors' advice and tend to not perform a comprehensive market analysis. This finding is further in line with Nareswari, Balqista and Negoro (2021) and Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna (2020).

However, Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) which studied the influence of behavioural factors on the Colombo Stock Exchange's retail investors and found no significant impact of herding on investors' performance.

2.5. CRYPTOCURRENCY AND BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE

2.5.1. INCENTIVE TOWARDS RETAIL INVESTORS

From the previous discussion in sub-chapter 2.1, the adoption of blockchain technology into cryptocurrencies has been focusing on trust and the belief in a free market. It aims to cancel the need of a governmental body who has the power to control or manipulate prices of an asset. In the case of institutional investors, they also own a certain amount of power over the financial markets (Park, 2003). Although cryptocurrency is not a traditional financial market, evidence of widening engagement from institutional investors can be seen in their trading volume of cryptocurrencies. A report from Coinbase (2022) announced the total trading volume by institutional investors accounted for \$120 billion in 2020; this figure later rose to \$1,136 billion after one year. The percentage of trading volume by retail investors on Coinbase accordingly reduced from over 38% down to 32% between 2020 and 2021 (Coinbase, 2022). It can be said that institutional investors are slowly conquering and gaining more power in the cryptocurrency market. The example on meme stocks in the earlier chapter represents evidence on activist investors to have stood up and fought back institutional investors who have massive amounts of control over the stock market and close relationship with a governmental entity. If cryptocurrency is said to be the money of the poor and the people demanding a free market, researchers should focus more on retail investors and recommend findings that serve the purpose of helping them make better investment decisions. This is the main rationale for this paper and behavioural finance is going to be used as a tool to portrait the current picture of crypto retail investors' behaviours and understand where the mistakes might be situated.

2.5.2. BEHAVIOURAL FINANCE REPORTS ON THE CRYPTO MARKET

Relatively considerable research interest in the field of behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market has been shown over the recent years. However, the opportunity to expand further research in investors' behaviours remains largely open

due to most studies attempting to find the relationship between the price fluctuations in the cryptocurrency market and behavioural biases, not by directly studying investor's behaviours, their trading performance and investment decisions. Hidajat (2018) conducted an overall review on literature on the behavioural perspective within the cryptocurrency market during different stages of a bubble. The researcher agrees there has been a low amount of papers that specifically study each and every psychological biases and crypto investors' investment decisions. Among those, herding seems to gain the most attention compared to other behavioural biases.

Kim, Hanna and Lee (2021) examined the relationship between subjective as well as objective financial literacy amongst investors and their investments in cryptocurrency. The authors also chose to look deeper into the effect of overconfidence bias and found that overconfidence has a positive significant impact on the tendency to invest in cryptocurrency. Furthermore, Syarkani and Tristante (2022) examined a number of predictors, including overconfidence, and their impacts on crypto investors' decisions. Their results suggest overconfidence has a positive relationship with the decisions made by crypto investors. To conclude, after assessing the literatures above, the author introduces the first hypothesis:

H1: Overconfidence has a significant positive impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Xi, O'Brien and Irannezhad (2019) applied the concept of prospect theory to examine its impact on investors' choice of different Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs). The sample of the study was concentrated on Chinese and Australian cryptocurrency enthusiasts and investors. The findings showed there is a certain level of unwillingness to be involved in the cryptocurrency market from Australian investors due to the market crash in 2017. Previous experience with substantial losses and uncertainty have made them risk averse and less confident to believe in cryptocurrency, resulting in a switch to a more traditional market. The research also addressed further on the irrationality amongst investors and determined that it is a big problem in the cryptocurrency market. Biases such as overconfidence, loss aversion, disposition effect and herding have shown their

existence in the surveyed sample which are concluded to be the reason for poor investment decisions and ultimately the market inefficiency. According to these papers, the second hypothesis can be constructed:

H2: Loss aversion has a significant negative impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Popova (2020) proposed that the Monte Carlo simulation and stochastic optimisation approach can be used to build an optimisation portfolio across eleven different asset classes which includes Bitcoin and Ether. The results indicate that an optimal one can be achieved when there is a considerable portion assigned to the two cryptocurrencies. This also suggests that in any case due to uncertainty, investors should have an appetite as a risk-seeker. Due to high volatility of Bitcoin and Ether alone, investors must feel comfortable in allocating the highest amount of money to the crypto asset class. Their findings show that one of the main drivers behind great allocations in cryptos appears to be loss aversion. Although the paper does not specify or assess further the impact of loss aversion, more research on that is essentially in need. However, according to the literature on the stock markets, regret aversion may predominantly lead to a loss for investment performance. Hence, the third hypothesis is introduced as follows:

H3: Regret aversion has a significant negative impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Gurdgiev and O'Loughlin (2020) studied the reaction and sentiment of investors in the cryptocurrency market due to uncertainty and fear. They pointed out that there is a tendency where people invest in Bitcoin or cryptocurrencies in general as a safe haven and to hedge against the stock market during uncertain times. While it might be subjective to consider cryptocurrency as a promising safe haven, the findings show that there is evidence of herding bias and anchoring effect on the buy and sell positions of investors. Based on this recommendation, the study believes it is crucial to consider these effects as factors in order to measure or evaluate the price of a crypto asset.

Jia, Simkins, Xu and Zhang (2022) investigated the association between the anchoring and adjustment bias and future crypto investment returns. By using portfolio-level analysis and cross-sectional regressions, the researchers found that the anchoring and adjustment effect supports and accelerate returns on crypto investments. Based on evidences of the anchoring and adjustment effect and existence within the cryptocurrency markets, the author proposes the fourth hypothesis:

H4: Anchoring and adjustment has a significant positive impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Herding effect has been found to exist in the cryptocurrency market in Poyser (2018), Vidal-Tomás, Ibáñez, & Farinós (2018), King and Koutmos (2021), Omane-Adjepong, Alagidede, Lyimo and Tweneboah (2021).

Ajaz and Kumar (2018) examined the herding effect on the daily returns of six different cryptocurrencies as well as the market index CCI130. The authors found that there is evidence of herding in both bullish and bearish markets. Investors tend to overreact and follow the majority when there is a massive price fluctuation. However, there is no presence of herding in two different scenarios of low and high market volatility. In addition, Bouri, Gupta and Roubaud (2018) conducted their research on the effect of herding by two different analysis models: static and rolling window. The results found that there is no significance in herding effect, however, the nonlinearities in the data made the model not acceptable for the results. Alternatively, the rolling window model was used and discovered an existing impact of herding in the cryptocurrency market. The research also found the tendency of increasing herding effect as investors face higher levels of uncertainty.

Boxer and Thompson (2020) studied a sample of 130 active crypto investors for what factors of herding would affect cryptocurrency purchasing attitudes. Their findings demonstrate that herding has a positively significant influence on crypto investors contributed by perceived behavioural control, social norms and propensity to imitate

others. Accordingly, this previous finding would suggest an expectation on the relation of herding bias on crypto investment performance which leads to the formation of the fifth hypothesis:

H5: Herding has a significant positive impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Ciaian, Rajcaniova and Kancs (2015) attempts to understand the price formation of Bitcoin by analysing the mechanism of demand and supply in the market as well as the attractiveness amongst investors in both short and long term. The authors found that new information on Bitcoin can drive prices higher in the short term. Crypto enthusiasts and investors are extremely active on social media and online forums such as Twitter, Discord, Telegram and Reddit can be under an enormous impact with the news and the public attention on Bitcoin prices. This kind of attention is suggested to constantly drive up the price as people are prone to availability bias. They tend to react immediately to a change in price whenever they look into what is on the news or within the discussion between the crypto communities. This suggests that availability bias may produce some short-term gains for crypto investors, however, it is problematical to predict if it has a positive impact on performance under a long-term perspective. Since there is no straightforward direction to predict the relation of availability bias with crypto investment performance, the sixth hypothesis will be using the short term expectation of availability bias on crypto investors' performance:

H6: Availability has a significant positive impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

Al-mansour (2020) studied over 100 Arabic investors with the perspective of behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market by the quantitative method. The findings show that Arabic investors tend to rely on previous experience before making the next investing move and they believe that they are sufficient enough in terms of knowledge and trading skills to make a decision. This implies the sample's investment decisions in the cryptocurrency market are evidently under the influence of heuristic

biases. In terms of prospect theory, the study's findings suggest that investors become more risk-seeking and buy more crypto securities as a result of capital gain from a previous trade. Similarly, when investors encounter losses, they have the tendency to become risk averse and withdraw from future investments. This also indicates that there is presence of biases associated with prospect theory, including mental accounting, amongst the surveyed investors. The results further indicate there is a significant and positive impact between prospect theory and investors' investment decisions. Overall, this research proposes clear evidence of different behavioural biases on investors' decisions in the cryptocurrency market and suggests the market is inefficient. Since mental accounting was not assessed in Al-mansour (2020) as a separate independent variable, this paper aims to fill the gap by examining the direct relationship of mental accounting to crypto investors' performance. Following the suggestion from this paper, the seventh hypothesis is presented as below:

H7: Mental accounting has a significant positive impact on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

To conclude, one study could only be found to have used a survey to study different aspects of behavioural finance and their effects on investment performance within the cryptocurrency market. However, Arabic investors were exclusively and solely included in the researching process. More evidence of multiple behaviour effects on the price of cryptocurrencies can be seen in listed papers above. No studies were found to link the relationship between investment decisions as well as trading performance and behavioural biases amongst retail crypto investors. In addition, this paper earlier proposed two biggest motives that can divide retail investors into two groups: people that believe in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth and people that only seek to expand their income or increase their wealth. The author has decided to develop the eighth hypothesis as below as she believes an investor with a strong interest in the cryptocurrency markets and a belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth would be more inclined to conduct more research and analysis on the crypto assets. Hence, that are more likely to assist the investors themselves to perform better.

H8: Motivational factors have a significant positive effect on investment decision outcomes in the cryptocurrency market.

2.5.3. LITERATURE GAPS

Under the theory underpinned in this thesis, which is behavioural finance theory, there have remarkably lack of research using the assumptions of this theory on the cryptocurrency markets. Behavioural finance can be viewed as a broad context ranging from various heuristics concepts to sub-elements within prospect theory. By studying these aspects comprehensively in the context of cryptocurrency market, it will produce an immense amount of new advanced knowledge and intuitiveness not only for crypto investors, but also for the academic field. In addition, quantitative approach was found to be predominately used in identifying the relationships between different behavioural biases and investment outcomes.

Literature review from this paper may further suggest the necessary to assess different types of quantitative data analysis, such as cross-sectional and time-series to examine the impact levels of each behavioural bias to crypto investors' performance. Furthermore, because of the largely use of the quantitative approach within this context, this calls for applications of other research methodologies within the field to deeply understand and explain the reasons behind these relations.

Finally, the author identifies another research gap which more studies are needed to review existing policy and regulation landscape of the cryptocurrency markets as well as authority's guidelines to protect crypto investors. The expected outcomes could potentially identify crucial fragmentation, policy implication difficulties and essential interventions. Results that imply a negative relation may indicate more concentration from the authority to invest more into mitigating psychological factors and impose restrictions on more vulnerable investors. On the other hand, results with a positive impact may encourage innovations which utilise the positive effect to benefit consumers.

In respect of this research paper, the author attempts to fill the gaps which include challenging the seven key behavioural finance concepts in the context of cryptocurrency markets to as one of the few direct studies linking with retail investment outcomes, as well as to hopefully provide some policy and regulatory implications within the cryptocurrency markets. The research also expects to shed more light on the motivational aspect regarding investors who strongly believe in the fundamental values of crypto assets.

2.6. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework is a significantly vital component of a research paper where the author(s) attempts to illustrate the core studying concept and assumptions through visualisation (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2018; Maxwell, 2012). This visualisation is expressed in the form of an integration map, used to highlight the key relationships between each researched variable (Rallis, 2018). From the researcher's point of view, it helps to construct and examine their own social beliefs more critically to achieve more intellectual goals (Maxwell, 2012). In addition, the role of conceptual framework is to help and guide researchers throughout the whole research process with applicable methodology choices (Ravitch and Carl, 2019).

According to the literature review of this study, overconfidence, anchoring and adjustment, availability, loss aversion, regret aversion, mental accounting and herding are the the seven behavioural biases to have been found to evidently have some impacts on investment decisions of individual investors. Consequently, seven hypotheses on these behavioural finance biases are constructed to explore more on their relationships with the outcomes for cryptocurrency retail investors. Although they are previously grouped and categorised into heuristics, prospect theory and herding, the author decides to raise individual hypotheses for each bias to study in a more detailed way about each of them. As a result, a conceptual framework in the form of flowchart is developed in the below diagram.

This conceptual framework was originally adopted from the research of Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Karmacharya, Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022). Later studies are found to also adopt this conceptual framework namely Rehan and Umer (2017), Sugathedasa (2018), Audu and Abubakar (2019), Sukamulja, Meilita and Senoputri (2019), Hamidon and Kehelwatatenna (2020) and Nareswari, Balqista and Negoro (2021) with slightly modification where the hypotheses were linked directly between the biases and investment performance. Similarly, the author follows the direct hypothesis testing and adds motivational factors of cryptocurrency investors as the extra independent variable to investment decision outcomes. This is also the eighth and last hypothesis for this study.

CHAPTER 3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) proposed a spectrum of five different research philosophies for business and management researchers which are positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism and pragmatism. Positivism and interpretivism are frequently made as choices and discussed as the two extremes within research philosophies (Bryman and Bell, 2008; Travers, 2001). For each level of research philosophy, assumptions on the branch of ontology, epistemology and axiology are justified. The ontology branch is subject to as a researcher's perception of realities which he or she shall encounter during the research process, while epistemology are the assumptions on how human knowledge are shaped and axiology is referred to the assumptions on his or her values that may have the influence on what is being studied (Saunders et al., 2019, p. 130). This chapter will first consider the research philosophy applying to this thesis, alongside associated assumptions on ontology, epistemology and axiology branches. The discussion will then be followed by the relevant research approach and strategies as well as the methodology on how data is collected and analysed. By adopting the "research onion" diagram introduced by Saunders et al. 2019 on research methods in business and management, a summary on this chapter can be viewed as below:

3.2. RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Research philosophy is understood as one's system of belief and own perception on knowledge creation and development (Zukauska, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitiene, 2018). The everyday advancement in science constantly influences the way of thinking and reasoning in human beings which consists of three elements: belief, knowledge and value of the world (Goldman, 1999). Researchers often set out questions along the lines of these elements to form a systematic approach and find answers in the way that is philosophically reasonable to them; that is also to understand their own belief of the universe and attempt to discover their own research philosophy (Kenaphoom, 2017). During this process, certain philosophical assumptions can be constructed either from experience or an authoritative source and operate as the foundation while conducting research (Kenaphoom, 2017). The purpose of it is to determine how research questions as well as collected data will be analysed and interpreted and eventually produce new knowledge (Crotty, 1998).

Research philosophies can be established by determining different sets of ontological, epistemological and axiological assumptions (Zukauska, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitiene, 2018). In the field of business and management studies, Saunders et al. (2019) provided a diagram that highlights five main research philosophies and their associated branches of ontology, epistemology and axiology as well as the typically linking research method.

	Ontology	Epistemology	Axiology	Typical method
Positivism	Real, external, independent One true reality (universalism) Granular (things) Ordered	Scientific method Observable and measurable facts Lawlike generalisations Numbers Causal explanation and prediction as contribution	Value-free research Researcher is detached, neutral and independent of what is researched Researcher maintains objective stance	Typically deductive, highly structured, large samples, measurement, typically quantitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be analysed
Critical realism	Stratified/layered (the empirical, the actual and the real) External, independent Intransient Objective structures Causal mechanisms	Epistemological relativism Knowledge historically situated and transient Facts are social constructions Historical causal explanation as contribution	Value-laden research Researcher acknowledges bias by world views, cultural experience and upbringing Researcher tries to minimise bias and errors Researcher is as objective as possible	Retroductive, in-depth historically situated analysis of pre-existing structures and emerging agency Range of methods and data types to fit subject matter
Interpretivism	Complex and rich	Theories and concepts too	Value-bound research	Typically inductive, small samples,

	<p>Socially constructed through culture and language</p> <p>Multiple meanings, interpretations, realities</p> <p>Flux of processes, experiences, practices</p>	<p>simplistic</p> <p>Focus on narratives, stories, perceptions and interpretations</p> <p>New understanding and worldviews as contribution</p>	<p>Researchers are part of what is researched, subjective</p> <p>Researcher interpretations key to contribution</p> <p>Researcher reflexive</p>	<p>in-depth investigations, qualitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be interpreted</p>
Postmodernism	<p>Nominal</p> <p>Complex, rich</p> <p>Socially constructed through power relations</p> <p>Some meanings, interpretations, realities are dominated and silenced by others</p> <p>Flux of processes, experiences, practices</p>	<p>What counts as 'truth' and 'knowledge' is decided by dominant ideologies</p> <p>Focus on absences, silences and oppressed/repressed meanings, interpretations and voices</p> <p>Exposure of power relations and challenge of dominant views as contribution</p>	<p>Value-constituted research</p> <p>Researcher and research embedded in power relations</p> <p>Some research narratives are repressed and silenced at the expense of others</p> <p>Researcher radically reflexive</p>	<p>Typically deconstructive - reading texts and realities against themselves</p> <p>In-depth investigations of anomalies, silences and absences</p> <p>Range of data types, typically qualitative methods of analysis</p>
Pragmatism	<p>Complex, rich, external</p> <p>'Reality' is the practical consequences of ideas</p> <p>Flux of processes, experiences</p>	<p>Practical meaning of knowledge in specific contexts</p> <p>'True' theories and knowledge are those that enable successful action</p> <p>Focus on</p>	<p>Value-driven research</p> <p>Research initiated and sustained by researcher's doubts and beliefs</p> <p>Researcher</p>	<p>Following research problems and research question</p> <p>Range of methods: mixed, multiple,</p>

	and practices	problems, practices and relevance Problem solving and informed future practice as contribution	reflexive	qualitative, quantitative, action research Emphasis on practical solutions and outcomes
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Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019)

3.3. POSITIVISM

This research has chosen to adopt Positivism as research philosophy. The ontology assumptions under positivism suggest there is only one true objective reality and it is independent from people as social factors and researcher's own perspective (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). Unlike interpretivism which is the other-end extreme in the research philosophy spectrum and assumes there are many existing realities, positivist researchers believe there is only one way of interpreting human society and that is through scientific knowledge (Crotty, 1998). Under the positivism approach, the behaviours and actions of each and every social actor are looked at through the society as whole (Saunders et al., 2019). Accordingly, positivists take the stand of providing law-like generalisations and trend predictions through the majority (Saunders et al., 2019). This research philosophy tends to utilise the use of a highly structured and straightforward quantifiable research approach since it follows the view of a measurable reality (Churchill, 1996). Future studies on similar scenarios can later adopt the same approach to create consistency and refer to the approach as guidance (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). Furthermore, this research philosophy requires researchers to distance their personal experience and emotions from the objects that are being studied in order to create objectivity as well as logical and rational reasoning (Carson et al., 2001). Positivists should maintain a value-free mindset and avoid value judgement at all times while conducting research (Carson et al., 2001).

Research hypotheses under positivism are normally constructed based on an existing theory and tested using statistical analyses to provide empirical findings to uncover the research questions (Carson et al., 2001). Typical research methods associated with positivists are quantitative methods which can frequently be seen with highly structured questionnaires or distributed surveys in a large sample (Saunders et al., 2019). By following this way, researchers can further support the axiological assumptions under the positivism philosophy as to be value-free and promote detachment between researcher and study participants. Sufficient communication while maintaining minimal interaction is understood to be highly crucial during the data

collection phase (Wilson, 2010). The later phase of data analysis to provide quality empirical findings is also expected to be distinct and not be influenced by any feeling or personal value of the researcher (Carson et al., 2001).

In the context of this research, positivism is determined to be the philosophical foundation to understand what behavioural biases affect the investment outcome of cryptocurrency investors. Under positivism, social phenomena and human behaviours are viewed to be external to the researcher (Saunders et al., 2019). Hence, the minds of cryptocurrency investors and their cognitive biases associated with the way they make investment decisions are separated from the mind of the researcher as she does not have control over their decision-making process nor their prior investing experience. Additionally, this paper aims to study what factors have the tendency to affect the investment outcome of individual investors using the theory of behavioural finance. As positivism demands the researcher to use a generalised fundamental law (Turner, 2021), it fits the context of this groundwork where the author employs the law of behavioural finance.

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between investment outcomes and investors' behavioural biases. Guba and Lincoln (1994) suggested that positivism can be considered to be an ideal research framework in order to study the correlation between social variables. Furthermore, the influencing factors will be able to be scientifically measured together with investors' investment outcome and do not take accounts from any specific individual perspectives, thus, the concept of positivism is found to be more relevant than interpretivism.

From the epistemological point of view, this research's goal is not to interpret the meanings of the investment decisions made by cryptocurrency investors nor the essence of behavioural biases amongst them, but to generalise a principle for the whole population and provide causal relation in human behaviours. It has been emphasised that researchers who follow the positivism approach primarily focus more on studying

the causes and impacts of a social phenomena, whereas interpretivist researchers aim to gain deeper understanding and true meanings of its (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988; Neuman, 2000). In addition, this research uses a large number of observations for sampling to feasibly produce generalised findings, instead of a few which would appeal more to interpretivism.

For those reasons, positivism is found to be the most appropriate research philosophy for this study. As the typical research method with structured self-completion survey is adopted to study the behaviours of cryptocurrency investors and is digitally distributed, survey participants are separated away from the researchers which allows the research to be conducted in a highly value neutral manner. Questions employed in the questionnaire as well as research hypotheses are generated from the existing behavioural finance theory to further comply with the principle of positivism philosophy. A summary of all justifications for the positivism approach can also be viewed in the following table.

	The choice of positivism
The author	Acting as an external observer and is independent from the studied observations and remains objectively
Existing theory used	Behavioural finance with different aspects of prospect theory, heuristics and herding
Explanations	Proving causal relations and possible impacts was identified to be the major objective of this research
Research approach	A certain amount of hypotheses were constructed to test whether behavioural finance biases can influence the investment outcome of cryptocurrency investors

Analysing method	Scientifically and statistically
Required sampling numbers	A large number of observations was determined and selected

3.4. RESEARCH APPROACH

Saunders et al. (2019) and Bryman, Bell and Harley (2015) proposed the main options for research reasonings or in other words, research approach as follows:

- Deductive
- Inductive

Saunders et al. (2019) described deductive as a method of reasoning which finds the conjunction among general principles to deliver a specific conclusion to an argument. As a research approach, it starts by introducing research hypotheses based on an existing general defined theory, followed by its application to a specific phenomena in order to test the validity of those hypotheses (Wilson, 2010). Theory-driven hypotheses are formed to be certain concepts and deductive approach is used to bridge the causal relation between these concepts and a set of variables (Saunders et al., 2019). This approach is typically underpinned in positivism research as it requires a strongly structured methodology to promote consistency and reliability in researching (Saunders et al., 2019). Although deductive approach can be employed in either quantitative and qualitative research design, more dominant use is seen in quantitative research since it allows facts to be quantifiable (Saunders et al., 2019). In order to apply this approach appropriately, a sufficient sample size is necessary and should be carefully chosen in order to promote confidence in generalisations (Saunders et al., 2019).

On the other hand, Neuman (2000) stated inductive reasoning is a reasoning method which uses specific propositions to establish a probable generalised conclusion. In opposition to deductive, inductive approach initially starts with observation on research objects, discovering data patterns and eventually forms new theories, rather than testing an existing theory like deductive approach (Bryman, 2008). Under the

inductive approach, tentative hypotheses shall be determined along the process of detecting patterns in observations and repeatedly tested with additional data so that the researcher can form a sound social theory (Goddard and Melville, 2004). Inductive approach is found more frequently in qualitative research and under interpretivism philosophy which concentrates more on the subjectivity of humanities and each individual's personal experience and behaviour (Saunders et al., 2019; Neuman, 2000). A comparison diagram for deductive and inductive approach can be seen as follows:

Deductive vs Inductive approach respectively

This research has chosen to follow a deductive research approach. Behavioural finance is used since the start of this study as an existing theory to argue against the efficiency of the market, make certain assumptions on investors' irrationality and build specific hypotheses needed testing in the cryptocurrency market. The theory is then used to establish the statements for evaluation for the self-completion questionnaire in order to detect biases amongst cryptocurrency investors. This is more consistent with the deductive approach which allows the researcher to find the answer to her specific research questions. Moreover, the positivism philosophy is adopted as mentioned in the previous section. This makes deductive to be the more appropriate and consistent research approach, rather than inductive which is more associated with interpretivism research.

3.5. RESEARCH DESIGN

Saunders et al. (2019) suggested three main different types of research purpose which can assist researchers to select the right methods:

- Explanatory research
- Exploratory research
- Descriptive research

Explanatory research is the type of research that is used to uncover the cause and effect of a particular phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2019). Explanatory research is often found with developing hypotheses and testing them to find a correlation between variables to explain a certain event on 'how' and 'why' it happens (Saunders et al., 2019). It attempts to gain deeper understanding of a problem by reviewing a pre-determined theory or set a preliminary foundation for future research (Williams, 2007). Measures on certain causes and impacts should be clearly identified before conducting data collection, hence, exploratory research adopts a highly structured research approach (Saunders et al., 2019). Researchers who follow an explanatory research mostly find themselves to gather data by distributing surveys or conducting experiments and further apply quantitative methods when analysing data (Patten and Newhart, 2017).

Exploratory research is explained to be an approach seeking to explore study subjects that have not been examined in-depth prior (Haslam and McGarty, 2014). Its purpose is to provide a groundwork of an analysis to a problem instead of testing any defined hypotheses and providing precise conclusions to the research questions (Bob, Scapens and Theobald, 2002). It is designed to answer the open questions beginning with 'what' or 'how' about the problem being studied (Saunders et al., 2019). Consequently, the questions given to the observations during the process of collecting data should be in line with those open questions in order to gain deeper understanding and insights about the problem (Haslam and McGarty, 2014). Exploratory research is often associated with the qualitative method with unstructured interviews or literature review so that the

researcher has the flexibility to ask more in-depth open questions (Saunders et al., 2019). As a result, the quality of an exploratory research heavily relies on the value of the observations included in the study (Saunders et al., 2019).

The third type of research to be considered is descriptive research. It aims at portraying a specific type of events or individuals as the word 'descriptive' refers to (Saunders et al., 2019). Unlike exploratory research which seek to understand the reason and why an type of event occurs, descriptive research looks to describe the overall data being collected and provide certain characteristics linking to it (Omston, Spencer and Barnard, 2014). Data under descriptive research can also be used to examine the relationships between defined variables, however, they do not provide evidence of causality like explanatory research (Scholtz, Klerk and Beer, 2020). Descriptive research can be found to be associated with both quantitative or qualitative studies (Koh and Owen, 2000). While quantitative descriptive research presents a comprehensive narrative and identification of trends or patterns in behaviours about the sample, qualitative descriptive research looks for a subjective perspective about that type of events or individuals (Kim et al., 2017). In terms of data collecting methods, descriptive research is inherent to interviews, observations, case studies and questionnaires (Jansen, 2010).

This research study seeks to find the causal relationship between crypto investors' performance and the behaviour biases, hence, this matches with the nature of an explanatory research. Behavioural biases namely overconfidence, availability, anchoring, regret aversion, loss aversion, mental accounting and herding are determined prior under the theory of behavioural finance and survey questions were formed in order to measure these seven specific biases. Investment outcome is also included as a variable in the data collection process to serve the purpose of finding its relationships with the biases. Furthermore, another research's objective is to understand the correlation between investment outcomes and two different investing motivations: increasing wealth (1) and believing in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth (2). A variable is particularly created with respect to these motives while conducting survey questions to find its correlation with investment

outcome and listed behavioural biases. This objective does not necessarily aim at examining a causal relation but rather an association relation. Descriptive research hence is to be additionally adopted. In summary, a combination of descriptive and explanatory is set to be the purpose of this study.

3.6. RESEARCH STRATEGY

Johannesson and Perjons (2014) defines research strategy as the comprehensive plan involving certain techniques and methodologies to effectively assist researchers in monitoring and executing their study. This section will therefore contain discussions on the options of research methodology available during the data collection and analysis phases, followed by the reasonings and selection of the most appropriate one for this research study.

3.6.1. QUANTITATIVE METHOD

Within the domain of research strategy, a methodological choice on how the data can be collected and analysed should further be determined. Saunders et al. (2019) proposed three options for researchers in business and management as follows:

- Quantitative method
- Qualitative method
- Mixed method

Quantitative and qualitative methods can be differentiated through the nature of data where quantitative approach involves numbers and qualitative approach assesses non-numeric data (Saunders et al., 2019). For this reason, a sufficient sample size is

demanded in quantitative research (Faber and Fonseca, 2014). Evaluating data in qualitative research can be time consuming, hence, it requires a much smaller sample compared to quantitative research (Boddy, 2016). They can also be distinguished through the lense of research by considering research philosophies, reasoning approaches and strategies (Saunders et a., 2019). As previously discussed in the research philosophy sub-chapter, positivism is generally associated with quantitative method since one of the underlying assumptions includes the independence between the researcher and the observations (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). Nonetheless, qualitative researchers are widely interpretivists (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020).

In terms of reasoning approaches, quantitative method is highly correlated with deductive approach whereas qualitative method largely follows either inductive or abductive approach (Burns and Groove, 2014). Quantitative research consists of statistical analysis to discover correlation between a set of variables while qualitative research conducts data analysis through the employment of conceptualisation (Saunders et al., 2019). In terms of research strategies, quantitative method is predominantly adopted through experiments, questionnaires or structured interviews (Kothari, 2004). On the other hand, qualitative method can be found to link with a range of strategies such as action research, case studies or grounded theory (Saunders et al., 2019). In addition to the two proposed methods, researchers can choose to adopt mixed method including both quantitative and qualitative approaches if two or more phases of collecting input comprise.

Quantitative method is chosen to apply in this study since its research objective is to examine the relationship between a number of variables where investment performance and outcome of crypto investors is deemed to be the dependent variable and investing motivations as well as named behavioural biases act as independent variables. According to Leedy and Ormrod (2014), qualitative research using open-ended questions can provide in-depth understanding about human social behaviours. However, with the subjective philosophy paradigm, the findings presented by qualitative research cannot be generalised to the bigger population and sometimes can

be invalid and misleading (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). Behavioural biases might not be initially collected in the form of numbers, however, it is possible to quantify them using a number of quantitative methods which have become advanced and more widely used in behavioural science (Leshner and Pfaff, 2011). Furthermore, since the aim of this research is also to describe two different profiles of crypto investors, a quantitative method is more appropriate to adopt. By conducting research on an adequate sample size, their generalised characteristics can be identified whereas following the qualitative method on a small sample might not be suitable in this case. Mixed method is also found to be inappropriate since this research only consists of one data collection phase.

3.6.2. SURVEY

Under the quantitative research method, Saunders et al. (2019) stated there are two principal research strategies open but not limited to business and management researchers. They are:

- Experimental strategy
- Survey strategy

While both strategies are designed to test out hypotheses and assess relationships between certain variables, their nature of settings can be considered to be significantly different. Experimental strategy is designed to take place within an experimental research. It demands a highly controlled physical environment such as a laboratory or a workplace where researchers can conduct full observations on the objects being studied (Andersen and Clevenger, 1963). This also gives them the ability to influence independent variables in some ways to detect different changes in impacts on the dependent variable (Ledyard, 2020). As a result, experimental strategy can produce accurate and reliable data as well as research findings (Ledyard, 2020).

Experimental design is often utilised within the field of physical and natural science since it involves strong engagement of physical activities between a researcher and intended observations (Asgari and Baptista Nunes, 2011). Respectively, experimental design can be costly and time consuming to set up, even on a relatively small sample (Asgari and Baptista Nunes, 2011). On the other hand, survey strategy is designed for explanatory or descriptive research. Survey strategy does not necessarily require physical attendance of participants. Alternatively it gives the options of conducting research remotely in the forms of questionnaires or interviews (Wardropper et al., 2021). However, attending research remotely and having minimal direct interaction with the studied objects can significantly minimise the direct ability to manipulate independent variables under survey design compared to experimental design (Kelley et al., 2003). Survey design is largely employed in the field of social and behaviour study since it allows participants to report to the researcher directly about their feelings and attitudes (Grunert and Olander, 2012).

Survey is chosen to be the research strategy for this study. Since this research pursues the explanatory and descriptive purpose as determined previously, experimental design is not suitable since it only applies under experimental research. Prior discussion on the essentiality of a sufficient sample size for this research is visited and found survey design to be more appropriate to employ. Considering the context of when this research is being conducted, the emergence of the coronavirus or COVID-19 in 2019 put the world on hold with measurements in social distancing and occurrence of national lockdowns (Nicola et al., 2020). This has immersively created travelling difficulties and direct social interaction challenges not only to academic researchers but everyone around the world. Taking this problem into account, the researcher takes the option of collecting data remotely whereas that was not possible if experimental research was undertaken. In addition, since the conducted research falls under behavioural business and management, it can be said that survey is the most suitable strategy to maximise its utility within the studying field (Saunders et al., 2019; Grunert and Olander, 2012)

3.6.3. DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Survey design offers three main categories of data collection methods (Saunders et al., 2019) such as:

- Observation
- Interview
- Questionnaire

The first type of data gathering method is observation where the researcher recognises and records actions and behaviours of the participants in a particular environment (Kawulich 2005). The second method is interviews which allow a researcher to ask questions and evaluate respondents' answers accordingly (Fox, 2009). There are three types of interviews namely structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews (Saunders et al., 2019). The term 'structured' refers to the kind of questions presented during an interview where only close-ended questions are included while unstructured interviews permit full flexibility for the researcher to raise all available open-ended queries and semi-structured ones include both types of questions (Saunders et al., 2019). The third method is questionnaires in which self-completing questionnaires are highly common in use during conducting quantitative research.

Online self-completing questionnaires are deemed to be selected for the following reasons. Saunders et al. (2019) stated that respondents' characteristics play a crucial role in determining the right data collection method. In order to own, store and trade cryptocurrency, electronic devices are a must-have for cryptocurrency investors (Sung and Park, 2019). This benefits the choice of using online questionnaires as they maximise the accessibility of the questionnaire itself. Like how the name indicates, self-completing questionnaires are distributed to the reachable respondents and allow themselves to complete in their own time and space. It introduces flexibility and

convenience to both researcher and the respondents so that there is no need to organise mutual available time on both sides.

Another aspect of convenience is that all data will be collected and stored digitally. That means manual data input is not required unless information needs to be integrated from different platforms. Compared to other survey methods, online questionnaires are found to be least time consuming and also highly cost effective (Szolnoki and Hoffmann, 2013). In the case of this research, the author uses microsoft forms which is free to the users and offers all functionalities and features necessarily needed to build the survey questions. Furthermore, online self-completing questionnaires offer anonymity which some respondents might find more comfortable in disclosing sensitive information (Ong and Weiss, 2000).

3.7. SAMPLE DESIGN

One of the main features of cryptocurrency is decentralisation which does not require a centralised body to manage any assets (Vaidhyanathan and Jain, 2022). All crypto coins are also digital (Rodriguez, 2021), which means having an internet connection is fundamental in investing in cryptocurrency. For these reasons regardless of geography, people from across the globe can participate in the cryptocurrency market as long as the internet is accessible for them. A recent study from Broker Chooser (2020) conducted a survey on the percentage of crypto awareness and ownership across nations around the world. As of 2020, the study reported around 8 percent of American citizens have once owned and invested in cryptocurrency. That is approximately 26 million people using the whole population of America in 2020 stated by World Bank (2020). Ukraine and Russia are at the top of the list of percentage crypto ownership with 12.7 percent and 11.9 percent respectively. That accounts for around 23 million people of both Ukraine and Russia combined with the population statistics reported by World Bank (2020). The United Kingdom was stated to have about 5 percent of their citizens or 5 percent of approximately 67 million Britains according to World Bank (2020) participating in the

cryptocurrency market. That adds the total of crypto investors across four countries to around 52 millions crypto investors.

According to Saunders et al. (2019) and Krejcie and Morgan (1970), 384 is recommended for the ideal sample size for researchers using a 95 percent confidence level and 5 percent for margin of error on any population that is larger than 100,000. Smaller samples could also be considered, however, smaller samples result in increasing margin of errors which means the less reliable the findings will be as sample size decreases (Saunders et al, 2019). Having said that, using confidence level and the size of population to calculate the sample is not always the rule of thumbs to determine the right sample size (VanVoorhis and Morgan, 2007). Reasonable sample size can be decided by considering the statistical test to be used in analysing data (VanVoorhis and Morgan, 2007).

Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson and Tatham (1998) provided a recommendation of at least 100 observations to gain better fit while running statistical analysis. To detect group differences, Cohen (1988) suggested a size of 30 per group is ideal to apply t-test and one way analysis of variance. In order to examine correlation relationships, Green (1991) built a formula for quantitative research and suggested at least a sample size of 50 adding the total number of independent variables should produce a good estimate.

For factor analysis, Tabachnick and Fidell (1996) and Comrey and Lee (1992) proposed a sample of 300 cases is an adequate sample size. For descriptive statistics, researchers can be less strict by not sticking to a good sample size, however, a sample in between 200 and 500 is ideal for multiple regression and analysis of covariance (Israel, 1992). Having reviewed the literature points on determining the right sample size for this research, the author decides to pursue a sample of 250 individual crypto investors which follows the recommendations of Hair et al. (1998), Green (1991), Israel (1992) and satisfies the sample formula proposed by Saunders et al (2019) if the margin of error is raised to 6.2% instead of 5% in the case above.

The author uses the voluntary response sampling method for the data collection phase of this research. Probability sampling was initially preferred as the advantages of using probability sampling methods are simplistic, able to generate highly representative samples of the whole population and minimise any potential biases (Cook, 2005). However, since the whole population of cryptocurrency investors around the world is significantly large and can be measured at least in millions, it is impossible for the researcher to obtain a full sampling frame, or in a different term, the complete list of all crypto investors across the globe.

Saunders et al. (2019) recommended non-probability sampling methods should be considered instead of probability sampling methods. Hence, the voluntary response sampling under non-probability sampling design is chosen. Like the name of the method indicates, it is understood to be the response gathering method from people who choose to participate voluntarily. It falls under non-probability or non-random sampling as certain biases are present. The sample is made up of people who are connected to the mediators bridging surveys to them, therefore, the group of people that are unavailable to reach and not willing to volunteer will be excluded from sampling (Tiit, 2021). Another bias is individuals likely to participate in a voluntary survey have the tendency to express strong opinions about the raised topic (Tiit, 2021). In other words, the method of voluntary response sampling tends to oversample participants who express relatively intense attitudes and judgements and undersample the ones with less interest about the matter.

Nonetheless, considering all non-random sampling methods have some particular biases to themselves, Grooves (2006) and Jupp (2006) argue that voluntary surveys are widely used in the field of academic research and more convenient in rolling studies on a national scale. Glen (2015) further adds this type of sampling design helps researchers to save time and produce ease at gathering data. The questionnaire built for this research is distributed via crypto investing related threads on platforms namely Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Reddit, Discord, Telegram, Survey Swap, Survey Circle, and

Prolific. Due to time constraint and limited resources, the author collected a total of 246 responses. That is 4 responses under the anticipated sample size which only accounts for 1.6% of the intent. Saunders et al. (2019) indicated that the decision on a sample size can depend on the availability of resources and affordability of the researcher. The sample of 246 observations also satisfied the adequate threshold of 200-500 under recommendations from Israel (1992). In addition, the author filtered the responses with the screening questions as below. If the responder chooses “no” for both questions, they will not participate in this study. The first criteria is indeed to filter crypto investors and non-crypto investors, whereas the second criteria is to reduce the inclination towards speculative investors with no investing experience and gather investors who have had some previous exposure to types of market conditions, more familiar with market analysis as well as composing investing strategies.

- Have you invested in cryptocurrency before?
- Do you invest into anything else rather than crypto?

3.8. DESIGN OF MEASUREMENTS AND MODEL SPECIFICATION

3.8.1. DESIGN OF MEASUREMENTS AND QUESTIONNAIRES

The questionnaire for this research contains four sections which can be categorised as engagement in the cryptocurrency market, investment outcome, influencing behavioural factors and demographic information. Information based on the engagement in the cryptocurrency market is gathered from the list of five questions below:

No	Question	Measurement scale
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1	What is the biggest motivation of yours to invest in the cryptocurrency market?	Nominal
2	How often do you trade with cryptocurrency?	Ratio
3	How many years of trading do you have (including trading foreign exchange, equity, etc)?	Ratio
4	What are the crypto securities that you often trade with?	Nominal
5	How much monthly capital do you normally trade with?	Ratio

Alongside with the hope to detect impacts of behavioural factors on retail crypto investors, the objective of this research is also to divide the sample into two groups by having different motivations in owning a cryptocurrency coin. By revisiting the chapter of literature review, this study looks to assess the two predominant reasons why people invest in crypto. They are the desire to increase wealth (1) and strong belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth (2). Most participants are expected to have both as their motivations, however, the question is addressed by asking “what is the biggest motivation of yours” and the answer is only open to one selection. The second, third and fifth questions select ratio scale as measurement method since these questions require measurements in time and money and an order of response (Dalati, 2018). The fourth question asks for multiple selection of cryptocurrency coins that investors have once owned or are actively trading with, hence, nominal scale is chosen for investors to pick names of their crypto coins.

For investment decisions and influencing behaviour factors, all questions are asked in the forms of evaluating provided statements and likert scale is used in the process of gathering data. Messick (1989) stated researchers can find Likert Scale strongly useful to measure psychological constructs. They include personal characteristics on affection,

emotions, behaviours and cognitive attitudes (Nemoto and Beglar, 2014). Jebb, Ng and Tay (2021) further added Likert Scale plays an important role in modern psychology studies and is widely used for intangible observation measurements. Likewise, investment decisions are looked at through the lens of investment satisfactions and are also measured based on Likert Scale. Barber and Odean (2001) and Chang and Shi (2011) argue that investment performance and outcome based on risks and returns through recorded historical data often generate underperformance findings about individual investors. Abdin, Qureshi, Iqbal and Sultana (2022) demonstrated there is a necessity of assessing investment performance via investors' satisfactions on their own investments. Abdin et al. (2022) further addressed that behavioural finance has created investing satisfactions as the alternative way to measure investment performance and outcome since investors might achieve low returns but they are happy or feel that is enough. Therefore, a Likert Scale of five points in the order of strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree is employed to measure behavioural factors and investment outcome of crypto individual investors.

Under the second part of the questionnaire which is investment outcome, the statements given to the survey participants to evaluate themselves are presented below. They contain in total 7 questions and are divided into two categories: returns on investments and investment satisfactions.

No	Category	Statements to be evaluated with five point Likert Scale	Sources
6	Returns on investments	The return rate of my recent crypto investment meets my expectations (IP1)	Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), Karmacharya,
7		My extra income has been generated significantly from crypto investments (IP2)	

8		The return rate of my crypto investments is better than that of my investment in any other markets (IP3)	Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022)
9	Investment satisfactions	In the past year, I am satisfied with my choice of buying orders (IP4)	
10		In the past year, I am satisfied with my choice of selling orders (IP5)	
11		In the past year, I am satisfied with my choice of picking assets (IP6)	
12		In the past year, I am satisfied with my choice of trading volume (IP7)	

All statements that are dated from number 6 to 12 are collectively adopted from Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), Karmacharya, Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022) and many more scholars in the field using this based groundwork (Le and Doan, 2011; Audu and Abubakar, 2019; Sugathadasa, 2018; Rehan and Umer, 2017; Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna, 2020; Sukamulja, Meilita and Senoputri, 2019).

The third part following the crypto investment outcome is behavioural finance factors. Under influencing behavioural factors, survey respondents are similarly asked to evaluate a set of twenty statements which measures seven behavioural biases: overconfidence (1), loss aversion (2), regret aversion (3), anchoring (4), herding (5), availability (6) and mental accounting (7). Details on those statements can be found in the below table.

No	Category	Statements	Sources
13	Overconfidence	I am an experienced trader (OC1)	Sahai (2014)
14		My forecast on market is better than that of my friends and relatives (OC2)	
15		I can pinpoint the major reversals in the crypto market (OC3)	
16	Loss Aversion	I am more concerned about a loss in my position than missing a substantial gain (LA1)	Sahai (2014)
17		I feel nervous when my holdings lose value (LA2)	
18		I will not increase my investment when the market performance is poor (LA3)	
19		When it comes to investments, no loss in capital is more important than returns (LA4)	
20	Regret Aversion	When I suffer losses, I tend to avoid the same investment (RA1)	Sukamulja, Meilita and Senoputri (2019)
21		I will stick to my investments rather than making new ones with higher returns but also with bigger risks (RA2)	

22		I feel uncomfortable to make an investment that once made me lose (RA3)	
23	Anchoring	I am unlikely to buy a coin if it was more expensive than last year (AC1)	Karmacharya, Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022)
24		I use the coin's purchase price as a reference point for trade (AC2)	
25		I am likely to sell my coin after the price hits recent year high (AC3)	
26	Herding	I tend to follow investment suggestion of the majority, rather than the opposition of a few (HRD1)	Kudryavtsev, Cohen and Hon-Snir (2013)
27		I tend to increase the sum of my crypto holdings if the recent market trading volume is higher than usual (HRD2)	
28	Availability	I prefer to buy coins on the days that the value of BTC increases (AV1)	Kudryavtsev, Cohen and Hon-Snir (2013)
29		If I heard from a friend about a coin that recently achieved high returns, I would buy it (AV2)	
30	Mental Accounting	I do not care about the performance of my investment portfolio as a whole but I care about the return of each asset separately (MA1)	Karmacharya, Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022),

31		I tend to treat each asset of my investment portfolio differently (MA2)	Pompian (2012)
32		I hesitate selling coins that recently fell in price but had high returns in the past (MA3)	

The order of each sub-category does not follow the order from heuristics, prospect theory and lastly herding. The reason for the adjustment is for less fatigue and lengthy effect for survey participants through each stage of the questionnaire. Question 13 to 15 refer to the overconfidence bias and are adopted from Sahai (2014). Similarly, the next four questions on loss aversion bias are also selected from Sahai (2014). To measure regret aversion bias, it is assigned to question 20, 21 and 22 and adopted the narratives from Sukamulja, Meilita and Senoputri (2019). Question 23 to 25 are used to assess the anchoring bias among the cryptocurrency investors. Kudryavtsev, Cohen and Hon-Snir (2013) is then used to be the source for statements measuring herding and availability bias for question 26, 27 and 28, 29 respectively. Lastly, mental accounting finishes the behavioural bias scale measurement with the statements adopted from Karmacharya, Chapagain, Dhungana and Singh (2022). The criteria for choosing these sources is based on the testing reliability of their own research and also where the statements are worded in an anticipatedly clearest way for the respondents. Nonetheless, some statements have been modified to fit in the context of cryptocurrency since all used sources for this section are studies within the stock market (Sahai (2014); Sukamulya et al. (2019); Kudryavtsev et al. (2013); Karmacharya et al. (2022)).

The last part of the questionnaire is to collect demographic information about the survey respondents. That includes age, gender, level of education, marital status, ethnicity, employment status and annual income. Apart from age, level of education and annual income which adopt ratio scale as measurement method, the rest of the questions in this part employ nominal scale. Schmidt, Germano, Schmitt and Milani

(2019) advise ratio scale promotes discreteness and higher rate of disclosure in more sensitive subjects.

No	Questions	Measurement scale
33, 35, 39	Age, level of education and annual income respectively	Ratio
34, 36, 37, 38	Gender, marital status, ethnicity and employment status respectively	Nominal

3.8.2. DATA ANALYSIS METHODS AND MODEL SPECIFICATION

The aims of this study are revisited to consider which tests should be conducted in order to uncover the research questions and provide empirical findings. The first distinct objective is to examine the difference in investment performance and outcome of two distinguished crypto investor profiles who invest in cryptocurrency either for increasing wealth (1) or their belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth (2). In order to achieve this objective, an univariate analysis is conducted to find indicated t-test and p-value and to see if the difference is significant. In addition, the second distinct objective is to investigate which biases are more to be associated with which motivation under the behavioural finance aspect.

The relations between the behavioural biases namely overconfidence, anchoring, availability, loss aversion, regret aversion, mental accounting, and herding will be examined using the correlation matrix. The third objective of this paper is to find out what impacts crypto investors' associated biases have on their investment outcome. OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) regression is adopted to examine the influence of behavioural bias predictors on the investment outcome as the dependent variable.

STATA software is used to run all tests and regressions for this study. Acock (2005) indicated that STATA has a relatively user-friendly command system and is “extraordinary” on panel data regressions. Mitchell (2005) further added STATA is more powerful in intermediate and advanced statistical procedures compared to SPSS and SAS software. STATA also offers the ability to conduct econometrics tests to identify any model misspecification (Mitchell, 2005). Descriptive statistics is also used in order to describe the central and variability tendencies of the sample of crypto investors.

Descriptive statistics:

As mentioned above, descriptive statistics is widely used in the field of research and adopted as a technique to summarise the characteristics of the sample set by looking at the measurements for central tendency and variability of all available variables. In this study, median, mode and mean are considered for measurements of central tendency and minimum, maximum and standard deviation are examined as measurements of variability. All measurements are to be conducted on all independent variables including motivations and behavioural biases and dependent variable which is crypto investment outcome/performance. Descriptive statistics can be used to describe certain features of an entire population or a sample set. It is used to describe the behavioural finance characteristics of a sample which consists of 246 crypto investors in this paper.

Descriptive statistics will be analysed and adopted guidance from Al-Khadash (2015) to comment on the influential effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable based on the weighted mean and standard deviation.

Weighted mean	Level of agreement
Between 4.2 and 5	Very high

Between 3.40 and 4.19	High
Between 2.60 and 3.39	Average
Between 1.8 and 2.59	Low
Between 1 and 1.79	Very low

Source: Al-Khadash (2015)

Correlation matrix:

Correlation matrix is widely used to detect patterns between two or more variables by calculating correlation coefficients between each variable pair (Kumar and Chong, 2018). It is displayed in the form of a table and stated as a powerful way to summarise and disclose any present relationships within a large given data set (Bland and Altman, 1994). Pearson's correlation and Spearman's correlation are the two typical tools to measure association between variables. Pearson's r is used when all testing variables follow a normal distribution, whereas Spearman's correlation is selected to test monotonic relationships of non normally distributed or ordinal variables (Schobar, Boer and Schwarte, 2018). In the case of this study, Spearman's correlation is chosen since the variable assigned to motivations is measured in nominal scale. The behavioural statements are measured in Likert Scale and will be transformed to average values which present a mixture of interval and ordinal scale. In order to ensure accuracy, Spearman's correlation is therefore chosen to calculate the correlation coefficients.

The Spearman's correlation r can be expressed in the form of equation as follows:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where:

- $r(s)$ is the value of the Spearman's correlation score and only have the value between -1 and +1
- D is the difference between each pair of ranked measurements
- N is the total number of observations

However, correlation matrix is unable to detect any causal relationships which leads to the adoption of a regression model as the alternative method (Rohrer, 2018). An application of correlation matrix is to discover any problems regarding multicollinearity in a regression model. Further discussion on the multicollinearity test can be read at the end of this chapter.

Regression:

Regression analysis is typically a statistical method which can find the impact degree of one or more random variables on a particular interested variable. As discussed prior, regression models are highly popular in quantitative research and often used to detect causal relations. There are two types of variables that are needed to establish a regression model: independent variable(s) and dependent variables. Throughout this research work, readers will frequently see regressors, predictors or explanatory variables as synonyms for independent variables and output variable, regressed variable or predicted variable as other names for dependent variable. The process of analysing regression models helps researchers to confidently identify any significant impacts that one or more available independent variables have on a dependent variable (Chatterjee and Hadi, 2006).

Test of significance:

In regression analysis, t-test and f-test are used in order to test the significance of two hypothesis types. T-test is adopted to retain or reject any hypotheses which concern relationships between a set of predictors and the output variable. F-test is adopted to retain or reject hypotheses that a regression model is significant. Both t-test and f-test will be conducted and examined with 90%, 95% and 99% of confidence level.

REGRESSION MODEL

Multiple OLS regression is adopted to examine the influence of motivations and behavioural biases on crypto investment decisions. A range of previous studies such as Kumara and Kawshala (2021), Septian, Hasnawati and Hendrawaty (2022) and Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) proposed multiple regression analysis as a systematic way to detect the role of behavioural factors on stock market investors' decision making. The multiple regression equation is estimated based on the input of 246 survey participants who are actively investing in the cryptocurrency market.

Regarding the type of available data, cross-sectional data is used to analyse and estimate the model. Cross-sectional data is input information on one or more observations at a certain point in time (Olsen and St George, 2004). Cross-sectional data is extensively used in the field of medical, psychology and economics to report human behaviours and cognitive biases (De La Mare and Sergean, 1961). Nevertheless, cross-sectional studies have been relatively controversial in the sense that they cannot be used to uncover causality between variables and only serve the purpose of descriptive statistics as the collected data is present together at the same time (Thelle and Laake, 2015; Bignold, 2019). Mebane (1990) argued that pure cross-sectional studies can still be applied to assess causal relationships if researchers specify certain assumptions on

the collected data. Lewin (1951) stated in his field theory that causal relations can exist where only psychological facts present amongst studied observations can affect current situations. By adopting this assumption, the author of this study considers cross-sectional data to carry out the process of data analysis and look for meaningful interpretations from the empirical survey findings.

Multiple regression is used to test certain hypotheses that have been developed earlier in the literature review section. The hypotheses can be revisited and assisted to determine the list of independent variables as well as the single dependent variable. In the case of this study, motives and behavioural factors act as explanatory variables and investment decision amongst crypto investors is present as the regressed variable. By testing the significance of these hypotheses, the author can assess the impact level of motives and behavioural biases have on investment decisions. Multiple regression and t-test is therefore used as a tool to estimate whether the influences are significant. In addition, the model's error terms will be used to test a number of assumptions that will be discussed later on in this chapter.

The t-test formula to test the significance of the coefficients is slightly different to the proposed one in univariate analysis.

$$t = \frac{\beta_i - \beta_j}{SE}$$

Where:

- T is the value of t-test
- β_j is the estimated coefficient of the corresponding coefficient
- β_j is the null value of coefficient to be tested

- SE is the standard error associated with the corresponding coefficient

Linear multiple regression requires a number of assumptions in order to be considered accurate and reliable (Osborne and Walter, 2002). Violation of these assumptions can lead to invalid conclusions and the produced model to be scientifically wrongful in estimation (Krieger, 2018). Krieger (2018) indicated the following assumptions to establish a reliable multiple linear regression:

- Linear relationships between each of the predictors and the predicted variable
- No multicollinearity
- Homoscedasticity
- The error term is normally distributed

Linearity:

Linearity means that there are linear relationships between the pairs of each independent variable and the response variable. Tabachnick and Fidell (2006) argued that if this assumption is violated, the suggested statistical results from the regression model may not be able to give a generalised concept for the whole population. Absence of linearity in a multiple regression model implies an underestimation of true relations between the regressors and the regressed variable (Hox, 1995).

To test the linearity of a model, a graphic assessment in the form of scatter plots on the regressors and the regressed variable (Osborne and Waters, 2002). The assumption is met when the scatter plots of regressors follow a straight line as the value of the regressed variable increases (Stevens, 2009). If it does not follow a linearity but rather a curved tendency such in c curve or v curve, there is a non-linear relationship between the regressors and the regressed variable (Stevens, 2009). Osborne and Waters (2002)

further explained that a curved shape in the scatter plot diagram is an indication of non-random residuals.

Normality distribution:

The second assumption to have a reliable and accurate multiple regression model is to have the estimated model residual to follow a normal distribution. In other words, this assumes that the residual is random and free from bias which leads to better and more learning interpretation of coefficients. A non-normal distribution of residuals can exist in the form of outliers, skewness or kurtosis (Krieger, 2018). Failure to have a normal distribution may indicate that certain bias exists within the model's error term (Osborne and Waters, 2002). Osborne and Waters (2002) outline one of the reasons resulting in non-normal distribution in error terms can be the size of a sample being too small. Tabachnick and Fidell (2006) argued outliers can seem to be a problem when the sample is too large and skewness and kurtosis are more resistant on smaller samples.

In order to detect the non-normality in multiple regression models, histograms can be used to quickly visualise the following tendency of the residual as the predicted variable rises. Histogram is found to be helpful in examining the shape of a regressed distribution (Krieger, 2018). If the scores of the residual gather around the middle axis of the diagram and generate a bell shape for the distribution, it can be said that the residual follows a normal distribution (Krieger, 2018). When there is a skewness problem, the shape of the distribution can be leaning more towards one side of the diagram. If the tail is longer on the left hand side, it can be said that the residuals are negatively skewed (Krieger, 2018). Alternatively, if the tail is longer on the right, the residuals are positively skewed (Krieger, 2018).

In terms of the problem of kurtosis, the shape of the distribution can be recognised by some level of distortion and does not hold a good bell shape as it would be if it followed

a normal distribution. Tabachnick and Fidell (2006) explained the assumption of normality is violated with kurtosis when the peak of the distribution outlier can be seen to be out of shape or the tails to be slimmer or heavier. Krieger (2018) explained the most extreme case is to have zero value for both skewness and kurtosis to achieve perfect normal distribution, otherwise, scales between (-2;+2) can be considered as appropriate. In addition, the skewness-kurtosis test of Chi-square can also be used to test the hypothesis of normality in residuals. Similar with t-test and f-test, the null hypothesis of a normal distribution can retain if the p-value of chi-square is greater than 0.05 and reject if it produces a smaller value. This 0.05 value is based on the 95% confidence level. Other researchers may decide on which level of confidence is more reasonable to test the normality hypothesis.

Homoscedasticity:

The third assumption to consider in establishing multiple linear regression models is homoscedasticity for the model's residuals. Homoscedasticity in the error terms means that their associated variance is constant (Jarque and Bera, 1980). In other words, when the estimated value of the dependent variable changes, there is little to no noise in terms of residual disturbance. Evidence of homoscedasticity presents a high level of consistency in estimating the predicted values (Ruppert and Aldershof, 1989).

Heteroscedasticity is the opposite of homoscedasticity and means the variance of the error terms is not constant. To assess the level of homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity in the error terms, Osborne and Waters (2002) suggested to adopt the assistance of scatter plots between the residuals and the predicted variable, similarly in testing the assumption of linearity above. However, the scatter plots mentioned under the linearity assumption refer more to a curved shape in the error terms. The residuals tested for homoscedasticity on the other hand may produce scatter plots with patterns such as shrinking or expanding patterns. The homoscedasticity assumption is deemed to be met when the scatter plots of the residuals visually form a

linear trail in the diagram (Krieger, 2018). When the assumption is not met and apart from shrinking and expanding forms, heteroscedasticity may exist in the form of a bow tie or a fan blade (Osborne and Waters, 2002).

Apart from the option of a scatter plot diagram, the Breusch-Pagan test can be used to determine whether or not heteroscedasticity is present. The chi-squared test is used to statistically retain or reject the null hypothesis of constant variance. The null hypothesis can be retained when the p-value is bigger than 0.05 for 95% confidence level.

Multicollinearity test:

The fourth assumption for trustworthy multiple linear regressions is no multicollinearity between all variables. This anticipates that not only the response variable should be strongly uncorrelated with all explanatory variables, they should also be uncorrelated with each other. Multicollinearity can affect the reliability and wrongful estimation of a model or cause skewness problems (Frank, 2001). Shrestha (2020) explained when multicollinearity occurs, the standard errors for each regressor's coefficient broadens and result in retaining hypotheses of insignificant impacts. Aiken and West (1991) and Vatcheva, Lee, McCormick and Rahbar (2016) indicated multicollinearity can affect the standard errors that can further introduce the presence of nonlinearity and heteroscedasticity.

Another issue associated with multicollinearity is the tendency of volatile regression coefficients leading to inaccurate and unreliable analysis about them (Keith, 2015). To test for multicollinearity, Shrestha (2020) recommends Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) as an useful technique for the matter. VIF can be adopted when there are two or more regressors and tend to magnify when two variables are correlated. If VIF has a value of 1, it means that the pair of variables is considered to be non-correlated (Brown, Tauler and Walczak, 2020). VIF holding a value between 1 and 5 can interpret the variables as

being moderately correlated (Shrestha, 2020). Any value more than 5 can recognise the variables to be highly correlated (Shrestha, 2020). Therefore, a VIF value that is greater than 1 and smaller than 5 can be accepted and consider no multicollinearity existing in the regression model. The formula for VIF can be found as follow:

$$VIF = \frac{1}{1 - R^2} = \frac{1}{Tolerance}$$

Where:

- VIF is the Variance Inflation Factor
- R^2 is the coefficient of determination of the regressed model

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA)

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical technique by analysing the variance of the data between different parts in a data set. Kenton (2022) stated that ANOVA is largely adopted in the field of statistics to compare the part affected by systematic elements and random elements in a multiple regression model. Explanatory variables can be considered for systematic elements as researchers can quantify the effect they have on the response variable. Random elements are the residuals or error terms that are associated with the proposed model. The ultimate goal of ANOVA is to detect if the explanatory variables are statistically and overly significant as well as being a good fit for the regression model.

F-test is used as a tool in ANOVA for this purpose. If hypothesis testing is generated with the null hypothesis being that all explanatory variables do not influence the response variable and the alternative hypothesis being at least one of them is significant, researchers can reject the null hypothesis if the p-value for F-test is less than 0.05 with

95% confidence level. The formula for F-statistic can be calculated by determining the mean sum of regression squares and mean error sum of squares.

$$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$$

Where:

- F is the F-statistic
- MSR is the mean sum of regression squares
- MSE is the mean error sum of squares

In order to get the value of MSR and MSE, a process of calculation shall be followed as below:

$$SST = \sum_{j=1}^N (y_j - \bar{y})^2 = SSR + SSE$$

$$SSR = \sum_{j=1}^N (\hat{y}_j - \bar{y})^2 = SST - SSE$$

$$SSE = \sum_{j=1}^N (y_j - \hat{y}_j)^2 = \sum_{j=1}^N e_j^2 = SST - SSR$$

$$MSR = \frac{SSR}{k}$$

$$MSE = \frac{SSE}{n - k - 1}$$

Where:

- SST is the total sum of squares
- SSR is the total sum of regression squares
- SSE is the total sum of error squares
- y_j is the fitted value of the predicted factor
- \hat{y}_j is the estimated value of the predicted factor
- \bar{y} is the overall sample mean of the predicted factor

- N is the total number of observations
- K is the number of explanatory variables

CRONBACH'S ALPHA

Since the survey questionnaire used for data collection of this study contains a range of evaluating statement sets linking to each behavioural finance biases, it is important to determine the reliability of testing scales and essentially confirm if they are good measurements. Bonett and Wright (2014) and Tavakol and Dennick (2011) suggested Cronbach's alpha as a helpful tool to check the internal consistency within a set of group items in social science and business studies. The implication of Cronbach's alpha could also be seen in previous behavioural finance researches namely but not limited to Kengarathan and Kengarathan (2014), Hussain et al. (2022), Septian et al. (2022) and Wali et al. (2022). The Cronbach's alpha score can range from 0 to 1 whereas 0 implies no consistency or dependency amongst the scale items and 1 implies perfect inter-correlation. It is recommended by numerous methodologists that researchers should accept items with the value of Cronbach's alpha between 0.6 and 0.8. Cortina (1993) indicated a Cronbach's score of 0.7 is generally accepted for appropriate reliability but approaching 0.8 or more is also highly desirable. This is in line with Shemwell, Chase and Schwart (2015) and Barbera, Naibert, Komperda and Pentecost (2020). However, Taber (2018) and Griethuijsen et al. (2014) suggested a lower score of 0.6 is considered to be moderate inter-correlation, hence, 0.6 is still adequate. Taber (2018) further indicated that a score under 0.55 can be considered to be not satisfied.

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sigma_{y_i}^2}{\sigma_x^2} \right)$$

Where:

- α is the score for Cronbach's alpha
- K is the total number of scale items or statements

- $\sigma_{y_i}^2$ is the variance connecting with item i
- σ_x^2 is the variance of the total scale

MODEL SPECIFICATIONS AND VARIABLES

Multiple regression analysis has been chosen to examine the effect of motives and behavioural factors in crypto investor's decision outcome. Eight hypotheses which have been determined in this research's literature review chapter where investment outcome is the only predicted variable throughout all eight hypotheses. The eight explanatory variables included in the multiple regression model are motives, overconfidence, anchoring, availability, loss aversion, regret aversion, mental accounting and herding. Accordingly, the specified model for this study can be viewed as follows:

$$IO_i = \alpha + \beta_1 MOTIV_i + \beta_2 OC_i + \beta_3 AC_i + \beta_4 AV_i + \beta_5 LA_i + \beta_6 RA_i + \beta_7 MA_i + \beta_8 HRD_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

As discussed prior, the predicted variable investment outcome and the explanatory variable apart from motives are measured based on a set of scale items. The author adopts one-way aggregation to fit and take into account all scales categorised by groups. This means for instance, all scale items classified under variable overconfidence are added up and present as sum of scale and the rest of behavioural factors can adopt the same way. The one-way aggregation therefore makes up the total scale of an investor being perfectly overconfident to be 15 instead of 5. This is because there are three statements or scale items to be evaluated under the overconfidence bias. With the highest score of 5 can be awarded to each statement, the score can multiply with the number of statements available under each bias. In the case of loss aversion, there are 4 scale items in total, hence, the highest score one can be awarded for loss aversion bias is 20. In the case of herding and availability biases, only 2 scale items are included as

measurements which leads the maximum score for these factors to be only 10. In addition, the predicted variable investment outcome consists of 7 scale items in total. The utmost limit for the best investment outcome can be scored with 35.

The diagnostics tests for model misspecification namely linearity, normality, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity are proposed prior and it is highly suggested by Krieger (2018) that these tests should be conducted as soon as the regression model is established to prevent any inaccurate results and data misinterpretations. All tests were carried out on model (1) and found evidence of non-normality in the error terms. A histogram was used to assess the shape of the residuals' distribution which eventually defined negative skew as the problem. Peacock and Peacock (2011) and Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) recommended transformation on the predicted variable such as logarithm, squared, square root and inverse function methods can essentially introduce normal distribution to the residuals. The researcher of this study employs the squared method on dependent variable investment outcome and results give normal distribution to the error terms. The new multiple regression model is now:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (IO_i)^2 &= \alpha + \beta_1 MOTIV_i + \beta_2 OC_i + \beta_3 AC_i + \beta_4 AV_i + \beta_5 LA_i + \beta_6 RA_i \\
 &+ \beta_7 MA_i + \beta_8 HRD_i + \varepsilon_i
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

3.9. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Certain ethical and access issues have been considered while conducting research design and data collection for this research. In this section, these problems will be addressed separately into two phases: data collection (1), data analysing (3) and reporting (2).

DATA COLLECTION

During the phase of data collection, Kitchin (2007) defines three aspects of ethical manners in internet-based research designs with human participants: autonomy, beneficence and integrity. Anonymity has been emphasised by Flicker, Haans and Skinner (2004) and Kitchin (2007) as an important research principle where a research worker is obligated to protect the solitude and nobility of any participating individuals. Gelinias et al (2017) indicated personal information of survey respondents should be strongly secured and allow themselves to be able to undisclosed this type of data. Keller and Lee (2010) and Moreno et al (2013) promote the option to remain anonymous to protect an individual's identity if one decides to adopt survey questionnaires as their research design.

Flicker et al (2004) and Coleman (2021) highlight the use of informed consent form and participant information sheet to be highly crucial to assist communication between a researcher and survey participants under anonymity. Beneficency refers to a researcher's own assessment on the potential threats and benefits on psychological impacts upon taking part in the study (Gupta, 2017). Kitchin (2007) suggested it is vital to prevent and minimise all disadvantages and boost all advantages available to survey respondents. The main threats which might harm an individual are the exposure of personal identification as well as damages in one's emotions and reputations (Townsend and Wallace, 2016; Gelinias et al, 2017).

Regarding the integrity aspect, Kitchin (2007) demonstrated that researchers should act transparently, unbiased and free from discrimination throughout the whole data collection phase. Gupta (2017) stated researchers should disclose their contact points, honesty about the research purpose and procedures. This information can be included in the participant information sheet and presented to all participants at the beginning of a questionnaire (Gupta, 2017). Saunders et al (2019) also highlighted studies conducted under a researching facility should seek for approval from the facility's ethical committee.

By following the scholars on research ethics during the data collection phase, a participant information sheet and informed consent form were prepared to advise all necessary information so that prospective survey participants understand their rights to be protected. In terms of the participant information sheet, it contains relevant contact points about the author, the research facility and her direct supervisor, the aim of the study, information upon participating as well as the outlined benefits and risks when taking part in the study.

The purpose of the study is clearly stated in the participant information sheet as “investigation on the behaviours of crypto investors, from the behavioural finance perspective” and is further declared to only serve the purpose of scholarly research. Information upon participation includes the right to take part without pressure, free to withdraw at any time while inputting data and options to raise a complaint about the research. Data exposure is identified to be the risk upon completing the questionnaire. To minimise this risk, the author proposes the procedure of password protected archives and no personal identifiable information collection throughout the survey to maintain highest confidentiality of prospective responders.

The author also indicated her act in accordance with the Data Protection Act 1998 to securely store collected data for the maximum of 5 years. After this period of time, all collected data shall be destroyed. Informed consent is also included to seek approval of all respondents on all research details before entering the survey. Another risk discovered for this study is unpleasantness and embarrassment while evaluating investment performance and behavioural bias statements. More positive and euphemism wordings are used to avoid any distressing tendency and emotions amongst the survey participants. Before conducting data collection for this study, an ethical application was submitted and granted approval by the University of the West of Scotland’s ethics committee.

DATA ANALYSIS

During the data analysis and reporting phase, Resnick (2000) stated there are a number of ethical considerations that the research cannot miss. They require their own resolution to make sure that the moral, ethical and integrity values remain throughout the research process. These issues can be categorised into misinterpretations (1) and misuse of research techniques (2). Data fabrication, which means false and own formulated data by the researchers, is defined to be the most severe form of data misinterpretations (Resnick, 2000; Rosenthal, 1994). Researchers following this path if identified can face cancellation of their research work and essentially enormous damage to their career (Rosenthal, 1994). Another form of data misinterpretation is data manipulation (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). Under data manipulation, the make up addition to the missing data or excluding certain information to steer more to the researcher's anticipation can significantly result in wrongful estimation and misleading discussion (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). Furthermore, failure to use the right statistical technique is stated as another serious unethical practice in researching and potentially have a significant influence on research findings (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). This entails an attempt to switch to different statistical methodologies in order to achieve the desired result (Poon and Ainuddin, 2001). This leads to complete misleading interpretations and large statistical errors (Resnick, 2000). By doing this, researchers violate the code of ethics when they already acknowledge the unacceptance of misapplication of methodology (Resnick, 2000).

To control the potential issues that have been previously discussed, the author of this study introduces a number of approaches to administer these issues. During the stage of data collection, all questions provided to survey participants were marked as required which leaves no room for missing data. All 246 survey respondents provided in respect manners with answers to every question in the questionnaire. No missing variable was generated by the author as the questionnaire survey is publicly available to everyone and one can easily detect if any false data is added when the study results are published. In terms of statistical method misuse, the author has gained valuable advice and

assistance in defining the most appropriate research methodologies in the context of behavioural finance and crypto investments, especially for this study. Regarding data misinterpretation, the author promises to act in the most ethical and high integrity manners to prevent this problem. In addition, the researcher's supervisors are present throughout the research process and supervise all the research work of hers.

DATA REPORTING

Aquinis and Henle (2000) and Calebrese and Roberts (2004) indicated four ethical considerations for academic researchers in the phase of reporting data: plagiarism, fragmentation, concurrent various submissions and unwarranted authorship recognition. Firstly, plagiarism can be considered to be the most serious misconduct in research but remains popular amongst scholars (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). It essentially means one claims some or all another researcher's work to be his or hers (APA, 2010). The convenience and increasing use of internet nowadays seem to facilitate the tendency for plagiarism, however, a number of softwares and applications have been developed to detect that and employed by education institutions around the world such as Turnitin or Dupli Checker (Gibelman and Gelman, 2003; Poon and Ainuddin, 2011).

Another case of plagiarism is that a researcher recycles their own work to publish as a new one (APA, 2010). The consequence for this case can lead to deceive of knowledge, spoiling different kinds of resources, and potential copyrights complications (APA, 2010). Secondly, fragmentation involves the attempt of the researcher to separate his or her own work into smaller parts in order to gain a high number of publications (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). Thirdly, concurrent various submissions means multiple work submissions to many different publishers at the same time (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011). Finally, unwarranted authorship recognition entails the internal decision making on the order of ownership when two or more authors are involved in their research work (Poon and Ainuddin, 2011).

In the context of this study, the author does not tolerate plagiarism and the use of other scholar's work without proper referencing. Since this study is being conducted under the University of the West of Scotland, Turnitin as suggested by Poon and Ainuddin (2011) is used as a plagiarism managing application to verify the authenticity and genuinity of the author's work. References to work of relevant academia and scholars have been included throughout this research study to express the author's respect and accord credits to the intellectual work of other authors. Regarding fragmentation, concurrent various submissions and unwarranted authorship recognition, they do not apply in the case of this study since there is only one author for this study which is classified as a doctoral dissertation thesis to the single education facility of the University of the West of Scotland. It is also considered to be impossible to split this thesis work as it requires conduction involving a long period of time, resources and thorough supervision from the university.

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, descriptive results on the data background are presented firstly, followed by the results derived from the correlation matrix. Subsequently, ANOVA and multiple regression will be run and reported associating results. Hypotheses will be assessed with t-statistics in order to deliver conclusions on whether one is retained or rejected. In addition, statistics on Cronbach's alpha will be further presented to demonstrate the reliability of the data. In addition, testing on OLS assumptions including linearity, heteroscedasticity, normal distribution and multicollinearity is conducted to confirm the robustness of the regression model.

4.2. DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 4.1 shows the summary of the sample's demographic data which consists of seven categories: age, gender, educational level, marital status, ethnicity, employment status and annual income. Firstly, the age category was separated into seven groups: over 18, 18 to 24, 25 to 34, 35 to 44, 45 to 54, 55 to 64 and over 64 years of age. The age group which accounted for the highest proportion is 18 to 24, representing 48.78% of the total sample. The second highest group is participants aged between 25 and 34, comprising 36.99% of the whole sample. Investors in the age range of 35 to 44 and 45 to 54 constitute for much lower percentages which are 11.38% and 2.44% respectively. There is only one investor recorded for the age group between 55 and 64 among all 246 survey respondents which produces the result of 0.41%. Apart from the mentioned age range, there were no participants under the age of 18 or over 65. It can be clearly seen that the survey sample consists of younger investors, particularly ranging from 18 to 34.

This is in line with Senkardes and Akadur (2021), and IPSOS (2022). Regarding the gender context, the results indicate a combination of 147 male investors and 92 female investors, with 7 participants preferring not to reveal their gender. Percentile-wise, male investors make up for 59.76% of the sample whereas 37.4% are female investors. Senkardes and Adakur (2021) also proposed similar results based on their survey on cryptocurrency investors. In addition, the Crypto Report from Morning Consult (2022) found that men are significantly more dominant than women in terms of holding and investing in the cryptocurrency market. The report further suggests millennials showed much stronger interests and involvement with cryptocurrency, compared to baby boomers.

In terms of educational level, the survey results demonstrate most surveyed crypto investors are highly educated at least with a bachelor degree. In particular, participants graduated with an undergraduate degree account for 44.72% of the total sample. Moreover, investors who were awarded with a masters and a doctorate represent 20.33% and 3.66% respectively. Apart from that, approximately of the whole sample are retail investors with a high school degree or less.

Among 246 survey respondents, 193 people are reported to be single which make up for 78.46% whereas 17.89% of the sample are married; the rest of the participants (3.66%) are listed to be either separated, divorced or widowed. The large frequency of single participants can be resonated by a high fraction of younger generation investors within the sample. Regarding ethnicity, the majority of the respondents are white and cover 62.20% of the sample. Black, African, Caribbean or Black British are recorded to be the second most dominant ethnicity but with a much lower proportion (14.63%). Asian or Asian British further only make up approximately 10.57% of the sample, followed by mixed/multiple ethnicity and other ethnic groups with around 6% for each group.

For employment status, 117 survey participants responded to be in full time employment which account for the majority with 47.56% of the total sample. Nearly 30% listed their occupation to be students and just over 14% to be in part time employment. Other sub-groups which are not currently employed, retired and disabled (not able to work) make up much lower proportions of 7.32%, 0.41% and 1.22% respectively.

Lastly, the sample was asked to match themselves with the closest annual income bracket. The presented five sub-groups for annual income were less than £20,000, £20,000-£49,999, £50,000-£99,999, £100,000-£149,999 and over £150,000. More than half of the sample (54.07%) earn less than £20,000 whereas the two higher income brackets £20,000-£49,999 and £50,000-£99,999 constitute 30.08% and 11.38% of the whole sample, respectively.

Title	Category	Number	Percentage
Age	Under 18	0	0.00%
	18-24	120	48.78%
	25-34	91	36.99%
	35-44	28	11.38%
	45-54	6	2.44%
	55-64	1	0.41%
	Over 65	0	0.00%
Gender	Male	147	59.76%
	Female	92	37.40%
	Prefer not to say	7	2.85%

Education	Less than high school degree	4	1.63%
	Highschool or equivalent	73	29.67%
	BSc/BA	110	44.72%
	MSc/MA	50	20.33%
	PhD. Doctorate of equivalent	9	3.66%
<hr/>			
Marital status	Married	44	17.89%
	Separated	3	1.22%
	Divorced	3	1.22%
	Widowed	3	1.22%
	Single	193	78.46%
<hr/>			
Ethnicity	White	153	62.20%
	Asian or Asian British	26	10.57%
	Black, African, Caribbean or Black British	36	14.63%
	Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups	15	6.10%
	Other ethnic group	16	6.50%
<hr/>			
Employment status	Full time	117	47.56%
	Part time	35	14.23%
	Not currently employed	18	7.32%
	Student	72	29.27%
	Retired	1	0.41%

	Disabled, not able to work	3	1.22%
Annual income	< £20,000	133	54.07%
	£20,000-£49,999	74	30.08%
	£50,000-£99,999	28	11.38%
	£100,000-£149,999	9	3.66%
	> £150,000	2	0.81%

Table 4.1. Demographic results

The figure 4.1 represents the answers with their constitutions to the question: what is the biggest motivation of yours to invest in the cryptocurrency market. The two options presented to the survey respondents are either to increase wealth or based on their belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth. The results show that 78% of the survey sample responded that increasing wealth and capital gain is their biggest motivation. On the other hand, only 22% of the participants recorded their answers to be because of their belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth. It can be made into awareness that investors participating in the cryptocurrency market might hold both types of motivation. However, the survey collected the feedback of what they value significantly more.

Figure 4.1. Motivations of cryptocurrency investors

The figure 4.2 represents how often survey investors trade with cryptocurrencies and the choices are divided into 4 groups: daily, weekly, monthly and once every few months. 39% of the sampled investors responded that they invest in cryptocurrency monthly. A slightly lower percentage of 36% belongs to respondents who trade cryptocurrency once every few months. The third highest percentage is 17%, representing weekly trading investors. The lowest proportion (8%) falls into traders and investors who do daily executions. It can be considered that the majority of surveyed investors trade less frequently or they might hold their investments in length of month(s).

Figure 4.2. The frequency of crypto investors trading cryptocurrency

The figure 4.3 illustrates the distribution of how many years investors have participated in trading and investments. As stated in the question, the question does not refer to investing experience only within the cryptocurrency market, but also in other markets such as the foreign exchange and equity market. It can be observed that more than half (56%) of the sample has trading experience of 1 year or less. While approximately one third (33%) of the surveyed investors acquire 1 to 3 years of trading experience, more experienced traders with over 3 years account for 11% among 246 observations.

Figure 4.3. How many years of trading experience do you have (including FX, Equity, etc)

As can be seen in figure 4.4, the pie chart demonstrated the portions for five different spending brackets for how much monthly capital do surveyed investors normally trade with, exclusively for cryptocurrency market only. The five suggested spending ranges are less than £500, £500 to £999, £1,000 to £4,999, £5,000 to £9,999 and over £10,000. A significant amount, 177 out of 246, of investors spend less than £500 a month on cryptocurrency investments. That accounted for 72% of the whole sample. For the higher spending bracket £500-£999, the results reflect around 16% while reasonably lower distributions belong to other higher monthly trading amount brackets. In particular, 8% represent investors trading between £1,000 and £4,999 a month and 2% who trade the volume between £5,000 and £9,999 a month. Similar result of 2% is recorded for crypto investors who use more than £10,000 a month in executing trades.

Figure 4.4. How much monthly capital do you normally trade with?

As discussed previously within the literature review of the cryptocurrency market, BTC and ETH are the two dominant coins and own one of the biggest cryptocurrencies by market capitalisation as of March 20th 2022. Beside BTC and ETH, several altcoins which are in the top list of the industry were also included in the survey. They are CARDANO (ADA), CHAINLINK (LINK), DOGECOIN (DOGE), RIPPLE (XRP), SOLANA (SOL), POLKADOT (DOT), AVALANCHE (AVAX), FANTOM (FTM), LITCOIN (LTC), TERRA (LUNA), POLYGON (MATIC), COSMO (ATOM), BINANCE COIN (BNB), DECENTRALAND (MANA) and CRYPTO.COM COIN (CRO). The results show that Bitcoin and Ethereum remain to be the most traded cryptocurrencies among the presented 17 coins, with approximately 74% and 63% of the sample respectively. The third most traded coin is rewarded to XRP, representing 22% of the surveyed respondents. Apart from that, less traded cryptocurrencies with the number of investors between 18 and 46 out of the whole sample are ADA, LINK, DOGE, SOL, DOT, AVAX, LTC, LUNA, MATIC, BNB and CRO. The three least traded coins with less than 10 participated investors out of 246 are FTM, ATOM and MANA.

Figure 4.5. What are the crypto securities you often trade with?

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 4.2 represents the main descriptive statistics for each statement for crypto investment performance and each explanatory variable, together with the overall figures for each of them. To measure crypto investment performance, the author adopts seven statements as discussed previously from several sources in the methodology chapter. The answers for the first, second and third statements can be said to be collected from investors' objective perspective and the rest to be considered from a subjective perspective. As can be viewed in table 4.2, all first three items have slightly lower mean compared to the rest of the measurement items of crypto investment performance. This implies that by evaluating opinions, the response for investment satisfactions are more positive than that of returns on investments.

The first item to measure overconfidence among cryptocurrency investors is *"I am an experienced trader"* and returns a mean of 2.374 together with a standard deviation of

1.0294. This item has the lowest mean, median and mode compared to the other two items of overconfidence measurement, which indicates that the crypto investors participated in the survey do not confidently consider themselves equipped with enormous trading and investing experience. However, the second item within this measurement scale *“My forecast on market is better than that of my friends and relatives”* has the highest mean and lowest standard deviation, which are 2.9065 and 1.0239, respectively. This implies that the overconfidence bias might mostly come from the crypto investors’ belief in their own ability to outperform their peers. Overall, the measure for overconfidence has a mean of 2.6775 and a standard deviation of 0.8351, illustrating an average effect on crypto investment performance.

From the loss aversion perspective, the second item of the measurement *“I feel nervous when my holdings lose value”* presents with the highest mean of 3.3211 and a standard deviation of 1.1529. This suggests that crypto investors might feel more emotional when experiencing a negative unrealised loss on their investments. Thus, this can potentially cause irrational decisions such as closing their positions too soon. The recorded mode and median for this item were both 4, hence, this indicates that crypto investors in the sample mostly agree on this statement altogether. In addition, the first item *“I am more concerned about a loss in my position than missing a substantial gain”* returns a slightly smaller mean of 3.2967 with a standard deviation of 1.0524. It also has both the value of median and mode to be 4, thus, the sample for this paper generally agrees with this statement. The overall score of mean for loss aversion is 3.2327 with a standard deviation of 0.7619, signalling that loss aversion has an average impact on crypto investment performance.

Regarding regret aversion, all three items to measure this variable have the mode of 4 which means that they mostly agree with these statements. It is notable that the second statement *“I will stick to my investments rather than making new ones with higher returns but also with big risks”* has the highest mean of 3.3740 and a standard deviation of 0.9205. In addition, this item also has a minimum score of 2. It is the only item among all items which does not have “strongly disagree” with the recorded answers. This result

expresses that the crypto investors in the sample could generally be risk averse. The overall mean for regret aversion returns a value of 3.3062 and a standard deviation of 0.7446, indicating an average influence on crypto investment performance.

The results on the mean and standard deviation recorded for the first item of anchoring *“I am unlikely to buy a coin if it was more expensive than last year”* are 2.8455 and 0.9692, respectively. This item has the lowest score of mean and value of mode to be 2. This indicates that the sample mostly disagrees with this statement. In other words, if anchoring bias has a significant impact on investment performance, this will not potentially be the item to drive the bias. On the other hand, the second item *“I use the coin’s purchase price as a reference point for trade”* and third item *“I am likely to sell my coin after the price hits recent year high”* for anchoring measurement have approximately similar mean of 3.5122 and 3.5 and standard deviations of 0.8701 and 0.9551, respectively. These results demonstrate a firm agreement amongst the sample’s crypto investors on these items. This means that by anchoring at a crypto coin’s buying price and recent year high’s value could have an impact on cryptocurrency investment performance. The overall mean for anchoring is recorded to be 3.2859 with the standard deviation of 0.5993, indicating a generally average influence on crypto investment performance.

From the herding perspective, the first item *“I tend to follow investment suggestion of the majority, rather than the opposition of a few”* and the second item *“I tend to increase the sum of my crypto holding if the recent market trading volume is higher than usual”* returned roughly similar scores of mean which are 3.1463 and 3.2195, accordingly. The results also present similar values of standard deviation of 0.9141 and 0.9217, respectively. Both of the items obtained the mode of 4, demonstrating that the majority of the sample agree with these statements. This illustrates by following other investors’ moves and trading volume could likely impact cryptocurrency investment performance if herding is found to be statistically significant. The overall mean and standard deviation of herding are recorded to be 3.1829 and 0.7292, respectively. This result indicates an average role on impacting crypto investors’ performance.

The first item to measure the availability bias *“I prefer to buy coins on the days when the value of BTC increases”* and the second item *“If I heard from a friend about a coin that achieved high returns, I would buy it”* present a mean of 3.0610 and 2.9553 as well as a standard deviation of 1.0303 and 1.0031, all respectively. It is further notable that the mode for the first item is 4 while it is 2 for the second item. In other words, the surveyed crypto investors mostly agree that their decision to buy a coin depends more on the value fluctuation of a coin, rather than depending on a suggestion of a peer. The overall mean and standard deviation for availability bias is 3.0081 and 0.7824, accordingly, suggesting an average impact on crypto investment performance.

Lastly of all behavioural biases is mental accounting. The second measurement item *“I tend to treat each asset of my investment portfolio differently”* and the third *“I hesitate selling coins that recently fell in price but generated high returns in the past”* received relatively high mean values of 3.4756 and 3.4715, respectively. The results further return the standard deviation for these items of 0.8651 and 0.9504, accordingly. This indicates that the surveyed sample agree that they might be prone to mental accounting. However, the first statement *“I do not care about the performance of my investment portfolio as a whole but I care about the return of each asset separately”* receives a smaller value of mean (3.0650) and 3 for both median and mode. The overall mean for the mental accounting bias is 3.3374 and a standard deviation of 0.7149, indicating an average influence on crypto investment performance.

Regarding the motivation variable, it receives a mean of 0.2154 and the value of median and mode to be both 0, suggesting the majority of the sample invest in the cryptocurrency market is mostly to generate more wealth, rather than a belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth. Since this is a dummy variable, a regression analysis is crucial for the purpose of finding its role on crypto investment performance. Furthermore, the descriptive results suggest a level of average influence to crypto investment performance by the independent variables. Hence, a regression analysis is essential for further assessment.

Item/Variable	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Min	Max
IP1	2.8415	3	4	1.0782	1	5
IP2	2.6220	3	2	1.0989	1	5
IP3	2.8333	3	3	1.0845	1	5
IP4	3.3780	4	4	1.0017	1	5
IP5	3.1423	3	4	1.0021	1	5
IP6	3.2480	3	3	0.8896	1	5
IP7	3.1667	3	4	0.9173	1	5
<i>Crypto investors' performance</i>	3.0331	3.142857	3.428571	0.7041	1	5
OC1	2.3740	2	2	1.0294	1	5
OC2	2.9065	3	3	1.0239	1	5
OC3	2.7520	3	2	1.0611	1	5
<i>Overconfidence</i>	2.6775	2.66667	2	0.8351	1	5
LA1	3.2967	4	4	1.0524	1	5
LA2	3.3211	4	4	1.1529	1	5
LA3	3.1870	3	4	1.2542	1	5
LA4	3.1260	3	3	1.0043	1	5

Loss Aversion	3.2327	3.25	3.25	0.7619	1	5
RA1	3.2642	3	4	0.9558	1	5
RA2	3.3740	4	4	0.9205	2	5
RA3	3.2805	3.5	4	1.0607	1	5
Regret Aversion	3.3062	3.3333	3.6667	0.7446	1.3333	5
AC1	2.8455	3	2	0.9692	1	5
AC2	3.5122	4	4	0.8701	1	5
AC3	3.5000	4	4	0.9551	1	5
Anchoring	3.2859	3.3333	3.3333	0.5993	1.3333	5
HRD1	3.1463	3	4	0.9141	1	5
HRD2	3.2195	3	4	0.9217	1	5
Herding	3.1829	3	3	0.7292	1	5
AV1	3.0610	3	4	1.0303	1	5
AV2	2.9553	3	2	1.0031	1	5
Availability	3.0081	3	3	0.7824	1	5
MA1	3.0650	3	3	0.7824	1	5
MA2	3.4756	4	4	0.8651	1	5
MA3	3.4715	4	4	0.9504	1	5

<i>Mental accounting</i>	<i>3.3374</i>	<i>3.3333</i>	<i>3.6667</i>	<i>0.7149</i>	<i>1.3333</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>Motivation</i>	<i>0.2154</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0.4120</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1</i>

Table 4.2. Summary table of items and variables

FURTHER INSIGHTS

The tool to collect survey data for this research was Microsoft Forms, which offered insights features about the responses (Microsoft, n.d.). By using this tool, the author was able to extract a number of insights about the collected data which are presented in figure 4.6, 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9. In summary, they are as below:

- Investors, who have up to one year of trading experiences and represent 57% of the whole sample, marked:
 - 84% of them responded to have increasing wealth as their biggest investing motivation
 - 68% of them answered “white” for the ethnicity
 - 85% of them spent up to £500 on their monthly trading capital
- 94% of the investors within 18 - 24 years of age category are single
- The majority of single investors in terms of marital status are white (63%) and have “increasing wealth” as their biggest investing motivation in cryptocurrency (78%)

57% of people answered **Up to 1 year** for this question, and the majority answered "**Increase wealth**" for Question 2.

Figure 4.6. Extracted insight 1

49% of people answered **18-24** for this question, and the majority answered "**Single**" for Question 15.

Figure 4.7. Extracted insight 2

79% of people answered **Single** for this question, and the majority answered "**White**" for Question 16.

Figure 4.8. Extracted insight 3

79% of people answered **Single** for this question, and the majority answered "**Increase wealth**" for Question 2.

Figure 4.9. Extracted insight 4

4.3. CORRELATION MATRIX

According to Pham-Gia and Choulakian (2014), it is vital to consider correlation matrix in multivariate analysis since it can apprehend duo-relationship degree between different component pairs. They can be demonstrated in a row-by-column arrangement with associated correlation coefficients between each pair (Hadd and Rodgers, 2020). The correlation coefficients are then analysed by the strength of value and their direction. A high correlation value implies that the variable pair assesses similar characteristics to one another. However, if that value holds a positive sign, this means that they implement each other in the same direction and the opposite direction if vice versa. In the case of low correlation between the two components, they may assess unrelated aspects or may not be accurately defined. Akoglu (2018) stated that correlation coefficients can range between -1 and +1; -1 indicates perfect negative correlation while +1 indicates perfect positive correlation. Correlation coefficient equal to 0 means the component pair does not relate at all to one another (Akoglu, 2018). In terms of strength classification, Dancey and Reidy (2007) suggest coefficient values above 0.7 are considered to be strong, 0.4 and 0.6 to be moderate and less than 0.4 is weak.

Recalling from the research methodology chapter, the independent variables for the constructed OLS regression model are overconfidence (OC), loss aversion (LA), regret aversion (RA), anchoring (AC), herding (HRD), availability (AV), mental accounting (MA) and motive (short for motivations). Table 4.2 illustrates the correlation matrix for these eight independent variables and the dependent variable crypto investment performance of the regression model. As can be seen in the table, most variable pairs are weakly correlated apart from the loss aversion and regret aversion pair. They hold a correlation coefficient value of 0.5166 which accounts for a positively moderate correlation. This is in line with the correlation analysis findings from Shafqat and Malik (2021), and Awais and Estes (2019).

	<i>MOTIV</i>	<i>OC</i>	<i>LA</i>	<i>RA</i>	<i>AC</i>	<i>HRD</i>	<i>AV</i>	<i>MA</i>	<i>IP</i>
<i>MOTIV</i>	1.0000								
<i>OC</i>	0.2107	1.0000							
<i>LA</i>	-0.2742	-0.1029	1.0000						
<i>RA</i>	-0.2781	-0.3482	0.5166	1.0000					
<i>AC</i>	-0.1954	-0.0497	0.2902	0.3162	1.0000				
<i>HRD</i>	-0.1521	-0.0301	0.2371	0.2698	0.2488	1.0000			
<i>AV</i>	-0.0498	-0.0282	0.3314	0.3110	0.2228	0.2746	1.0000		
<i>MA</i>	-0.0677	0.0349	0.0813	0.1229	0.1635	0.2478	0.0170	1.0000	
<i>IP</i>	0.2668	0.4476	-0.0796	-0.1903	-0.0953	0.1006	0.1165	0.1225	1.0000

Table 4.3. Correlation matrix between behavioural factors

4.4. REGRESSION MODEL

As discussed previously, the seven behavioural factors namely overconfidence, loss aversion, regret aversion, anchoring, herding, availability, mental accounting as well as the dummy variable *motiv_* were selected as independent variables to perform the OLS regression model and predict investment outcomes. The model with a total of 246 observations was regressed with the statistics software STATA and returned the results which can be seen in table 4.4 and 4.5. The correlation coefficients given in table 4.4 suggest the following fitted model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (IO_{fitted})^2 &= (-0.2866061) + 2.044026 * OC_i + (-0.1559678) * LA_i \\
 &+ (-0.2118844) * RA_i + (-0.6097613) * AC_i + 0.1690023 * HRD_i \\
 &+ 0.8039743 * AV_i + 0.8769319 * MA_i + 1.857366 * MOTIV_i + \varepsilon_i
 \end{aligned}$$

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE (ANOVA)

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	246
Model	1323.37671	8	165.422089	F(8, 237)	=	13.61
Residual	2879.62399	237	12.1503122	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.3149
				Adj R-squared	=	0.2917
Total	4203.0007	245	17.1551049	Root MSE	=	3.4857

Table 4.4. Analysis of variance

The results on analysis of variance of the overall model is reported in table 4.3. As can be seen in the table, the R-squared value is 0.3149 which implies approximately 31.49% of the investment outcome's variations can be explained by the independent variables. In addition, the adjusted R-squared equals 0.2917, meaning roughly 29.17% of the response variable's changes are defined by regressors that have actual effect on the

dependent variable. Furthermore, the results also provide values of F-statistics and its p-value which examine the overall significant level of the regression's correlation coefficients. The model returns the value of 13.61 for the F-statistics and 0.0000 for p-value. Since p-value is smaller than 5%, the null hypothesis of overall insignificance is rejected and the model's coefficients are jointly significant. In other words, all eight explanatory variables can critically affect the dependent variable i.e., investment outcome. Above all, the ANOVA results suggest this model is a good fit for the data.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

sq_ip	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
oc	2.044026	.2910612	7.02	0.000	1.470629	2.617424
la	-.1559678	.3585838	-0.43	0.664	-.8623865	.5504509
ra	-.2118844	.3913535	-0.54	0.589	-.9828603	.5590914
ac	-.6097613	.4076988	-1.50	0.136	-1.412938	.1934152
hrd	.6190023	.3378544	1.83	0.068	-.046579	1.284584
av	.8039743	.315876	2.55	0.012	.1816911	1.426258
ma	.8769319	.3256094	2.69	0.008	.2354736	1.51839
motiv_	1.857366	.5826286	3.19	0.002	.7095733	3.005158
_cons	-.2866061	2.023068	-0.14	0.887	-4.272098	3.698886

Table 4.5. Regression analysis

The model is regressed with eight independent variables namely overconfidence, loss aversion, regret aversion, anchoring, herding, availability, mental accounting and motivations towards the dependent variable which is investment performance. The results are returned in table 4.4 presenting the correlation coefficients, standard errors, t-test, p-value and the 95% confidence interval for each regressor. As explained in the previous chapter, the transformation on the predicted variable was performed in order for the error terms to pass the normality test.

OVERCONFIDENCE (OC)

According to table 4.4, the correlation coefficient for variable “overconfidence” is 2.044026 with t-test equals 7.02 ($p=0.000$). These outputs suggest “overconfidence” has a significant impact on investment performance at all levels of confidence since p-value for t-test is too small and less than 0.01. The positive coefficient further indicates that “overconfidence” has a positive causal relationship with investment outcome. That is to say, increased levels of overconfidence may lead to more future success in cryptocurrency investing.

Since the response variable was squared in the suggested model, the author attempts to interpret the change in the dependent variable based on any independent variable as follows.

In a simple function with squared dependent variable where $Y^2 = \alpha + \beta_1 * X + \beta_2 * Z$, assessing how a change in X would affect the change in Y might preferably Z to be constant or unchanged. With this assumption taken into account and to find out derivatives of Y over X, the following process shall be conducted.

$$\text{Let } Y^* = Y^2 \text{ and variable } Z \text{ remains constant, } \frac{d(Y^*)}{d(X)} = 2 * Y * \frac{d(Y)}{d(X)} = \beta_1$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \frac{d(Y)}{d(X)} = \frac{\beta_1}{2 * Y}$$

Due to the derivative result above, the suggested regression model will indicate non-linear relationships between all independent variables and the dependent variable.

Regarding the fitted regression model presented above for this thesis and assuming that other independent variable remains constant, the change in one unit of variable “overconfidence” will give the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(OC)} = \frac{\beta_1}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{2.044026}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = 1.022013 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

Since a function of IO_{fitted} is included in the change value, it cannot be constant and will rely on the particular set of all other independent variables’ values in order to calculate a specific number.

Based on the regression results presented above, the correlation coefficient for “overconfidence” is 2.044026. To apply the more simplified method into the suggested fitted regression model and with respect to nil changes/constant in any other independent variables (i.e. motivation, loss aversion, regret aversion, availability, anchoring, herding and mental accounting), an unit change in the level of “overconfidence” will lead to a change of $1.022013 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$ in the dependent variable investment performance.

Overall, the regression result on overconfidence leads to the retention of H1, that overconfidence has a significantly positive impact on crypto investment performance. This is in opposition to Syarkani and Tristnato (2022).

LOSS AVERSION (LA)

The regression analysis results in table 4.4 presents the correlation coefficient to be -0.1559678. In addition, the given t-test and p-value are -0.43 and 0.664 respectively. Firstly, the coefficient correlation for variable “loss aversion” is less than 0, indicating a negative relationship with the regressed variable “investment performance”. Secondly, a p-value of 0.664 demonstrates that “loss aversion” is not statistically significant at all levels of confidence (1%, 5% and 10%).

Although the result recommends an insignificant effect of “loss aversion” on “crypto investment performance”, a change in one unit of “loss aversion” would lead to the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(LA)} = \frac{\beta_2}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{-0.1559678}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = (-0.07798) * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

The interpretation on the regressed result of “loss aversion” therefore suggests the retention of the null hypothesis H2 where loss aversion has an insignificant and negative impact on crypto investment performance.

REGRET AVERSION (RA)

For variable “regret aversion”, the regression model returns the value for correlation coefficient of -0.2118844. This implies regret aversion is negatively correlated with crypto investment performance. In addition, the t-test and p-value are given in table 4.4 as -0.54 and 0.389 accordingly, indicating that the predictor “regret aversion” is not statistically significant at any levels of confidence.

However, a change in one unit of “regret aversion” would result in the change of “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(RA)} = \frac{\beta_3}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{-0.2118844}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = (-0.1059422) * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

Similarly to the variable “loss aversion”, the regression results on “regret aversion” demonstrate that the null hypothesis of H3 shall not be rejected, thus, regret aversion has an insignificant and negative effect on crypto investment performance.

ANCHORING (AC)

According to table 4.4, the correlation coefficient for variable “anchoring” is -0.6097613, recommending a contradictory relationship with dependent variable “investment performance”. Moreover, the table also displays the t-test of -1.50 and p-value of 0.136 for variable “anchoring”. Since the p-value is above 0.1, the predictor “anchoring” is not statistically significant at all levels of confidence.

In addition, an attempt to explain the corresponding changes between “anchoring” and “investment performance” is constituted. A change in one unit of the regressor “anchoring” will lead to the change in the regressed variable “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(AC)} = \frac{\beta_4}{2*IO_{fitted}} = \frac{-0.6097613}{2*IO_{fitted}} = (-0.30488) * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

The results presented above therefore illustrate that the null hypothesis of H3 should be retained, meaning anchoring has an insignificant and negative influence on crypto investment performance.

HERDING (HRD)

As can be seen in table 4.4, the correlation coefficient for variable “herding” returns the value of 0.6190023 with t-test and p-value equal to 1.83 and 0.068 respectively. These results propose that herding has a positive relationship with crypto investors’ investment performance; however, since its p-value is above 0.05 and less than 0.1, it only has a statistically significant influence at 10% level of confidence and not at 1% as well as 5%. This indicates actions followed with other investors could bring better performance to cryptocurrency investments.

If an assumption of non-changes in the values of other predictors and similar derivative function to the above is conducted, the change in one unit of variable “herding” will lead to the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(HRD)} = \frac{\beta_5}{2*IO_{fitted}} = \frac{0.6190023}{2*IO_{fitted}} = 0.3456 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

To conclude on the independent variable “herding”, it has a statistically positive influence on crypto investment performance at 10%. The attempted interpretation for a change in one unit of variable “herding” is that it will lead to a change of $0.3456 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$ of crypto investment performance. Hence, the null hypothesis of H5 is rejected, suggesting herding has a positively considerable impact on crypto investment performance.

The result on herding behaviour is consistent with Boxer and Thompson (2020) where they also found positive influence of herding towards crypto purchasing behaviours. It is also in line with Gupta and Roubaud (2018) when the rolling window model is applied. In addition, this result is further in line with Al-mansour (2020).

AVAILABILITY (AV)

According to table 4.4, the correlation coefficient, t-test and p-value for the predictor “availability” returns the value of 0.8039743, 2.55 and 0.012 respectively. Since the correlation coefficient of “availability” is positive, there is a positive causal relationship between “availability” and “investment performance”. Moreover, a p-value of 0.012 indicates that this independent variable is statistically significant at 5% and 10% level, but not at 1% level. Therefore, it can be understood that the predictor “availability”

could generate and improve financial gain and/or investment satisfactions in cryptocurrency investing.

In terms of changes regarding the regression model, one unit change of “availability” will lead to the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(AV)} = \frac{\beta_6}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{0.8039743}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = 0.40199 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

Due to the results presented above, since “availability” is statistically significant, the null hypothesis of H6 is rejected. In particular, availability has a remarkable positive influence on cryptocurrency investment performance.

MENTAL ACCOUNTING (MA)

By further referring to table 4.4, the correlation coefficient for the regressor “mental accounting” is 0.8769319. This recommends a positive correlation between “mental accounting” and “investment performance”. The t-test and p-value for “mental accounting” were calculated to be 2.69 and 0.008, accordingly. As 0.008 is less than 0.01, the predictor “mental accounting” is statistically significant at all levels. A positive and significant result on mental accounting suggests that by being prone to this bias, crypto investors might experience good investing experience and increase in financial wealth in the cryptocurrency market.

By proceeding with similar steps on the derivative function, the change in one unit of variable “mental accounting” will lead to the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(MA)} = \frac{\beta_7}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{0.8769319}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = 0.438466 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

In summary with respect to the results on the regressor “mental accounting”, it is positively significant at all levels and an increase of $0.438466 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$ in the dependent variable “investment performance” would follow an unit increase in mental accounting. Hence, the null hypothesis of H7 is rejected, meaning that mental accounting has a considerable impact on crypto investment performance.

MOTIVATION (MOTIV)

The last independent variable to be considered is “motivation”, marked as *motiv_* in the regression model. Unlike the behavioural factor variables above, “motivation” is a binary dummy variable whereas 0 indicates the investing motivation in line with increasing wealth only and 1 implies the investing motivation solely of belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth.

As can be seen in table 4.4, the correlation coefficient for the predictor “motivation” is 1.857366. This suggests that there is a positive relationship between motivation and investment performance. Furthermore, the t-test and p-value for the variable is given as 3.19 and 0.002 respectively. Due to such a small figure of the p-value, the regressor “motivation” can be said to be statistically significant at all levels of confidence. This means that investors who are motivated with the belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth have more investing success than investors who solely want to achieve financial gains.

In terms of the derivative function, by having the *motiv_* value equals to 1 comparing to 0 will result in the change in “investment performance” of:

$$\frac{d(IP)}{d(MOTIV)} = \frac{\beta_8}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = \frac{1.857366}{2 * IO_{fitted}} = 0.92868 * \frac{1}{IO_{fitted}}$$

As explained above, the change still includes the function of IO_{fitted} means that the change value would really depend on the set of any other independent variables, in order to generate a specific numerical value.

In summary, it can be concluded that the regressor “motivation” has a statistically significant positive influence on investment performance. Hence, the null hypothesis of H8 is rejected.

SUMMARY

A retention of null hypothesis means that there is no statistically significant influence of a behavioural bias to the investors’ performance within the cryptocurrency market. Contradictory, a rejection of null hypothesis means otherwise where there is a statistically significant impact. According to the results from running the multiple regression analysis with the seven behavioural biases and the motivation variable, the rejected hypotheses are hypothesis 1, hypothesis 5, hypothesis 6, hypothesis 7 and hypothesis 8. In other words, behavioural biases namely overconfidence, herding, availability, mental accounting together with the motivation variable are found to have statistically significant impact on the crypto investors’ performance.

On the other hand, the null hypothesis regarding hypothesis 2, hypothesis 3 and hypothesis 4 are retained. This demonstrates that behavioural biases including loss aversion, regret aversion and anchoring are reported to not provide any significant

influence on the performance of crypto investors in the sample. A summary table for the retention and rejection of the proposed hypotheses can be regarded below.

Variable	Sig at 1%	Sig at 5%	Sig at 10%	Not sig	Reject null hypothesis? (Yes/No)
OC	x				Yes (H1)
LA				x	No (H2)
RA				x	No (H3)
AC				x	No (H4)
HRD			x		Yes (H5)
AV		x			Yes (H6)
MA	x				Yes (H7)
MOTIV	x				Yes (H8)

Table 4.6. Summary table of retained/rejected hypotheses

In the phase of observing whether the results of this thesis are consistent or inconsistent with previous research, the author could only find related findings with overconfidence and herding. This is due to the remarkable lack of prior papers which hypothesise similar propositions with this research.

However, by referring to the literature review, there has been one research providing findings regarding prospect theory and heuristic influences as a whole to the crypto investors' performance. The Al-mansour (2020) reported that both prospect theory and heuristics bias have a statistically significant impact towards crypto investors' performance. This might indicate in some ways that any particular biases categorised within prospect theory and heuristics can potentially have an impact on the performance of crypto investors.

CRONBACH'S ALPHA

As mentioned in the methodology chapter, Cronbach's alpha is chosen to examine the inter-correlation between each statement that have previously been categorised in groups of behavioural bias and provided to respondents in the questionnaire. Several scholars have indicated the acceptable score for the Cronbach's alpha for reliability. Cortina (1993), Shemwell, Chase and Schwart (2015) and Barbera, Naibert, Komperda and Pentecost (2020) stated that a score of 0.7 is generally appropriate, however, the higher is more desirable. Taber (2018) and Griethuijsen et al. (2014) suggested a lower score of around 0.6 is also considered to be moderate inter-correlation, hence, 0.6 is still adequate.

Amongst all independent variables, the motivation variable is excluded from testing for reliability since it is a dummy variable. Accordingly, all seven behavioural biases are then tested with Cronbach's alpha. In addition, the dependent variable crypto investment outcome/performance was measured with 7 items. Hence, this variable shall be also included to be tested with Cronbach's alpha. The results of the scores for this study are run with the software STATA and the results could be seen below.

Behavioural biases	Cronbach's alpha score
--------------------	------------------------

Overconfidence	0.7271
Loss aversion	0.6130
Regret aversion	0.6323
Anchoring	0.6133
Herding	0.6895
Availability	0.6171
Mental accounting	0.6675
Crypto investment performance	0.8215

Table 4.7. Cronbach's alpha score

As can be viewed in table 4.6, all Cronbach's alpha scores for the behavioural biases are above 0.6. The lowest score is 0.6130 associated with the loss aversion bias whereas the highest score of 0.8215 belongs to the dependent variable crypto investment performance. Amongst all variables, the overconfidence bias and crypto investment performance are above 0.7 which show strongest correlation between all items being tested. Overall, with all scores above 0.6 which satisfy the suggestions proposed by Taber (2018) and Griethujisen et al. (2014), it can be said that the data of this paper passes the reliability test with Cronbach's alpha.

. alpha oc1_ oc2_ oc3_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.5070903**
Number of items in the scale: **3**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.7271**

. alpha la1_ la2_ la3_ la4_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.3559068**
Number of items in the scale: **4**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6130**

. alpha ra1_ ra2_ ra3_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.3505503**
Number of items in the scale: **3**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6323**

. alpha ac1_ ac2_ ac3_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.3343344**
Number of items in the scale: **3**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6133**

. alpha hrd1_ hrd2_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.5831425**
Number of items in the scale: **2**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6895**

. alpha av1_ av2_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.5142857**
Number of items in the scale: **2**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6171**

. alpha ma1_ ma2_ ma3_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.3918699**
Number of items in the scale: **3**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.6675**

. alpha return_xtrainc_breturn_buyord_sellord_assetp_tv_

Test scale = mean(unstandardized items)

Average interitem covariance: **.407295**
Number of items in the scale: **7**
Scale reliability coefficient: **0.8215**

NORMAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESIDUALS TEST

As explained above, one of the assumptions for a reliable and accurate regression model is to assure the residuals to obtain a normal distribution. Tabachnick and Fidell (2006) explained the assumption of normality is violated with kurtosis when the peak of the distribution outlier can be seen to be out of shape or the tails to be slimmer or heavier. To test this, the author uses the skewness-kurtosis test run by the software STATA. The result therefore is presented below.

The result shows that the prob>chi2 is 0.8929 is the p-value for the test. Since this value is much higher than 0.05, the hypothesis of a normal distribution is retained. In other words, the residuals of the proposed regression model are normally distributed. Another point to be aware of is that the original dependent variable of the proposed regression model has been squared in order to have this assumption satisfied. Therefore, it is designated to have the following result for the skewness-kurtosis test.

```
. sktest resid
```

Skewness/Kurtosis tests for Normality					
Variable	Obs	Pr(Skewness)	Pr(Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	joint Prob>chi2
resid	246	0.9266	0.6405	0.23	0.8929

HOMOSCEDASTICITY TEST

Homoscedasticity in the error terms means that their associated variance is constant (Jarque and Bera, 1980). In other words, when the estimated value of the dependent variable changes, there is little to no noise in terms of residual disturbance. Heteroscedasticity is the opposite of homoscedasticity and means the variance of the error terms is not constant.

To test for homoscedasticity/heteroscedasticity, the author adopts the Breusch-Pagan test as suggested previously in the methodology chapter. The result returned from STATA can be seen as below.

```

. hettest resid

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
Ho: Constant variance
Variables: resid

chi2(1)      =      0.02
Prob > chi2  =      0.8766

```

The prob>chi2 for the chi squared test is 0.8766 which is significantly higher than 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis of homoscedasticity is retained. In other words, the residuals for the regression model is homoscedastic which satisfies the one of the assumptions of a reliable and an accurate model.

MULTICOLLINEARITY TEST

Multicollinearity can affect the reliability and wrongful estimation of a model or cause skewness problems (Frank, 2001). Shrestha (2020) explained when multicollinearity occurs, the standard errors for each regressor's coefficient broadens and result in retaining hypotheses of insignificant impacts. To test for multicollinearity, Shrestha (2020) recommends Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) as an useful technique for the matter. VIF can be adopted when there are two or more regressors and tend to magnify when two variables are correlated. VIF holding a value between 1 and 5 can interpret the variables as being moderately correlated, however, it is not significant enough to require attention (Shrestha, 2020). Any value more than 5 can recognise the variables to be highly correlated (Shrestha, 2020). Therefore, a VIF value that is greater than 1 and smaller than 5 can be accepted and consider no multicollinearity existing in the regression model. The thesis therefore adopts this method to test for multicollinearity between the dependent variables.

By performing the command "VIF" on the STATA software with the sample's data, the result of the multicollinearity test can be found as follows:

. vif

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ra	1.71	0.584100
la	1.51	0.664335
av	1.23	0.811914
hrd	1.22	0.817127
ac	1.20	0.830643
oc	1.19	0.839418
motiv_	1.16	0.860807
ma	1.09	0.915222
Mean VIF	1.29	

As can be seen above, all explanatory variables from the regression model lie within the range of 1.09 and 1.71. Even though this indicates some correlation degree between the explanatory variables, this is acceptable as suggested by Shrestha (2020). Accordingly, the regression model proposed in this thesis passes the multicollinearity test.

LINEARITY

To test the linearity of a model, a graphic assessment in the form of scatter plots on the explanatory variables and the regressed variable (Osborne and Waters, 2002). The assumption is met when the scatter plots of regressors follow a straight line as the value of the regressed variable increases (Stevens, 2009). If it does not follow a linearity but rather a curved tendency such in c curve or v curve, there is a non-linear relationship between the regressors and the regressed variable (Stevens, 2009).

To examine the linearity, eight scatterplots were performed and the result returned with all straight lines between the crypto investors' performance and each of the regressor which are overconfidence, loss aversion, regret aversion, anchoring, herding,

availability, herding and motivation. Therefore, the linearity assumption for the regression model is met.

4.5. DISCUSSIONS

4.5.1. INTRODUCTION

In this section, the theoretical framework will be revisited in order to assist explaining the findings on each behavioural bias. This paper uses behavioural finance theory which assumes investors often behave irrationally and make decisions based on their emotions. Those behaviours can be assessed through a number of key concepts within behavioural finance such as heuristics, prospect theory and herding.

The author has identified certain behavioural biases, which have been categorised through the key concepts, and how they influence crypto investors' performance. Regarding heuristics, behavioural biases such as overconfidence, anchoring and adjustment as well as availability are assessed to test the hypotheses of their impact on crypto investors' performance. Likewise, loss aversion, regret aversion and mental accounting are grouped under prospect theory with the purpose to identify the relationship between this particular theory to crypto investment outcomes. Finally, researching herding, which is a branch within behavioural finance theory, is crucial due to the extreme volatility, possibility to explain market bubbles and dispute the traditional market theory (Hwang and Salmon, 2004; Bouri, Gupta and Roubaud, 2019; Yao et al., 2014).

The empirical findings that this paper has discovered previously using the regression analysis shall be used to interpret the relationships between the key concepts within behavioural finance theory, review whether there are differences or similarities with previous research in order to demonstrate relevant contributions of the theoretical constructs.

4.5.2. DISCUSSION ON HEURISTICS

Heuristics are mental shortcuts that are used in complex decision-making processes based on past outcomes rather than taking the entire picture into account (Mouni, 2012). As mentioned previously, the key behavioural biases which have been found predominantly to have an effect on investment performance are overconfidence, anchoring and adjustment, and availability (Shah, Ahmad and Mahmood, 2018). The effect of heuristics concept will be examined and discussed firstly via overconfidence, followed by anchoring and adjustment and finally availability.

OVERCONFIDENCE

The regression output shows that overconfidence has a statistically significant and positive impact on crypto investment performance. The test was found to be significant at 1% confidence level. This result is contradictory to the findings in Syarkani and Tristante (2022). Syarkani and Tristante (2022) argue that the higher the overconfidence level, the more likely that will damage crypto investment performance and cause poor investment decisions.

Overconfidence bias occurs when an investor subjectively believes they are more superior by possessing better knowledge, skills, ability and sometimes luck than others. However, it can be considered to be on a degree or a spectrum where either overconfidence can seriously hurt investment experience or enough to support investors and enhance their performance. In the case of this study, it can be explained that cryptocurrency is a highly risky asset class and requires investors to equip with optimism to take on risks. They can be overconfident and also act within their rational boundaries. It is concurred with Parveen et al. (2020) where the authors suggest an overconfident risk taker can still act rationally and achieve abnormal returns on investment. In addition, the descriptive results return a more positive response on their investment satisfaction, compared to their returns on investment. Bonaparte et al. (2017) supported that because of optimism, investment returns might not play the most

important role in the investment experience. Retail investors mostly experience poor returns; however, they are mostly satisfied with their investment decisions due to overconfidence bias (Bonaparte et al., 2017). Hence, this explanation is found to be compatible with the finding on overconfidence bias in this research.

Further relevant research on overconfidence bias can be found in another risky asset class, the stock market. The finding on overconfidence bias is consistent with Abdin et al. (2022), which found overconfidence bias plays a crucial role in enhancing stock investment performance, via risk propensity. The finding is further supported by Riaz and Iqbal (2015), Nareswari et al. (2021) and Rehan and Umer (2017). On the other hand, a large number of previous research suggested otherwise where overconfidence bias can damage investment performance and lead to poor decision making. That can be found in Gervais and Odean (2001), Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), Kirchler and Maciejovsky (2002), Biais et al. (2002), Malmendier and Tate (2005) on corporate investments, and Broekema and Kramer and Liao (2021) through asset diversification.

Since overconfident investors use their mindset of possessing superior abilities and skills as a shortcut to make investment decisions, the finding of the overconfident bias can be said to support the theoretical construct regarding the impact of heuristics concept on crypto investors' outcomes. The judgement on this particular research suggests that where overconfident bias is present, investors may be more likely to take on more risks which can make potentially higher returns in such volatile market as the cryptocurrency markets. In addition, overconfidence or overoptimism can have a greater effect on investment satisfaction. This means that despite the volume of crypto investment returns, investors are nevertheless pleased with what they have achieved. Hence, the author concludes that overconfidence bias can introduce a positive impact on crypto investors' performance as part of the heuristics concept.

Future researchers are suggested to explore a few directions. Using tools such as metrics for risk measurement, volatility as well as investment returns to explain cryptocurrency investors' performance can add more in-depth insights regarding

overconfidence bias. Furthermore, other scholars can further assess the psychological factors and fundamental aspects of an overconfident investor to extensively accelerate their investment outcome. Moreover, since this thesis uses both judgment on retail crypto investors' returns and the associated satisfaction, future researchers can examine the relationships between behavioural biases such as overconfidence and investment returns and the satisfaction separately.

ANCHORING AND ADJUSTMENT

After the assessment with the regression analysis, anchoring bias is reported to have an insignificant and negative effect on crypto investment performance. In other words, it can be said that crypto investors participating in this research are insensitive to the anchoring and adjustment bias. One explanation for this finding is that the sampled investors do not rely heavily on a particular reference point of a cryptocurrency's price. As the vast majority of the respondents invest in BTC which is the fore-most dominant crypto asset in the market and have received attention for its extreme price swings (Gbadebo, Adedokun, Lukman and Akande, 2021). BTC investors might see the deficiency of concentrating on a reference point to make a latter decision, but rather concentrate on their judgements on the latest information and analysis to execute the next move. This encourages investors to adjust their anchors more frequently as well as accordingly and not back the initial anchor for a long amount of time.

Another possible explanation to the insignificance of anchoring bias is because of the data collection time of this research. The data collection was conducted in mid-year 2022 and the cryptocurrency market had been experiencing a huge turmoil since the earlier of the year (Gailey and Haar, 2022). In addition, the collapse of the stable coin LUNA happened in May 2022 which led to the bankruptcy of several hedge funds as well as huge liquidations and further brought the cryptocurrency market into a crisis (Gailey and Haar, 2022). It can be said to have created a remarkable doubt on the future prospect of the cryptocurrency market and have affected retail investors immensely. This could have introduced a potential influence on how the survey respondents

evaluate their returns on crypto investments and their satisfaction at the time of collecting the data. Sicherman et al. (2016) and Jia et al. (2022) stated that anchoring effects tend to wear off during recessions as investors infrequently use past high prices as their anchors when purchasing cryptocurrency. Therefore, the insignificance effect of anchoring bias after the examination in this paper could be the result of this.

As the literature review in the previous chapter suggested, there are no previous papers to the author's knowledge that examine the direct relation between the anchoring and adjustment bias and cryptocurrency investors' performance. However, there is some evidence of the direct relation within the stock and debt markets which are worth mentioning. The insignificant effect of anchoring bias on investment performance was discovered within the debt security market in Nigeria in Babajide and Adetiloye (2012) and Tin and Hii (2020) in Malaysia.

Nonetheless, Waweru et al. (2008) studied how anchoring bias affects investors' performance on the Nairobi Stock Exchange and found a significant and negative impact while Shah et al. (2018) also reported consistent findings on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. In contrast, Aziz and Khan (2016) demonstrate a positive correlation between anchoring bias and equity investors. Similar results are also presented in Ranjbar et al. (2014), Ishfaq and Anjum (2015), Menike et al. (2015), Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Obara (2015).

By reviewing the finding on the anchoring and adjustment bias on crypto investors' outcomes, it can be said it provides challenge to the constructed hypothesis as this paper found an insignificant impact of such bias to crypto investors' performance. Despite the statistical insignificance, the correlation coefficient from the hypothesis testing maintains the negative effect of anchoring and adjustment. Since the hypothesis on this behavioural bias was formed based on a short-term perspective, this assumption might not be applicable. Another critical aspect which was discussed above regarding the data collection period could also be the reason leading to the insignificance result. Future research can further assess different specific time periods or a longer time span

for the purpose of considering a long-term effect. Another direction could be studying the anchoring and adjustment bias with a different measurement to further examine its relation to crypto investment performance.

Regarding the clarification on the theoretical framework constructed in this paper, there is yet no evidence that anchoring and adjustment bias can contribute to produce an effect as a heuristic concept to crypto investors' outcomes.

AVAILABILITY

According to the regression results of this study, availability bias was found to be significant at 5% level of confidence. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and concludes that availability bias has a significant and positive influence on crypto investment performance. The responses collected from the survey of this study indicate crypto investors rely on available information not essentially from friends or trusted people but more on recent security prices. They believe that this could potentially be the momentum if a price of a coin increases or decreases on the day. Ciaian et al. (2016) also confirmed that BTC investors react speedily on new information of BTC which can drive the price higher shortly after.

Another notable point is events of initial coin offerings (ICOs). ICOs can be announced early by crypto exchanges, data aggregators or on social media platforms where investors can receive this kind of information fairly quickly (Fahlenbrach and Frattaroli, 2021). If there is a discussion of social media on the prospect of a new coin, investors tend to overestimate a price jump immediately after an ICO (Fisch and Momtaz, 2020). Furthermore, investors can be more enthusiastic about crypto airdrops where they can receive newly launched cryptocurrencies for free (Merchant, 2022). This is generally good opportunities to gain short-term funds for free by quick sale after an ICO and could improve investment performance. However, it can possibly work if investors only look for short-term goals.

Availability is another behavioural bias that is a very limited researched area within the cryptocurrency market. There are unfortunately no papers, to the author's knowledge, reporting a direct relationship between this bias and the performance of crypto investors. However, it has largely been explored within the stock market. Javed et al. (2017) conducted the research of availability bias on the perceived investment performance and also reported a significant and positive relation between the bias and stock investors' performance. Similarly, Ranjbar et al. (2014) further confirmed the positive effect of availability bias through heuristics and emphasised that it is the main and effective factor which leads to higher investment success. However, Aziz and Khan (2016) addressed a negative and significant relation between availability bias and investment performance of Pakistan stock investors. The findings are further in line with Le and Doan (2011), Qureshi et al. (2012), Nofsingera and Varmab (2013) and Bakar and Yi (2016).

Since availability bias is found to have a significant positive influence on crypto investors' performance, the established hypothesis for this behavioural bias is supported at 5% level of confidence. By revisiting the definition of availability bias, it is considered to be an investor's tendency to make decisions based on readily information rather than conducting in-depth research or assessing the fundamental factors (Read and Grushka, 2011). It is a shortcut to make an investment decision quickly which would save time and resource for an investor. This is aligned with the concept of heuristics, therefore, this finding shed light on the proposed theoretical framework from the author.

Based on the discussion on availability bias on crypto investors' outcomes, the author believes that as BTC is the cryptocurrency asset with the highest market capitalisation according to CoinMarketCap (2023), there might be a potential bias of availability factor towards this particular crypto asset. Future scholars can examine the relation of this behavioural bias through other crypto assets rather than BTC. Furthermore, an investigation on certain crypto assets which recently launched via ICOs and availability bias can also be another suggestion to be further explored.

2.5.3. DISCUSSION ON PROSPECT THEORY

Prospect theory was first introduced as the key theory within behavioural finance by Kahneman and Tversky (1979). According to the theory, investors perceive the value of gain and losses differently which results in the tendency to misestimate the probability associated with each framing scenario (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979). Loss aversion and regret aversion are considered to be the crucial aspects of prospect theory which are crucial for a paper such as this thesis to assess. In addition, the author also investigated the relation of mental accounting bias and crypto investors' performance as it was found to be present within the cryptocurrency markets.

LOSS AVERSION

The regression results suggest loss aversion does not produce a significant impact but has a negative relation with crypto investment performance. Loss aversion, as a part of the prospect theory's branch, is a bias where an investor perceives the level of pain in losing their investment value much more than the joy of gaining it. To put in a simpler sentence, losses loom larger than gains. In the context of this study, demographically speaking, the majority of the sample is made up by single white male investors, aged 18 - 34 and in full-time employment. Rau (2014), Schmidt and Traub (2002), Gächter et al. (2007), and Rieger et al. (2011) reported that women appear to be more loss averse than men. This is due to a lack of willingness to take financial risks and prevent future potential losses (Charness and Gneezy, 2012). Ripley (2019) further demonstrates a research conducted by Bayes Business School with main characteristics of a less loss averse person to be single, healthy, have good financial literacy and in full-time employment. This is in line with the majority of the sample for this study. Being single and in full-time employment also means that they have less worry about providing financially for another person or family as well as the ability to maintain a consistent and sufficient source of income through time. Thus, their risk-taking attitude and

appetite tend to be higher and bigger than other groups of people. That can explain the insignificance of the loss aversion in this paper's findings.

From the cryptocurrency perspective, it is a highly fluctuating and volatile market. Therefore, staying in a position for too long is not technically ideal since that might generate poor returns or lead to a remarkable amount of losses. On the other hand, the main idea of being loss averse is the tendency to be risk-averse when facing a loss and the boiling pressure of not selling just yet. That leads to the rejection of changing into a different situation and the investor rather sticks with the pre-made decision. This tendency is also known as status quo (Xu et al., 2009). In a way, this goes against the nature of investing in the cryptocurrency market when the market is in an extreme state. Hence, loss aversion can minimise returns and hurt satisfaction.

There are no findings from any prior research regarding loss aversion bias and its effect on investment performance within the cryptocurrency market, to the author's knowledge. If the stock markets can be related, Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Sugathadasa (2018) found no significant impact of loss aversion on investment performance, which is similar to this research finding.

However, Al-mansour (2020) studied the influence of prospect theory as a whole on the Arabic crypto investors and found a significant positive effect. It is in contrast to the finding of loss aversion alone in this paper. In the stock markets, there is some evidence which has shown the negative relation of loss aversion with investment performance. It was found in the research of Bouteska and Regaieg (2018) in the United States, Yiwen (2021) in the Chinese stock market, Lee and Veld-Merkoulova (2016) in the Dutch market and Mahina et al. (2017) in the Rwanda stock market. That is consistent with the result on loss aversion within this study. On the other hand, Popova (2020) found that loss aversion drives portfolio optimisation with large amounts of money invested in cryptocurrencies. That suggests that loss aversion could potentially have a positive relation with equity investment performance, however, that is contradictory to the finding in this study.

Since loss aversion does not produce a significant effect based on the finding from this paper, this element can be suggested to be close to absent in order to support prospect theory. However, the result recommends an insignificant and negative relationship between the loss aversion bias and crypto investors' performance. The insignificance outcome certainly set a challenge to the theoretical framework of this thesis. This means that loss aversion bias, as a component of the prospect theory, does not sufficiently produce an impact on crypto investors' performance. As discussed above, the nature of the cryptocurrency markets is highly volatile and fluctuates highly frequently. As investors who are prone to loss aversion can over-hold a position for too long and hurt their performance, crypto investors might recognise and try to avoid this. Nonetheless, some who are risk-seeking could be affected by loss aversion which can explain the negative result according to the finding from this paper.

For future research directions, prospective scholars can potentially study a different region of demographics who have less appetite and attitude for risks. That is for the purpose of searching deeper insights into loss aversion as a singular behavioural bias. Apart from examining crypto investors with less appetite and attitude for risks, other researchers can also study the effect of loss aversion based on different levels of risk-taking profile.

REGRET AVERSION

Regarding the regret aversion bias, the regression output represents an insignificant and negative influence of the bias and the crypto investment performance. Generally speaking, it means that the level of regret aversion that the surveyed respondents have does not suggest a meaningful impact on whether or not they choose to participate in the cryptocurrency market. One of the questions submitted to the sample is "how often do you trade or invest in the cryptocurrency market" which returns with the large number of answers to be either "once every few months" or "monthly", rather than "daily" or "weekly". This suggests a low frequency of investing for the sample. This might give investors more time to carefully evaluate and be well-informed of any

available information to make a decision, rather than making any aggressive and impulsive ones. In addition, investors could potentially focus less and avoid being swayed with their regret emotions and act in a more rational way. Ultimately, it can be considered that the sample for this paper are less sensitive to regret aversion while making their crypto investments.

Loss aversion and regret aversion can seem to be highly similar where investors can become more risk averse and strongly prefer refraining from losses in both cases. However, the most remarkable difference between them is the ability and capacity in making a decision. A loss averse investor finds no difficulty making a decision while a regret averse one can be indecisive or rather not making any at all. Because of past mistakes which make them regret, pain and distress, they tend to withdraw from the same investments or make new ones that might introduce similar results as before. Another case is holding on to not well performing investments with the hope to realise a gain at the end (Shiller, 2003). Cryptocurrencies perform in a highly volatile context so the anticipation for a major reversal in price can also be great. In the case of leveraged trading, holding on a losing asset too long can lead to early liquidation. Generally, regret aversion could prevent cryptocurrency investors from investing opportunities to maximise their profits as well as efficiently diversify their portfolios. Hence, this can be explained for the negative effect that regret aversion has on crypto investment performance.

Similarly to loss aversion bias, there is minimal to no prior research about the immediate impact of regret aversion on investment performance within the cryptocurrency market. However, Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Sugathadasa (2018) found no significant impact of regret aversion on investment performance within the stock market.

If the research of Al-mansour (2020) is considered again for this context, the finding of regret aversion in this paper still appears to be in opposition to the significant and positive impact of prospect theory in Al-mansour (2020). Nonetheless, certain papers

have attempted to assess its influence on the investment outcome of equity investors and in the real estate and the stock market. The significant and negative impact of regret aversion is found in Wangzhou et al. (2021) within the real estate market in developing countries. The authors emphasise on the negative consequence of regret aversion that leads to poor investment decision making. Moreover, more evidence on the negative impact of regret aversion can be found in Isidore and Christie (2019) on the annual income of Indian stock market investors. Similar findings are also addressed in Mellers (2000) and Zeelenberg and Pieters (2004). These related papers however reported the significant impact of regret aversion on investment performance, rather than the insignificant impact which is presented in this research.

The result found that the regret aversion bias has an insignificant and negative influence on crypto investors' performance. This suggests that this bias is less prominent in the context of the cryptocurrency investments. Furthermore, it also proposes the role of regret aversion within the prospect theory can be considered to be absent. Its insignificant but negative effect can be explained by missing out on potential opportunities because of past mistakes or early liquidations due to an anticipation of a price reversal.

For regret aversion bias, the author proposes several directions for future research. Other scholars might be interested to delve into the trading frequency and asset liquidation spans of crypto investors as mediators to connect regret aversion and their investment performance. Another direction is to study other investing behaviour patterns regarding regret aversion within the cryptocurrency markets.

MENTAL ACCOUNTING

For the last behavioural factor, the regression output shows that there is a significant and positive effect of mental accounting on crypto investment performance. The majority of the sample gave a neutral response on the first statement which indicates

they might not code each value of their money based on perceived outcome of each owned crypto asset. Instead, they are concerned about their portfolio's return as a whole. This suggests that crypto investors have strategies to diversify their portfolio and aim for efficient allocations of their capital.

In terms of nature and activity, they tend to create different accounts for past profit and loss as well as the type of each crypto asset owned. The third statement "I hesitate selling coins that recently fell in price but had high returns in the past" received a median evaluation score of 4 and also for the mode. This implies crypto investors have the likelihood of dividing profit and loss of the same cryptocurrency into different compartments. They assign an account for the substantial gain which the cryptocurrency once achieved, and psychologically self-construct some anticipation of that gain to return.

Regarding the type or nature of a crypto asset owned, it is worth mentioning about well-established cryptocurrencies and ICOs. As discussed previously, ICOs can be great opportunities for crypto investors to acquire significant earnings. Crypto investors might treat ICO assets distinguishably from already existing cryptocurrencies. Successful ICOs can bring substantial returns to crypto investors than exposing them to more risks and price fluctuations lying with the already existing cryptocurrencies.

Another side why crypto investors might treat each crypto asset in their portfolio differently is because of the expectation on the future functionality of its blockchain. For example, according to figure 4.5 of this study, XRP received the third highest attention and is built on the blockchain Ripple which is designated to accelerate faster, cheaper and more efficiently in using energy payments (Daly, 2021). Other instances are SOL and ADA. SOL is best known for its blockchain Solana's mission to achieve high speed and small fee transactions (Lee and Madhuranath, 2022); ADA is built by the Cardano blockchain which focuses on providing better security and scalable solutions to smart contracts and decentralised applications (Russo, 2021). By regarding and sorting crypto assets into different applications and categories can reduce price correlations and assist

in diversifying portfolios. Ultimately, these can be the explanations for mental accounting to serve as a behavioural bias that can enhance crypto investors' performance.

Mental accounting within the cryptocurrency market still maintains to be a less researched area, hence, there have been no prior papers documenting its direct effect on the investment performance of crypto investors. However, Al-mansour (2020) attempted to assess the relationship between the general prospect theory factor, including mental accounting, and the Arabic crypto investors. The result suggests a significant and positive impact which in some way, the finding on mental accounting in this thesis can be regarded to. In addition, more related evidence can be found within the stock market with all positive and significant impact. Rashwan and Shaqfa (2021) demonstrate that mental accounting can act as a tool to assist Palestinian stock investors to achieve better investment decisions. The bias can help them to broaden knowledge and improve investing skills. Moreover, mental accounting can encourage investors to reduce errors and support estimating risks and returns more precisely. The result is further in line with Obademi and Ogunlusi (2019) and Mascarenas and Yan (2017). Mascarenas and Yan (2017) indicated that mental accounting can aid managing financial activities based on their risk appetite and lead to expectation fulfilment of an individual investor.

Since the finding suggests that there is a significant and positive influence of mental accounting on crypto investors' outcomes, the role of mental account bias can be said to be present as an element within the prospect theory. This further supports the proposed theoretical framework in this research. The significant positive impact could be a result from planning separate budget for certain prospective and profitable ICOs and treating them differently from usual crypto assets. Another reason that leads to a significant positive effect on investment outcome is when crypto investors identify a number of cryptocurrencies that will consistently develop in the long-term and become valuable assets.

As for future research direction regarding mental accounting bias, the author hopes to encourage more studies on this particular behavioural bias on investors' performance within the cryptocurrency markets. This is due to the absence of any previous research regarding this division. In addition, other scholars can explore the difference in the effect of mental accounting bias on cryptocurrency assets which are divided into a number of categories such as predominant assets, newly releases or ICOs, and such cryptocurrencies invented for purposeful and meaningful functions.

2.5.4. DISCUSSION ON HERDING

In terms of the regression results on the herding bias, it is reported to have significant and positive effect on crypto investment performance. As mentioned previously in the discussion of results for anchoring bias, the cryptocurrency market experienced a significant recession in 2022. Because of this, the market condition was understood to face great volatility and uncertainty which encouraged crypto investors to be more likely to engage with herding behaviour. As there are numerous social platforms where crypto enthusiasts and retail investors can be a part of comprehensive discussions with experts, uncertainty can influence them to follow professional advice or mimic actions of other investors. Another notable point is that crypto transactions are completely transparent to everyone on the blockchain networks. Any movements or transactions associated with well-known, reputable and/or considered "big whales" of the market can also impact one's next investing move.

In addition, 56% of the respondents for the survey of this study answered to have had up to a year of investing experience and an extra of 33% to have had anytime between 1 and 3 years of experience. That together makes up for nearly 90% of the full sample. Lack of experience and expertise may cause an investor less ability to believe in their own judgements and analysis in order to achieve success in trading and investing. Therefore, by following actions of a larger group may generate better results. Furthermore, if everyone as part of the larger group also executes the same buying or selling decision at a particular price, this could potentially cause price speculation in

favour of this group. An investor exercising herding behaviour hence thinks that they could be beneficial because of that.

Herding has recently received great attention from scholars in the past few years as a worth assessing behaviour factor within the cryptocurrency market. However, only a few papers are discovered by the author that reports a direct significant influence on cryptocurrency investment decisions. The result presented above on herding behaviour is in line Jawuta et al. (2022) where the researchers found significant effect of herding behaviours in millennials and gen Z investors. Boxer and Thompson (2020) where they also found positive influence of herding towards crypto purchasing behaviours and investment satisfaction. The results are further agreed by Bouri et al. (2018) when the rolling window model is applied. In addition, this result is further in line with Almansour (2020) when the author conducts his research on Arabic crypto investors.

In terms of the stock market, there are some papers which reported similar findings. Mahmood et al. (2016) found a positive and significant relationship between herding behaviour and investment performance of Pakistan stock market investors. Furthermore, Cao et al. (2021) also reported a significantly positive effect of herding on Vietnamese stock investors' performance, however, it only produces a weak effect. This is further consistent with Le and Doan (2011), Karmacharya et al. (2022), Nareswari, et al. (2021) and Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna (2020).

According to the finding on herding, this behavioural bias produces a significant and positive effect on crypto investors' performance. This confirms the research hypothesis which confirms the aligned relation between herding and crypto investors' performance as proposed in the theoretical framework. By associating with fellow individual investors and experts, a large proportion of crypto investors in this research's sample are identified to have little to three years of investing experience can potentially benefit by following more experienced individual investors. Another reason for such finding is because of the time of data collection. This is when the cryptocurrency market experienced a critical recession and received immense level of uncertainty. During this

market condition, herding can act as a dominant and more comforting behaviour for crypto investors in order to attempt to avoid disappointment.

As mentioned previously, herding has been one of the leading behavioural factors to be studied within the cryptocurrency markets. Furthermore, evidently herding has a great presence amongst crypto investors under behavioural finance theory. By revisiting the time period of the data collection study was in 2022, the crypto market downturn created a high level of uncertainty which can cause economic agents to act irrationally and suffer from emotional biases as the fundamental assumption of behavioural finance theory. According to this, a suggestion for further researchers is to examine the crypto investors' performance during a different time period where the market is more stable or bullish in order to see the effect of herding more comprehensively. Furthermore, other researchers can also adjust and assess different regions of demographic such as concentrating more on senior investors and experts.

2.5.5. DISCUSSION ON MOTIVATIONS

The motivation variable is assigned as a dummy variable for the regression model where 0 is for increasing wealth generally as the biggest motivation and 1 is for belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth as investors' biggest motivation. The result returns a significant and positive correlation between this variable and the performance of crypto investors. Unlike other independent variables which aim to find a causal effect with crypto investment performance, the motivation variable ought to document a non-causal relationship. Although 78% of the sample responded to participate in the cryptocurrency market with "increasing wealth", the other 22% experienced significantly higher returns on investment and satisfaction aggregately.

The insight drawn from the survey report recorded 84% of investors with up to a year of investing experience have "increasing wealth" as their biggest motivation. This implies new investors possibly see cryptocurrency as a way to "get rich quickly" of the

market's extreme volatility. With less than one year of experience, these investors can be overexposed to the risks associated with the market and not have enough knowledge and skills to overcome this matter. Hence, their returns and satisfaction on investment can be much lower than other groups of investors within the sample. Furthermore, the mentality of "get rich quickly" in any group of investors can make them become impulsive or rushing in decision making. Hence, this can lead to financial losses. Newly emerging cryptocurrencies may require properly extensive research and analysis on investments as well as the blockchain they are built on. Without doing this, individual investors can be captivated by the hype and lose a remarkable amount of invested capital if those cryptocurrencies decrease in prices or are revealed to be a scam. It is crucial for investors to be mindful of their motivations and remain careful while making investment decisions rather than letting the desire for quick profits cloud their judgement.

On the other hand, investors who have "belief in decentralisation, free market and democratising wealth" at heart may have had more time exposing themselves to the currency market for a possible amount of time. They might equip themselves with more crypto knowledge and skills to potentially reduce the risk with their investments. Furthermore, understanding the concept of decentralisation can help investors in this category make more informed decisions. Investors who understand decentralisation and the underlying technology (i.e. blockchain) behind cryptocurrencies may be better at evaluating the associated risks and rewards of different investments (Stix, 2021). They may also be more likely to understand the prospective impacts of regulatory and fundamental changes or other external factors on the value of their investments. This is similar to any individuals who are appealed to the ideology of free market as cryptocurrencies are often seen as a way to facilitate free and open markets. Since there are no intermediaries and central authority involved, their prices should solely be determined by supply and demand rather than being managed by anyone.

In addition, democratising wealth means more of a social impact which any investors participating in the cryptocurrency market can bring to the table. Some

cryptocurrencies and blockchain-based projects may align with the goals of impact investors by promoting social or environmental causes or by providing solutions to global challenges. Playing a part in impact investing can therefore increase investment satisfaction, as investors may feel that they have achieved something or are bearing with a bigger mission.

Again, there have been no prior scholars studying the direct relationship between investors' motivations and their performance. However, Mattke et al. (2021) pointed out a key finding where a portion of their sample would still invest in BTC even if they do not anticipate any profits from it and this is to support their ideology and expectation in the future of crypto. This implies that if generating wealth is not necessarily the reason why they invest in BTC, the satisfaction of participation can compensate and make them feel more content with their choice of investment. In other words, their ideology increases their investment satisfaction. Therefore, this piece of literature can be considered to be closest to the finding for motivations suggested in this study.

As the result provides a significant and positive relation between the motivation variable and crypto investor's outcome, the conceptual framework which is proposed in this paper is confirmed and validated. As the motivations do not fall under the behavioural finance theory as an independent variable, the author wishes to emphasise that this variable is added to hopefully generate and contribute new knowledge and deeper understanding about different crypto investor profiles.

Motivation has been a highly researched area within the cryptocurrency market which can be revisited in the literature review of this paper. Previous researchers have examined different types of motivations, and they can vary, be modified or transformed to be more explicit. In the context of this paper, the author aims to inspect the profoundly fundamental motivation and the more secondary motivation. The meaning by having chosen this approach lies greatly with the history of cryptocurrencies and their future prospect as an alternative financial market. The author believes that the

fundamental aspects can range from how cryptocurrencies were created, the decentralised foundation, to the belief in a financial market which can be freer and more democratic with the hope to benefit more on individual investors, whereas the more secondary motivation is mainly to increase wealth. With that being said, the author encourages future researchers with similar opinions can delve into more detailed investing profiles of these two groups with two different types of motivations. Future scholars can further study the relationships of the proposed behavioural factors under the behavioural finance theory and crypto investors' performance under those two groups as separate sample pools.

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. SUMMARY

Traditional financial theories have come under fire for their lack of ability to explain phenomena and the veracity of underlying presumptions (Takahashi and Terano, 2003). Sevil et al. (2007) argue that humans are not perfect and have emotions, hence, these emotions sometimes cause irrationality. This is in contrast to traditional theory where it assumes all market participants are homo economicus and acquire limitless capacity to maximise their own utility in decision making consistently (Brzezicka and Wiśniewski, 2014). Kiyila and Acar (2009) added traditional finance fails to explain investors behaviours and reactions in the real world, thus, behaviour finance emerged and alternatively attempts to explain investment decision making through emotions and cognitive errors.

Within chapter two, this research ought to provide a comprehensive review of literature about a number of behavioural factors, namely overconfidence (Broekema and Kramer, 2021; Von Gaudecker, 2015; Gentile et al., 2016; Kramer and Liao, 2016; Kengatharan and Kengatharan, 2014; Abdin et al., 2022), availability (Read and Grushka, 2011; Khan et al., 2017; Khan, 2015; Ikram, 2016), anchoring and adjustment (Waweru et al., 2008; Shah et al., 2018; Ranjbar et al., 2014; Ishfaq and Anjum, 2015; Menike et al., 2015; Obara, 2015; Kengatharan and Kengatharan, 2014), loss aversion (Bouteska and Regaieg, 2018; Lee et al., 2016; Yiwen, 2021; Mahina et al., 2017; Sugathadasa, 2018), regret aversion (Isidore and Christie, 2019; Wangzhou et al., 2021; Mellers, 2000; Zeelenberg and Pieters, 2004), mental accounting (Rashwan and Shaqfa, 2021; Obademi and Ogunlusi, 2019; Mascarenas and Yan, 2017) and herding (Le and Doan, 2011; Karmacharya et al., 2022; Nareswari et al. 2021; Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna, 2020) across different financial markets and their impacts on investors' performance.

Accordingly, a review of behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market (Hidajat, 2018; Kim et al., 2021; Syarkani and Tristanto, 2022; Xi et al. (2019); Popova, 2020; Gurdgiev and O'Loughlin, 2020; Poyser, 2018; Vidal-Tomás et al., 2018; Ibáñez, & Farinós, 2018; King and Koutmos, 2021; Omane-Adjepong et al., 2021; Ajaz and Kumar, 2018; Gupta and Roubaud, 2018; Ciaian et al. 2015; Al-mansour, 2020) and discussions from the scholars reveal a strong interest in researching investment decisions through the perspective of behavioural finance. However, there is certainly a gap for further research to be conducted. In fact, only Al-mansour (2020) is the only paper providing research findings of direct relationships between different behavioural finance factors and crypto investors' performance. Investment motivations were also found to have produced limited literature which seek to explain their relations to investment performance (Lee et al., 2020; Smutny et al., 2021; Bashir et al., 2016; Khairuddin et al., 2016; Mattke et al., 2020). Hypotheses are then drawn and set a goal to see relationships between different behavioural biases as well as motivations and crypto investors' performance.

Investment performance is suggested to be measured from both subjective and objective perspectives. From an objective point of view, returns on investment have been utilised as a metric to measure investment performance. Botchkarev and Andru (2011) emphasise that return on investment establishes value in reevaluating existing decisions, establishing the basis for future ones, and most significantly, assess investment performance in the most meaningful way. A vast amount of literature (Botchkarev and Andru, 2011; Musa et al., 2021; Wilcox and Moore, 2016; Orbay and Yurtoglu, 2006; Zhang and Zhang, 2021; Ivkovich and Weisbenner, 2003; Park and Kim, 2014; Khan and Ahmed, 2022) has been found to have adopted returns on investment as their tool to measure investment performance. From the subjective point of view, investment satisfaction is considered as it is widely used in the behavioural field. Oberlechner and Osler (2008) argue that professional performance can be regarded in different dimensions, and not only just profitability. The adoption of investment satisfaction as a measurement can be found within numerous prior papers such as Lee et al. (2010), Khan, Afrin and Rahman (2015), Boda, Guniganti and Ray (2017), Ainia and Lufyi (2018), Keswani, Dhingra and Wadhwa (2019), Cao et al. (2020) and Bairagi

and Chakraborty (2021). For investment satisfaction, four elements including buying and selling decisions, asset allocation and trading volume are assessed.

Subsequently, chapter three provides theoretical discussions on relevant research methods and highlights the chosen ones. Positivism approach suggested by Saunders et al. (2019) is selected since the minds of cryptocurrency investors are separated and external from the researcher. Guba and Lincoln (1994) further points out it is an ideal research framework in order to study the correlation between social variables. Positivism also focuses more on understanding a social phenomenon's causes and effects, whereas interpretivism seeks to comprehend a phenomenon's real meanings (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988; Neuman, 2000). In terms of research approach, deductive is chosen as behavioural finance is used as an existing theory with the assumption that investors are irrational and to construct testing hypotheses for the behavioural factors within the cryptocurrency market (Saunders et al., 2019; Bryman et al, 2015). Deductive approach is deemed to be more relevant as positivism is previously selected. It is also a beneficial tool for quantitative research (Saunders et al., 2019).

For research design, a combination of descriptive and explanatory is set to be the purpose of this study as it seeks to find causal relationships between behavioural factors and investment performance and portrays crypto investors with different investment motivations. Accordingly, the quantitative method and surveys are determined to be the research strategies for the data analysis and collection. The sample consists of 264 crypto individual investors using voluntary response sampling under non-probability sampling design (Saunders et al., 2019). In terms of data analysis methods, descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, ANOVA, t-statistics and multiple regression modelling are adopted to test the significance and relationships between behavioural factors, motivations and crypto investors' performance. Further testing for regression assumptions is also conducted to enhance the robustness of the model.

Chapter four provides research findings on the relationships between overconfidence, loss aversion, regret aversion, anchoring, availability, herding, mental accounting and crypto investors' performance. This chapter also reported the correlation between investment motivations and investment performance. A summary of research findings can be found in the next section.

5.2. RESEARCH FINDINGS

This section summarises the research findings as follows:

- Overconfidence has a statistically significant and positive impact on crypto investment performance which is contradictory to the findings in Syarkani and Tristante (2022). Investors can be overconfident and also act within their rational boundaries. Furthermore, an overconfident risk taker can still act rationally and achieve abnormal returns on investment (Parveen et al., 2020). Bonaparte et al. (2017) added due to overconfidence bias, individual investors typically see low returns, yet they are generally happy with their investment choices. This finding is found to be consistent with Abdin et al. (2022), Riaz and Iqbal (2015), Nareswari et al. (2021) and Rehan and Umer (2017) in the stock market. However, Gervais and Odean (2001), Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014), Kirchler and Maciejovsky (2002), Biais et al. (2002), Malmendier and Tate (2005) and Broekema and Kramer (2021) reported negative influence of overconfidence towards equity investors. In terms of theoretical contribution, this finding of overconfidence bias supports the heuristics concept within behavioural finance theory and offers crypto investors benefits to their investment performance.
- Loss aversion does not produce a significant impact but has a negative relation with crypto investment performance. The descriptive statistics reported a majority of the sample consisting young, single male investors and are in full-

time employment. Being single and working full-time means they have less worry about supporting a family or other people financially, and they can continue to have a steady and adequate source of income throughout time. Hence, they can be more risk taking and less loss averse. Rau (2014), Schmidt and Traub (2002), Gächter et al. (2007), and Rieger et al. (2011) also documented that men tend to be less loss averse than women. From the cryptocurrency perspective, high volatility suggests that investors may experience poor returns or even substantial losses if they stay in one position for too long. Being more risk taking when experiencing unrealised losses can seriously damage one's investment performance. This finding is in line with Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Sugathadasa (2018) in the stock market. Regarding the contribution to the underpinned theory, this finding does not indicate backing the prospect theory.

- Regret aversion has an insignificant and negative influence of bias and the crypto investment performance. The survey results reveal the sample consists of low trading frequency. This indicates investors might have more time to deliberate and be well-informed on all relevant facts before making a decision, as opposed to acting hastily and irrationally. Moreover, investors could potentially less concentrate and avoid being swayed with their regret emotions and act in a more rational way accordingly. However, past mistakes can make investors avoid investments due to distress and regretfulness which could minimise investment returns. Cryptocurrencies are also highly speculative and volatile, hence, holding on a coin that is not performing well due to regrets of potential price reversal can have a negative effect on investment performance. Kengatharan and Kengatharan (2014) and Sugathadasa (2018) also found an insignificant effect of loss aversion on stock investors' performance. Similarly to loss aversion, the finding for regret aversion also does not back the concept of prospect theory in the context of this study.

- Anchoring bias is reported to have an insignificant and negative effect on crypto investment performance. Because of extreme price swings, BTC investors may recognise the need to focus on their judgements on the most recent data and analysis to execute the next move rather than a reference point to make a later decision. Furthermore, the data was collected in mid 2022 after the cryptocurrency market experienced a crisis due to the collapse of LUNA (Gailey and Haar, 2022). Anchoring effects tend to fade away during recessions as investors infrequently use historical prices as their anchors when investing in cryptocurrencies (Sicherman et al., 2016; Jia et al., 2022). Similar findings on the insignificant effect of anchoring was reported in Babajide and Adetiloye (2012) and Tin and Hii (2020). In terms of theoretical contribution, the result found for anchoring bias does not support the concept of heuristics linking to crypto investors' outcomes.
- Herding is found to have a significant and positive effect on crypto investment performance. Due to the market condition mentioned above, uncertainty and great volatility may encourage investors to be more likely to exhibit herding behaviour. The sample also consists of investors with lack of trading experience which may cause crypto investors to believe less on their own analysis and judgements. Nonetheless, price speculation in favour of the bigger group may produce significant returns quickly. This result is in line with Jawuta et al. (2022), Boxer and Thompson (2020), Bouri et al. (2018), Al-mansour (2020) within the cryptocurrency market. In the equity market, Mahmood et al. (2016), Cao et al. (2021), Le and Doan (2011), Karmacharya et al. (2022), Nareswari, et al. (2021) and Hamidon and Kehelwalatenna (2020) also documented alike effect of herding on investors' performance. The significant and positive effect finding implies a strong presence of this factor within the crypto market and also supports the proposed theoretical framework.
- Availability bias has a significant and positive effect on crypto investors' performance. It is understood that sampled investors rely more on asset prices

and less on people they know. They think that this might perhaps be the momentum if a coin's price rises or falls that day. In terms of ICOs, early information on an emergence of a new coin would highly benefit investors profit-wise if that coin turns out to be a successful one. This is consistent with the finding of Javed et al. (2017), Ranjbar et al. (2014) and in contradictory with Aziz and Khan (2016), Le and Doan (2011), Qureshi et al. (2012), Nofsingera and Varmab (2013) and Bakar and Yi (2016) within the stock market. According to this research finding, it can be concluded that availability bias supports the heuristics concept within behavioural finance theory and indicates a significant relation between the concept and crypto investors' performance.

- Mental accounting is reported to have a significant and positive impact on crypto investors' performance. The descriptive statistics suggest sampled crypto investors care more about their portfolio's return as a whole. This could mean crypto investors have strategies to diversify their portfolio and pursue effective capital allocation. The results further suggest that they have the likelihood of dividing profit and loss of the same cryptocurrency into different compartments. In addition, crypto investors might treat each crypto asset in their portfolio differently because of the expectation on the future functionality of its blockchain. This can help to reduce price correlations and diversify portfolios by categorising and arranging crypto assets according to various applications, thus, contributes to enhancing crypto investment performance. This finding is consistent with Rashwan and Shaqfa (2021), Obademi and Ogunlusi (2019) and Mascarenas and Yan (2017) within the stock market. Since mental accounting produces a significant and positive effect to the crypto performance of retail investors, the theoretical framework in this study is confirmed for the validation of the prospect theory.
- Motivation variable is found to have a significant and positive influence on crypto investment performance, meaning that investors with primary motivation due to their belief in decentralisation, blockchain, free market and democratising

wealth experience better investment performance. With less than a year of experience, the majority of the sample may be overexposed to market dangers and lack the knowledge and skills necessary to deal with them. Hence, returns on investment and satisfaction can be lower than other groups of the sample. Moreover, any group of investors with a "get rich quick" mentality run the risk of making rash or impulsive decisions. Consequently, this may result in monetary losses. It may be necessary to also conduct thorough research and analysis on investments and the blockchain that newly emerging cryptocurrencies are based on, in order to avoid potential losses. On the other hand, investors who have "belief in decentralisation, blockchain, free market and democratising wealth" may have had more time to be more familiar with the fundamental aspects of the cryptocurrency market and how external factors can affect their investment decision making. Investors of this type can also be more of activist investors which aim to introduce social impact to the bigger crowd. Thus, playing a part in impact investing can therefore increase investment satisfaction.

5.3. RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

The following are a number of ways that this research can benefit the existing knowledge and policy makers:

- The review of literature on behavioural finance within the cryptocurrency market leaves a gap for more research to be conducted within the field. This thesis attempts to fill this gap by assessing the impacts of overconfidence, loss aversion, regret aversion, anchoring and adjustment, herding, availability and mental accounting on crypto investors' performance. The author further studied the relationship between investment performance and two primary investment motivations which are generating wealth and belief in decentralisation, blockchain, free market and democratising wealth. At the time of writing and to the author's knowledge after extensive search, there are no prior papers documenting the relations between different investment motivations and crypto

investors' performance. Thus, this thesis can be considered the first paper to do so. Furthermore, investment performance consists of both subjective and objective perspectives which aims to provide more aggregate results.

- The study applies the behavioural finance theory, including prospect theory, to assess some existing behavioural finance factors within the cryptocurrency market. The regression results reported some biases that have significant and positive influence on crypto investors' performance. They are overconfidence bias, herding, availability and mental accounting. The findings contribute to new research findings, especially within cryptocurrency which currently has very limited related studies on these biases' impact. Relevant research reporting similar effects mostly lie within different stock markets across the world.
- In terms of the proposed theoretical framework previously in this study, some branches are confirmed for validation and significant relations such as overconfidence and availability under heuristics concept, mental accounting under prospect theory and herding. These behavioural factors all produced a significant and positive influence on crypto investors' performance, implying that behavioural finance theory could be said to have an effective impact to investment outcome within the cryptocurrency markets.
- Prospect theory introduces the most significant two factors: loss aversion and regret aversion while mental accounting is a smaller branch compared to the other two. However, the regression results showed that only mental accounting has a significant effect on crypto investors' performance.
- By providing relevant research findings within the field of behavioural economics and finance, the paper suggests some positive impacts of behavioural factors on crypto investors' performance. This demonstrates the need for policy makers and other authorities to promote and encourage more talent to

participate and create technology innovations, in order to design personalised financial plans to help crypto individual investors.

5.4. PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The results found in this research paper also attempt to provide some practical implications to individual investors and financial advisors as follows:

- Based on the regression results from this study, overconfidence and availability showed a significant and positive effect on crypto investors' performance. This might encourage individual investors to be more risk taking and believe more in their ability and knowledge. The results further suggest that both individual and institutional investors should concentrate more on recent crypto prices to enhance performance.
- Mental accounting also reported a significant and positive effect on crypto investors' performance. Another implication to retail investors is that they should account for returns on their whole portfolio, and not returns of each asset separately. However, by considering different crypto assets differently by their nature, applications and blockchain networks may benefit investment performance. This could help individual investors and financial advisors to construct more efficient portfolio diversification to enhance their performance.
- Herding is found to have a significant and positive effect on crypto investors' performance. Discussions on herding suggest that both types of investors can be benefitted by following the move of the majority market. This can improve short term quick profits. Furthermore, new investors with limited resources and knowledge can also exploit herd behaviour to expand their profits.

5.5. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

There are several limitations that readers should be aware when considering the data results and research findings. One of the limitations associated with this research is the sampling method. The study consists of 264 crypto investors, recruiting from online channels and platforms using non-probability sampling. More random and bigger samples are needed to provide more generalised results. Hence, future research is recommended to adopt random sampling and recruit more investors. Moreover, other scholars could expand the scope of this study by applying qualitative or mixed methods to provide more insights and verification of the research findings, especially for the investment motivation variable. Another limitation is survey collection time.

The study aims to assess the overall investment experience; however, recent events could have potentially affected investors' emotions and reactions as well as the self-evaluation. Future research hence can contribute by collecting data that is more time specific. Moreover, other scholars can examine some particular impact levels of each behavioural factor on crypto investors' performance. If other researchers are more interested in investigating one or more specific factors with significant effect, the author can address certain directions for each of them. For the overconfidence bias, future researchers may wish to look at some risk measurements and the overall profile of an overconfident crypto investor for more in-depth insights. For availability bias, the author encourages more future research on the relationship between this factor and altcoins as well as ICOs as the sample from this paper might be more inclined towards BTC investors. Regarding mental accounting bias, other scholars can explore the difference in the effect of mental accounting bias on cryptocurrency assets which are divided into a number of categories such as predominant assets, newly released or ICOs, and such cryptocurrencies invented for purposeful and meaningful applications. For the herding factor, apart from the need to examine data in a different period, this bias can be studied when senior investors and experts are consolidated as a research sample. Finally, for the motivation factor, scholars can further analyse the relationships of the

behavioural biases under the behavioural finance theory and crypto investors' performance under those two groups as separate sample pools.

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